

Foundations of Unitary Quantum Mechanics

Lecture Notes

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Preface

Many physicists have no formal training in philosophy. Yet, as we shall see, when working at the edge of physics, progress comes from conjectures, speculations and guesses. A good philosophy of science can thus guide new conjectures. In other branches of physics, where the primary focus lies on predictions, calculating observables, and developing technologies rooted in well-established science, the role of philosophy might be easier to overlook. Yet, in the foundations of quantum mechanics, the friction between different philosophies of science becomes unmistakably apparent. One of the reasons behind the proliferation of quantum interpretations is that there is no consensus on the philosophy of science.

Among the blur of implicit philosophies, here I mention two that permeate the community. Instrumentalism and realism. Instrumentalism is driven by empirical observations, and the role of experiments is to increase credence in favour of a particular theory. In this view, better theories are the ones that give better predictions. In contrast, some realist philosophies of science frequently build on Popper and regard fundamental science as explanatory [37, 40]. The purpose of science is then not mapped to a particular prediction, but to conjecture explanations that specify an ontology and how it behaves. Theories that follow this philosophy do not rely on credence. Instead of finding a theory with high credence, scientific methodology finds flaws and deficiencies in a given explanation and seeks to replace it with a better one.

In most scientific disciplines, realism has traditionally been the dominant perspective. Regrettably, in the case of the most fundamental theory in science – quantum mechanics – a significant shift in the philosophical outlook has occurred. This shift, perhaps driven by historical and sociological factors, briefly provoked an instrumentalist stance. As a student, I was nearly swayed by the prevailing instrumentalist interpretations of quantum mechanics. It seemed as if there were no alternatives but to *shut up and calculate*, and *nobody understands quantum mechanics*. It felt as though a deep understanding of physics was elusive. Regrettably, for a considerable period, my enthusiasm for daring conjectures waned, and I spent years calculating observables without truly comprehending the underlying reality. Unfortunately, this is often what the job market demands of most of us.

However, the spark that initially drew me to physics never extinguished. After some mathematical training, I came across philosophers of physics such as Karl Popper, Tim Maudlin and David Deutsch. They demonstrated that simplicity, profound contemplation, and genuine understanding still thrive in science. During a holiday, I stumbled upon a paper by Hugh Everett, published in 1957. I decided to read this seemingly eccentric paper at least once in my life. To my surprise, it turned out to be one of the most pivotal papers in my understanding of quantum mechanics. It contained answers to many of my questions, all presented with a mathematical clarity accessible even to high school readers. Sadly, at the time, Everett's paper was met with skepticism from the scientific community, which had contributed to both substantial advancements in quantum mechanics and a philosophical crisis. Eventually, Everett's ideas were resurrected, but an unfortunate choice of labelling dubbed it the *many-worlds interpretation* of quantum mechanics [43].

These lecture notes explore recent developments in the foundations of unitary quantum mechanics. They are biased towards the Everettian view. Yet, the contents here is just unitary quantum mechanics, which may even be useful to a Qubist world-view. Nothing presented here is entirely

novel. Instead, my goal is to assemble a didactic collection of recent advancements in the field. These advancements demonstrate that the mathematical framework of quantum mechanics need not be mutilated, supplemented, or made non-local to gain a profound understanding of quantum theory. On the contrary, I aim to illustrate that by embracing a minimalist perspective rooted in unitary quantum theory, one can abandon non-realist philosophies, rekindle the spirit of inquiry, and genuinely grasp the essence of quantum mechanics.

These are rudimentary notes evolved from lecture slides I developed for elective graduate and undergraduate physics courses at Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, which I have been teaching since 2022. For any suggestions or comments, please feel free to reach out to me at mockli@ufrgs.br.

David Möckli, Porto Alegre, Brazil, March 9, 2024.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Memes about quantum mechanics are very popular. I am sure the reader knows some of them. Some memes are printed on T-shirts and read "Schrödinger's cat wanted, dead and alive." Other memes, show a person looking at the double-slit experiment, and when they look away, an interference pattern suddenly appears, as if this were a discrete process. One of my favourites (sarcasm) is a shirt saying *what part of the Schrödinger equation don't you understand?* Even as a professional physicist, I asked myself: do I understand? I did not, and probably also not physics students proudly wearing their shirts. Or is the shirt praising ignorance?

These are famous memes, but most physicists do not know the answers to the paradoxes. It's not their fault. We still learn quantum mechanics via a set of unquestionable postulates, as if, there were no better options. Also, in most physics curricula, quantum mechanics is left as a pair of heavy courses at the very end. There is just no time to savour understanding. We instead focus on calculating observables. In case you are an instrumentalist, let me tell you in advance that I spend very little time calculating observables in this book. This book is about the pleasure of understanding what nature is really doing. We of course do not know, but the aim is to reach the best approximation available.

To understand the apparent paradoxes of quantum mechanics, we must not only understand the quantum mechanics of the small but also of the big. After all, I believe it is uncontroversial to say that the big stuff is made up of the smaller stuff. Yet, archaic interpretations of quantum mechanics, such as the Copenhagen-type interpretations, prevent us from understanding exactly this: how the properties of the large emerge from the small.

A great deal of progress was provoked by the field of decoherence, which partly explains the transition from the small to the big. However, the role of the decoherence program is not only to show how classical behaviour emerges from the quantum but also how the classical is quantum.

Quantum theory (and its derivatives) is the most fundamental theory in physics there is. As frequently advertised, it is not the physics of the small. To calculate the macroscopic specific heat (or any other thermodynamic quantity) of any equilibrium system around you, we need quantum mechanics. Whether an object is hard or soft, is of course an emergent macroscopic property explained by quantum mechanics. What about macroscopic superposition states? There are now several of them. As an example: superconductivity only survives in a macroscopic uncollapsed entangled wavefunction. If there were collapse in a superconductor, a finite resistivity would immediately arise.

Most physicists have no training in philosophy, myself included. Yet, historically, philosophy and physics always coexisted hand in hand. At the moment there seems to be an artificial chasm between physics and philosophy and even animosity. Part of the proliferation of many interpretations of quantum mechanics is that there is no consensus on the philosophy of science. Since most of us have no philosophical training, each of us develops an internal and pseudo-self-consistent way of

seeing the world. It seems that many of the quandaries encountered in the debates about quantum mechanics could be alleviated if there were clarity on the different philosophies of science adopted by different researchers.

The objective of this chapter is not to survey the several philosophies of science. The aim is to state one good philosophy of science, which will orient the rest of the book. The philosophy adopted here will be of a realist stance, which contrasts with the instrumentalist. The reason for returning to realism in quantum mechanics is not only to show that quantum mechanics can be local, complete and describe real stuff; but also to demonstrate that different philosophies of science orient different research programs. In the author's current opinion (perhaps ask me again in a decade), research programs based on scientific realism provoke more progress.

1.2 Philosophical profiles

Through discussions with both students and researchers over the years, one quickly reaches the conclusion that there is no consensus on the working philosophy of science among practitioners of quantum mechanics. Many of the charged debates could be alleviated if individuals were more aware of the philosophical background from which others approach the subject. I have observed a range of implicit world-views and preconceptions, which naturally shape participants' expectations for this course. While the course has generally been well-received, with positive feedback from many participants, some have found it too focused on foundational aspects. I take this feedback seriously, as it aligns with the course's objectives. Below, I provide a very crude sample of the profiles I have encountered and outline their typical reactions to the course.

1.2.1 The instrumentalist

This is not the dominant profile in science in general, but some think that quantum mechanics forced us into this category. Instrumentalists generally emphasise the empirical success of the theory. They are concerned about the pragmatic practical slide of the theory, and less concerned about whether the deeper explanation refers to some underlying reality. The most acute version of empiricists considers that the world can only be studied through instruments. For them, the existence of iron cores in stars or the interior of black holes is rather controversial, because although our theories do describe stellar objects' interiors, our instruments do not access them. Mathematics is then just a tool of the user to develop applications and has no direct relation to reality. Reality is in the eye of the beholder.

Based on surveys on interpretations of quantum mechanics [93, 108, 113], I speculate that this is an uncommon view even among orthodox stances. This profile would likely remain uninterested in these lecture notes, since the problems that motivate this course, are no problems at all for the hardcore instrumentalist.

1.2.2 The orthodox

The orthodox thinks that quantum mechanics is something that cannot be widely understood and is likely to remain obscured from the general public. They think that understanding can only be accessed through the teachings of specific founders of quantum mechanics. They seem to be instrumentalists of the mind, meaning that what we feel is right, must be right. This originates dualist world-views, where people feel comfortable with the fact that there are two irreducible principles of the world. Universality is not possible.

This stance is common, not only among students but also among the first developers of quantum mechanics, most notably Bohr. It is the type of view that speaks of both particles and waves at

the same time, something being at multiple places at the same time, subjective observer-dependent phenomena, and the mind-body question.

Most people in this profile reject quantum esotericism as chicanery. However, they often do not realise that the very ideas they dearly hold on to originated quantum esotericism (see Ref. [73]). As physicists, we of course have the burden of patiently showing people that there is nothing esoteric about physics, but we are not exempt of fault. Current esoteric movement often base their ideas on the founders.

To my surprise, many orthodox oriented readers found the course instructive, as they learned that there are formulations of quantum mechanics that dispense with dualism altogether.

1.2.3 The relativist

This is an increasingly popular view in quantum mechanics, largely based on Rovelli's relational quantum mechanics, which took inspiration also from the theory of relativity [102]. Relativism recognises reality with respect to a particular reference frame. Therefore, it is frequently considered perspectival and contextual. However, relativism often rejects a single objective truth, as there is no absolute reference frame. Relativism often provides a bridge between instrumentalism and realism. For a modern philosophical treatment, the reader may consult Ref. [83].

1.2.4 The realist

This view rejects anthropocentrism. Realist stances usually assert that there is an objective observer independent reality. They do not necessarily believe in objective truth, but consider our best available theory as the best approximations. This is a common view in science and philosophy, but lost ground in quantum mechanics, due to its apparent and mistaken necessity to abandon realism. Part of this course is to show that, unlike frequently advertised, realist formulations of quantum mechanics remain available.

Realists are often considered as too detached from reality. This is of course a paradox. What they probably mean is that realists lack pragmatism, which is likely indeed the case. Realist value more the deeper explanation than the theories' predictions.

1.2.5 World-views

The dispute between instrumentalism and realism is often exemplified by the Bohr–Einstein debates. In Fig. 1.1, we summarize the controversy in the philosophy of physics. Consider three observers: Anakin, Bilbo, and Chewbacca. A visual barrier obstructs the direct perception between Anakin and Bilbo. While the laws of physics allow the barrier to be removed, assume that current technology has not yet made this possible. There is no barrier between Anakin and Chewbacca or between Chewbacca and Bilbo. Therefore, although Anakin and Bilbo cannot see each other, they may become aware of each other's existence by communicating through Chewbacca as an intermediary. The thick dashed lines illustrate the uncontroversial part in the philosophy of physics. In most philosophies of physics, except perhaps for an anti-realist stance, Anakin/Chewbacca and Chewbacca/Bilbo can verify their existence. I speculate that most of us have no problem in saying that even though Anakin does not see Bilbo directly, it is still acceptable for Anakin to consider Bilbo as real. I guess that most of us have no issue in taking other countries that we never visited seriously. However, this is where things get controversial. Based on Fig. 1.1, we might identify three levels of reality:

1. The direct dashed lines. Anakin/Chewbacca and Chewbacca/Bilbo. This is the lowest level and most uncontroversial criterion for reality. Specialised philosophical literature sometimes refers to this direct perception as the *gold standard*. The gold standard is usually associated to an instrumentalist stance. Example quantum interpretations are Copenhagen and Qubism.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of different worldviews.

2. The interrupted thin dashed line between Anakin and Bilbo. Anakin might admit the existence of Bilbo only if there is an intermediary (Chewbacca) that can see Bilbo and Anakin via a gold standard. However, if the intermediary lacks, then Anakin must abstain from believing in Bilbo. This second level of reality is commonly associated with a relational stance.
3. A realist has no problem considering Bilbo real, even if the barrier is never removed, and even if there is no intermediary. However, Bilbo will still consider Anakin as real if Bilbo is part of the explanatory theory. For the realist, there are unseen elements whose role is explanatory. Example interpretations are Everett and Bohm.

In the Copenhagen interpretation of quantum mechanics, things get even weirder. If Anakin sees Chewbacca, Bilbo will be obliterated. These ideas infect many textbooks, and will not be much entertained throughout this course.

1.3 Good theories

According to Maudlin [86], a good scientific fundamental theory specifies two things:

1. What exists (the ontology);
2. How the things that exist move (the dynamics).

We of course do not know whether the conjectured ontology appropriately describes reality. However, proposing an ontology and dynamics gives clarity and provides better predictions. But this is not all. More importantly, a good theory is a good explanation.

Let us use classical mechanics as the less controversial example. Consider Newton's second law of motion of a point particle $\mathbf{F} = m\mathbf{a}$. Loosely speaking, what ontology does the law suggest? The particle of mass m . Also, the particle experiences a force which is communicated by other particles. I am not mentioning fields just to keep things simple at the moment. How does the particle move? It moves according to the law of motion $\mathbf{F} = m\mathbf{a}$, and the trajectory is obtained by solving the law.

The instrumentalist might of course dispense the ontology completely and only speak of probabilities of observing the particle in a given place. The laws would then just be mathematical information devices, which serve to deliver some credence to an agent. Even in this case, the instrumentalist might still think of the situation *as if* particles existed.

How do we improve our best explanations? According to Deutsch [37, 40], a good theory is one that is universal, more testable than its rivals, and all the details matter. In this view, science is explanatory. The purpose of science is then not mapped to a particular prediction, but to conjecture explanations that specify an ontology and how it behaves. Theories that follow this philosophy do not rely on credence. Instead of finding a theory with high credence, scientific methodology finds flaws and deficiencies in a given explanation and seeks to replace it with a better one. Within this approach, one of two rival theories might be refuted. Deutsch draws from Popper's scientific methodology in which a good theory is never confirmed; instead, bad theories are refuted and replaced by better theories. Paraphrasing Ref. [40], a bad theory is one that:

- (i) does not account for the objects of the explanation; or
- (ii) conflicts with other good theories (theories that observe the opposites of criteria (i) and (iii));
or,
- (iii) is easy to vary.

If a theory displays at least one of the properties above, then it can be made problematic, which then motivates a scientific problem. Therefore, a scientific theory can only be refuted if it has a better rival according to these criteria. If it has no rival, it can at most be made problematic by the same criteria. A crucial scientific test could be an experiment that allows the identification of a better theory.

1.4 Bad theories and orthodoxy

Given the properties of the previous section, let us analyse if according to the criteria, orthodox Copenhagen-type interpretations are good or bad theories. Most introductory textbooks on quantum mechanics present the theory specifying a system's behaviour under two different circumstances.

1. Without monitoring. A state vector $|\Psi\rangle$ describes the system. The state evolves according to the Schrödinger equation

$$i\hbar\frac{d}{dt}|\Psi(t)\rangle = \mathcal{H}|\Psi(t)\rangle. \quad (1.1)$$

2. Under monitoring. The state vector *collapses* to a specific vector $|X\rangle$. The probability of observing X is given by the Born rule

$$p(X) = |\langle X|\Psi\rangle|^2. \quad (1.2)$$

The Born rule is well-established experimentally, and its instrumental success is uncontroversial. The fact that there are two sets of rules, already introduces a non-universality, since under some conditions we should apply one equation, and under other circumstances another equation. Also, what defines a monitoring device? Aren't monitors made up of quantum mechanical stuff as well? How do we identify the cut between the system being monitored by the monitor?

Note that, in principle, one could try to ignore the Born rule. Then, one would have a state $|\Psi\rangle$ to which one might attempt to associate an ontology. The dynamics is then given by the Schrödinger equation. To the authors' knowledge, the first one to attempt such a research program

was Schrödinger. Such a program would be aligned with the criteria of a good theory introduced in the previous section but has the challenge of explaining the Born rule. More on this in later chapters.

As we shall see, many interpret the Born rule simply as a projection of a state in Hilbert space, but without obliterating all the other states. That is, the monitor sees only a shadow of the full state. However, Copenhagen-type interpretations usually speak of a discrete reduction of the state vector, usually called a *collapse*. Contact with a more fundamental classical monitor is required to trigger a collapse. Furthermore, collapses are intrinsically random. This means that for the first time in physics, probability is introduced as an intrinsic property of the system. This is unlike statistical mechanics, where probability arises not because classical mechanics is deterministic, but because the user is partially ignorant about the exact microstate of the system. However, it is worth mentioning that even in classical statistical physics, the interpretation of probability is still a debated topic.

How do Copenhagen-type interpretations introduce the cut between the fundamental classical and the quantum system? They introduce an artificial and subjective *Heisenberg cut*, which is movable and subjected to the user's convenience. At the risk of stating the obvious, there should be no cut in fundamental physics, as there is nothing fundamentally different between the monitor and the monitored. Moreover, the dynamics of the supposed *collapse* is not described, and simply treated as a discrete process. Also, the state vector $|\Psi\rangle$ contains information about the state of the system but has no dynamic value. These types of interpretations do not explain why some outcomes are observed, and others not. The reduction of the state vector introduces spurious effects, similar to instantaneous non-local effects, as present in Newtonian gravity.

Enough with the blabber, and let us evaluate whether Copenhagen is a candidate for a good theory. Test number one: In Copenhagen, what does exist? Copenhagen does not specify. Real things apparently exist at the classical level, but one must abstain from reality while the system behaves quantumly. Is there dynamics? Dynamics of what? Information? Information carried by what? It seems that Copenhagen does not even classify as a candidate theory according to the philosophy suggested in Sec. 1.3. But there are of course other positivist and instrumentalist philosophies that do accommodate Copenhagen-type interpretations. According to Deutsch's criteria [37, 40], Copenhagen lacks a clear ontology, lacks universality, has a Heisenberg cut that is easy to vary, the transition from the classical to quantum is untestable and many details don't matter (just like folklore).

Yet, are there better rival theories according to the criteria? Yes. Consider for example pilot-wave theory. There might exist even better rival theories, but we use pilot-wave theory just for the argument of rivalling it with Copenhagen. Pilot-wave theory modifies quantum mechanics but does account for the objects of the explanation. The ontology is defined as a pilot-wave that is governed by the Schrödinger equation. But this is not all. There are also particles that are governed by a particle-guiding equation. Therefore, ontology and dynamics are well specified. It classifies as a candidate good theory. For now. Ignoring other good theories for now, pilot-wave theory does not conflict with other good theories. Compared to Copenhagen, pilot-wave theory is harder to vary, as there is no Heisenberg cut. We shall see that when compared to Everettian mechanics, which is just the pilot-wave part, the particles are the part that can be ignored, and hence will be easy to vary. We will get there.

1.5 The importance of explanations

As an example, let me quote a paragraph from *The book of why* by Judea Pearl [95]:

Let me give you an example in which probabilities make all the difference. It echoes the public debate that erupted in Europe when the smallpox vaccine was first introduced. Unexpectedly, data showed that more people died from smallpox inoculations than from

smallpox itself. Naturally, some people used this information to argue that inoculation should be banned, when in fact it was saving lives by eradicating smallpox.

A mad-dog instrumentalist would look at the data, and conclude that since inoculations are killing people, vaccinations should stop. The reason why inoculations continue comes from the deeper unobserved explanation. The explanation is that while the vaccines indeed do kill some people, the amount of people smallpox would kill vastly outnumbers the number of people the vaccines kill. If not for the vaccines, millions of children would die. Hence, inoculations are in fact saving, not killing, people. Yet, the explanation remains unobserved, since it relies on a counterfactual possibility. It is not because counterfactuals are not observed, that the deeper explanation is ignored. On the contrary.

This is one of many examples where different philosophies suggest different actions, with radically different effects. In quantum mechanics, adopting a bad philosophy might not kill people, but it greatly hinders scientific progress, which likely hurts us in the long term.

1.6 Science is strange

The philosophy suggested in Sec. 1.3 might lead to what humans find strange theories. By providing good explanations, one frequently explains the seen by the unseen. But this does not invite esotericism. Strange is not the mythic. Science is indeed strange. Let me give a list of strange but uncontroversial examples. I use examples from both science and mathematics.

On average, Mercury is closer to Earth than Venus. The core of some stellar objects remain unobserved. Olbers paradox. The Banach–Tarski paradox. The Monty Hall Problem. The Uncomputable Numbers. The Ramanujan’s sum $1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = -1/12$. The tip of a rotating rod accelerates faster than the gravitational acceleration. The Coin rotation paradox. Gravity is not a force.

Strange does not mean incorrect. Strange explanations are often the best ones.

1.7 Classes of quantum theories

This section is inspired by Maudlin’s essay called *Three measurement problems* [84]. Now that we have a well-defined philosophy, what classes of quantum theories might be considered? The following classification is certainly non-exhaustive, but it provides a good starting point to discuss interpretations and modifications of quantum mechanics.

Maudlin writes that the following three statements are mutually inconsistent:

1. Measurements have single outcomes;
2. The quantum state composed by the state vector and observables encode complete information about the system;
3. The system always evolves according to a linear equation of motion, that is, quantum mechanics is unitary.

We now identify three categories of theories by negating each one of the statements at a time.

1.7.1 Negation of 1: unitary quantum mechanics

The first statement must be negated if statements 2 and 3 are to be true. This is because 1 requires quantum mechanics to be non-unitary at some point, whereas 3 enforces unitarity at all times. Therefore, negating 1 leads to interpretations of quantum mechanics without collapses. Also,

because 2 is true, the theory is complete, which means that this class is simply unmodified unitary quantum mechanics. This class is perhaps Occam's razor applied to quantum theory.

Negation of 1 leads to a class of unitary quantum interpretations based on relative-state interpretations such as Everettian mechanics, relational quantum mechanics, decoherence-based approaches such as the Montevideo interpretation, modal interpretations, and consistent histories. All of these approaches can be understood starting from Everettian mechanics, which is why in these lectures, special emphasis is given to Everett.

1.7.2 Negation of 2: Hidden variable theories

The next option is to negate 2, where one requires that quantum mechanics is still linear, but now there should be single outcomes. If only statement 3 is assumed, due to the linearity of the theory, a multi-valued theory is natural. However, by imposing condition 1, one is forced to complement quantum mechanics with new elements that single out a specific outcome from the naturally multi-valued theory. Therefore, this category refers not to quantum mechanics, but to modifications of quantum mechanics, where the new elements are generically called the *hidden variables* of the modified theory. Hidden variable theories, by being different from quantum mechanics, in principle allow for different experimental predictions, technology permitting. Some of the most prominent hidden variable theories include pilot-wave theories such as Bohmian mechanics, and superdeterministic theories like the ψ -ensemble interpretation.

1.7.3 Negation of 3: collapse theories

The last option is negating 3. If one is to maintain 1 and 2, one necessarily enforces that a non-unitary process to obliterate the multi-valued part of the linear theory. This leads to collapse-type theories, but not necessarily of the Copenhagen-type. There are alternative collapse theories with well-defined ontologies and dynamics, which is a class of so-called objective collapse models. The most prominent examples are the Ghirardi–Rimini–Weber and the Diósi–Penrose models. There is increasing excitement about collapse models because they should leave peculiar thermodynamic signatures, whose experimental predictions might be soon contrasted with other rival theories.

1.8 Overview

In Chap. 1 we state the philosophy of science adopted in this course. The emphasis weighs on explanations rather than predictions. In Chap. 2 we introduce the simplest physical systems to discuss the foundations, which are qubits. In Chap. 3 we review Bell's original 1964 no-go theorem. Unlike frequently taught, the theorem restricts only modifications of quantum mechanics, not unitary quantum mechanics itself. In Chap. 4 we introduce the basic ideas of Bohmian mechanics, which is historically the most important realist non-local modification of quantum mechanics. In Chap. 5, building on Bohmian mechanics, we present the realist interpretation of unitary quantum mechanics, better known as Everettian quantum mechanics. In Chap. 6 we discuss the Schrödinger picture of quantum mechanics, and establish the technical elements in preparation for the decoherence program. Chap. 7 shows how the Heisenberg picture of quantum mechanics is more suitable to discuss foundational issues when compared to Schrödinger. In Chap. 8 we argue that, notwithstanding the current no-go theorems, unitary quantum mechanics can be understood as a deterministic, causal, complete and local theory. In Chap. 9 we discuss recently discussed thought experiments in the literature, with an emphasis on the Frauchiger-Renner protocol. Chap. 10 discusses notions of quantum decoherence within the framework of unitary quantum theory. In Chap; ??, we outline the basics of the constructor theory of information.

Chapter 2

Qubits

In this chapter, we introduce rudiments of quantum computation necessary to construct simple models of interactions between subsystems necessary to discuss the foundations of quantum mechanics.

To study the quantum mechanics of a system, one usually formulates a Hamiltonian and solves an equation of motion, such as the Schrödinger equation or the Heisenberg equation of motion. The various subsystems may interact, which requires complicated potentials describing the interactions in a realistic situation. The Coulomb interaction is an example of a charged system. To solve the equation of motion, we must address a continuous partial differential equation in both time and space. This is usually no simple task. Fortunately, to study the foundational aspect of quantum theory, we may simplify the matter by discretizing space and time, which saves us from solving a differential equation. Instead of dealing with a continuous Coulomb interaction, we can substitute the realistic interaction with discrete quantum operations, such as logic gates commonly found in quantum information. This approach allows us to focus on the physics at hand rather than on the non-universal continuous interactions.

The simplest matter constituents are spin-half particles. By having two energy levels, they are the simplest non-trivial quantum systems. Moreover, an interacting network of two-level systems can simulate not only any physical system but even non-physical systems (games) [32]. Typical two-level systems include the spin of an electron, the polarisation of a photon, quantum dots, superconducting qubits, and many more. Whatever the physical instantiation, the two-level system can be abstracted as *a qubit*.

2.1 The qubit

In quantum mechanics, every observable is described by a hermitian operator \hat{A} acting in a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . The eigenvectors of \hat{A} form a basis for \mathcal{H} . The observed result of \hat{A} must be one of the eigenvalues a of \hat{A} , $\hat{A}|\psi_a\rangle = a|\psi_a\rangle$.

A generic qubit requires a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} of dimension $d = 2$. The state vector of the qubit has two complex entries $|\psi\rangle = (\alpha, \beta)^T$ and the qubit observable is the vector of Pauli matrices $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)$, defined by

$$\sigma_x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \sigma_y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \sigma_z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.1)$$

If an experiment is set up to measure the z component of the qubit, then the corresponding observable is $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}} = \sigma_z$, with eigenstates $|1\rangle = (1, 0)^T$ and $|-1\rangle = (0, 1)^T$. The eigenstates are labelled after their corresponding eigenvalues.

Figure 2.1: The Bloch sphere.

Problem 2.1: *Spherical coordinates.* Also see Ref. [62]. An experiment might set up a reference frame in spherical coordinates, specified by the unit vector

$$\hat{r} = (\sin \theta \cos \varphi, \sin \theta \sin \varphi, \cos \theta). \quad (2.2)$$

Show that the observable matrix and the eigenstates (apart from a global phase) are given by:

$$\sigma_r = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & e^{-i\varphi} \sin \theta \\ e^{i\varphi} \sin \theta & -\cos \theta \end{bmatrix}, \quad |+\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) \\ e^{i\varphi} \sin(\theta/2) \end{bmatrix}, \quad |-\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-i\varphi} \sin(\theta/2) \\ -\cos(\theta/2) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.3)$$

Regardless of the reference frame (basis), $|\pm 1\rangle$ or $|\pm\rangle$, the eigenvalues of the qubit are always ± 1 . A change of reference frame does not affect the eigenvalues but changes the eigenstates. In classical mechanics, the microstate (x, p) of a particle would also change upon change of inertial reference frame, but the energy (for instance), remains invariant.

We might express a vector in spherical basis $|+\rangle$ in terms of the Cartesian basis as

$$|+\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) |1\rangle + e^{i\varphi} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) |-1\rangle. \quad (2.4)$$

The construction of Eq. (2.4) is known as the *Bloch sphere*. In the Cartesian basis, we specify the pair (α, β) for a state of a qubit. In the Bloch representation of Eq. (2.4), we specify (φ, θ) . The Bloch sphere allows for an intuitive geometric visualisation of a pure qubit state; see Fig. 2.1.

What is the probability of measuring the $+1(-1)$ eigenvalue of the Bloch state in Eq. (2.4)? According to the Born rule, we have

$$P_1 = |\langle 1|+\rangle|^2 = \cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \quad \text{and} \quad P_{-1} = |\langle -1|+\rangle|^2 = \sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right). \quad (2.5)$$

The probabilities sum up to $P_1 + P_{-1} = 1$. Therefore, if the qubit state is in the upper half of the Bloch sphere, the $+1$ eigenvalue is more likely. Similarly, if the qubit state is in the lower half of the Bloch sphere, the -1 eigenvalue is more likely. Both eigenvalues are equally likely for $\theta = \pi/2$, for which $\cos^2(\pi/4) = \sin^2(\pi/4)$.

The Bloch state in Eq. (2.4) is interpreted in different ways. In orthodox interpretations, the qubit collapses to $|1\rangle$ or $|-1\rangle$ upon measurement, with probabilities given by the Born rule Eq. (2.5). In Bohmian mechanics, a particle occupies either the $|1\rangle$ or the $|-1\rangle$ state. A measurement simply

reveals the particle's position. The Born rule is then simply understood as arising from the monitor's ignorance regarding the particle position. In Everettian mechanics, just as in Bohmian mechanics, both $|1\rangle$ or $|-1\rangle$ continue to exist after measurement, but there is no particle. Everettians must then explain why only one eigenvalue was observed. A Qubist views the qubit state as a mathematical function encoding information about the qubit. This information is then updated according to the Born rule after measurement. No collapse occurred, there was simply an information update.

2.2 Single qubit gates

Let us discuss the effect of quantum gates in the Schrödinger picture, where the qubit states evolve. The states $|\psi(t)\rangle = U(t)|\psi(0)\rangle$ evolve according to a unitary time evolution operator $U(t)$, which is found by solving the Schrödinger equation $\mathcal{H}|\psi\rangle = i\hbar\partial_t|\psi\rangle$. If the Hamiltonian is time-independent then $U(t) = e^{-i\mathcal{H}t/\hbar}$; see Prob. 6.1. In realistic situations, solving for $U(t)$ is hard.

Quantum logic gates serve as proxies for complicated interactions. In the context of a single qubit, these interactions unitarily evolve the qubit's state. Quantum gates, on the other hand, offer a discrete approach to handling these interactions, simplifying the complexity of continuous interactions. The effect of a single qubit gate is represented by an operator denoted as G , which allows us to compute the evolved qubit state as $G|\psi\rangle$. This approach is far more straightforward than solving a continuous equation of motion. Therefore, these operators denoted as G , are commonly referred to simply as *gates*. Instead of solving the Schrödinger equation to find G , we simply assume G . Then, it is a matter of (challenging) engineering to ensure a system Hamiltonian that provides G . Since here we only worry about foundational issues, the hard engineering part can be ignored.

2.2.1 Pauli gates

Single qubit gates are 2×2 matrices. The 2×2 identity matrix I is a trivial gate that leaves the qubit unchanged. The simplest non-trivial gates are the Pauli gates, defined as $X = \sigma_x$, $Y = \sigma_y$ and $Z = \sigma_z$. Note that the X gate toggles the qubit states $X|\pm 1\rangle = |\mp 1\rangle$. For this reason, the X gate is also called the not gate. Physically, an X gate might be implemented using microwave pulses on superconducting qubits, laser pulses on trapped ions, or manipulating a spin with a magnetic field.

The application of the Pauli gates in sequence to the state $|1\rangle$ is illustrated as:

$$|1\rangle \longrightarrow \boxed{X} \longrightarrow \boxed{Y} \longrightarrow \boxed{Z} \longrightarrow$$

Problem 2.2: *Pauli gates.* Work out the effect of the Pauli gates on the basis states $|\pm 1\rangle$.

2.2.2 Rotation operator gates

A rotation operation by an angle φ about an axis \hat{n} ($n_x^2 + n_y^2 + n_z^2 = 1$) is defined as [103]

$$R_{\hat{n}}(\varphi) = e^{-i\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{n} \frac{\varphi}{2}} = I \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) - i\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{n} \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right). \quad (2.6)$$

The equivalence of the exponential and the trigonometric form can be shown by expanding the exponential in a Taylor series and identifying the trigonometric functions. Note that while rotation matrices are unitary, they are in general not hermitian. The effect of a rotation gate of φ about \hat{x} over the state $|1\rangle$ is

$$R_{\hat{x}}(\varphi)|1\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right)|1\rangle - i\sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right)|-1\rangle. \quad (2.7)$$

This shows that except for special angles φ , rotations generally yield superposition states.

Problem 2.3: *Switching a qubit.* Verify that $R_{\hat{x}}(\pi)|1\rangle = -i|-1\rangle$. Note that a π rotation toggles the qubit (as intuitively expected), but accumulates a phase ($-i$), which is perhaps less intuitive.

2.2.3 The Hadamard gate

The Hadamard gate is a particular case of a rotation defined by

$$H = iR_{(\hat{x}+\hat{z})/\sqrt{2}}(\pi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.8)$$

The effect of the Hadamard on the basis states is

$$H|1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1\rangle + |-1\rangle), \quad H|-1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1\rangle - |-1\rangle). \quad (2.9)$$

The Hadamard creates and undoes superposition states, which makes it one of the most versatile gates in quantum circuits. We draw it as

$$|1\rangle \text{ --- } \boxed{H} \text{ ---}$$

2.3 Two-qubit gates

A quantum gate G might not only operate on a single qubit but can also operate on multiple qubits at the same time. Because of this, two-qubit gates can be used to model an interaction between two neighbouring qubits. Here we discuss the controlled-NOT gate (cnot). Other multiple qubit gates can be understood in a similar fashion.

2.3.1 The Kronecker product

Recall that the Kronecker product between 2×2 matrices is obtained as

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \begin{bmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{bmatrix} & b \begin{bmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{bmatrix} \\ c \begin{bmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{bmatrix} & d \begin{bmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.10)$$

If you are unfamiliar with tensor and Kronecker products, a good reference is Ref. [24]. Here we do not review all the properties of tensor products. We only recall the mixed-product property $(A \otimes B)(C \otimes D) = (AC) \otimes (BD)$ that will be exhaustively. The same formation structure of Eq. (2.10) also applies to vectors. Similarly, the Kronecker sum of two matrices A and B is formed as $A \oplus B = A \otimes I_b + I_a \otimes B$, where I_A is the identity matrix in the subspace of A , and analogously for B .

2.3.2 The controlled-NOT gate

The cnot operates on two qubits. Traditionally, one is called the *control* $|c\rangle$ and the other the *target* qubit $|t\rangle$ [90]. We draw it as

$$\begin{array}{c} |c\rangle \text{ --- } \bullet \text{ ---} \\ |t\rangle \text{ --- } \oplus \text{ ---} \end{array}$$

The cnot is a simplified interaction between the control and target qubits. It is defined by the matrix

$$G_{\text{cnot}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.11)$$

The upper left block is an identity, and the lower right block is a not operation.

Problem 2.4: *The effect of the cnot.* Show that the cnot evolves the two qubits states ($|c\rangle \otimes |t\rangle$) as $|1\rangle \otimes |\pm 1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle \otimes |\pm 1\rangle$ and $|-1\rangle \otimes |\pm 1\rangle \rightarrow |-1\rangle \otimes |\mp 1\rangle$. In other words: the target checks out the state of the control. The control remains unchanged. If the control is set to $+1$, the target also remains unchanged. If the control is set to -1 , the cnot performs a not operation on the target, hence its name.

2.4 Two-qubit networks and Bell gates

Let us discuss a two-qubit network described by the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_c \otimes \mathcal{H}_t$, where \mathcal{H}_c is the sub-space of the control, and \mathcal{H}_t the target. A Hadamard is applied to the control, which is followed by a cnot, as sketched below:

The network is initialised in the state $|\psi_0\rangle = |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$. After the Hadamard, the state of the network evolves to

$$|\psi_1\rangle = (H \otimes I) |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle = H|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle) \otimes |1\rangle. \quad (2.12)$$

The two qubits have not interacted yet, such that the state $|\psi_1\rangle$ is still separable. Now, the two qubits are assumed to be sufficiently close, such that they interact via the cnot, which evolves the network to

$$|\psi_2\rangle = G_{\text{cnot}} |\psi_1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + |-1\rangle \otimes |-1\rangle). \quad (2.13)$$

The final state $|\psi_2\rangle$ after the local interaction is now entangled (non-separable). The combination of a Hadamard and the cnot is an instance of a *Bell gate*, which is a simple circuit to entangle qubits.

Problem 2.5: *Bell states.* See [\[Link\]](#) [98]. Work out the other three Bell states produced by the three Bell gates illustrated in Fig. 2.2. Additionally, is there a more minimal Bell gate that generates the singlet state $|\Psi^-\rangle$?

If we consider a qubit as a spin-half particle, like an electron, we can relate the first three Bell states below

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi^+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|-1\rangle|-1\rangle + |1\rangle|1\rangle), & |\Phi^-\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|-1\rangle|-1\rangle - |1\rangle|1\rangle); \\ |\Psi^+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|-1\rangle|1\rangle + |1\rangle|-1\rangle), & |\Psi^-\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|-1\rangle|1\rangle - |1\rangle|-1\rangle), \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

Figure 2.2: Bell gates (not Bill Gates).

to the triplet states, while the fourth Bell state $|\Psi^-\rangle$ corresponds to the singlet state.

Let's imagine a scenario where we want to model the quantum state of two approaching electrons, both initially in the spin-up configuration (denoted as $|\uparrow\rangle \otimes |\uparrow\rangle$). As these electrons approach each other, the Coulomb interaction between them remains weak initially. During this phase, the quantum state of the electrons evolves, and when their wave functions start to overlap, interference effects become noticeable. This evolution can be mathematically modelled using Hadamard and Pauli gates. As the two electrons get closer, their interaction via the Coulomb force leads to entanglement, and this interaction is represented by the cnot gate. In cases where the electrons are extremely close, the Pauli exclusion principle comes into play. This principle favours the formation of the singlet state, which is precisely achieved by the fourth Bell gate. Bell gates serve as valuable tools for creating simplified models of complex quantum interactions. They spare us the need to solve the Schrödinger equation for quantum evolution, allowing us to focus on fundamental concepts and principles.

Chapter 3

Bell's 1964 inequality

To determine whether a theory is scientific, several criteria are typically considered. A widely accepted criterion is that the theory should have empirical support, meaning that it must be testable and potentially falsifiable by observation or experiment. However, in physics, theorists often apply an additional criterion even before experimental validation: mathematical self-consistency. If a theory is internally inconsistent, it generally disqualifies itself from empirical testing, as any supporting data would be rendered meaningless due to the theory's logical flaws.

For instance, theorists may derive no-go theorems based on a theory's foundational assumptions, which delineate conditions under which the theory cannot hold or make valid predictions. These no-go theorems establish boundaries for mathematical self-consistency and often reveal inherent contradictions, effectively "falsifying" the theory at a purely theoretical level. In this way, the requirement for mathematical consistency acts as a fundamental filter, ensuring that only theories with sound logical frameworks advance to experimental scrutiny.

Quantum no-go theorems are some of the most powerful tools available for distinguishing and testing both modifications of quantum mechanics and quantum mechanics itself. Among these, the most famous is Bell's 1964 theorem, which introduced an inequality that constrains potential modifications to quantum mechanics [11]. Other theorems in the Bell family impose constraints on quantum mechanics directly [12]. Many of these Bell-type results share conceptual similarities, and often similar statements, leading the literature to commonly refer to them collectively as *Bell's theorem*. This collective term is well-understood within the specialized community studying the foundations of quantum mechanics but is sometimes misunderstood in the broader physics community. In this chapter, we focus on Bell's 1964 inequality.

John Bell published his celebrated inequality in 1964 [11]. Its implications remain eagerly discussed to this day [11–13]. The derivation of the inequality is simple, but its meaning has a history of misunderstandings [85]. Perhaps for the first time after the development of quantum mechanics, and the proliferation of the first interpretations, one was able to rule out a large category of quantum interpretations, namely: local hidden variable theories admitting statistical independence. Bell showed that the field of foundations of quantum mechanics is not to be restricted to philosophy only, but that physics also has its part in this endeavour [12, 13, 93]. Based on Bell's result, one then hopes to develop refined no-go theorems and contrast viable categories of interpretations with constraints imposed by both quantum field theory and general relativity to narrow down the menu of interpretations [22, 51, 87, 97].

3.1 The setup

We will now provide a contemporary treatment of Bell's 1964 no-go theorem. Consider a pair of identical particles, represented as qubits A and B , which evolve into the entangled spin-singlet state given by $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle)$. This evolution occurs due to local interactions. In Sec. 2.4,

Figure 3.1: A Bell experiment.

we demonstrated that these interactions can be effectively modelled using a suitable Bell gate, as illustrated in Figure 3.1. It's important to note that the subsequent discussion applies to any choice of Bell gate. In a realistic setting, the qubits move, which introduces a position dependence of qubits. In our simplified model, the positions are implicitly associated with the respective Hilbert sub-spaces.

Fig. 3.1 might appear overwhelming at first glance. Let's simplify things by temporarily ignoring qubits L_A and L_B and focusing solely on qubits A and B . This corresponds to the Bell gate responsible for generating the singlet Bell state discussed in Sec. 2.4. The two-qubit network composed by A and B is initialised in the state $|\psi_0\rangle = |\uparrow\rangle|\uparrow\rangle \equiv |\uparrow\uparrow\rangle$, where we omitted the Kronecker product \otimes to alleviate the notation. In the first time-step, a Hadamard operates on A , and a not-gate on B , such that

$$|\psi_1\rangle = H \otimes X |\uparrow\rangle \otimes |\uparrow\rangle = H |\uparrow\rangle \otimes X |\uparrow\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\rangle) \otimes |\downarrow\rangle. \quad (3.1)$$

Next, we operate with the Z -gate on both qubits, such that

$$|\psi_2\rangle = Z \otimes Z |\psi_1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\rangle - |\downarrow\rangle) \otimes (-|\downarrow\rangle). \quad (3.2)$$

Here, the Z gate on B is actually optional, and is merely included here to match the convention adopted in Ref. [98]. Up to now, we only operated with single-qubit gates, which are unable to entangle qubits. Now, qubits A and B are brought close to one another, such that they interact. The interaction is modelled by the cnot, which acts on A as the control and B as the target qubit. This gives

$$|\psi_3\rangle = G_{\text{cnot}} |\psi_2\rangle = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\rangle \otimes |\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\rangle \otimes |\uparrow\rangle). \quad (3.3)$$

Particles A and B are now entangled. The singlet state $|\psi_3\rangle$ remains entangled even if A and B fly apart into space-like separated regions.

3.2 Properties of entangled states

A remarkable property of the singlet state is that it is spherically symmetric.

Problem 3.1: *Spherical symmetry of the singlet state.* Let $|\psi_s\rangle$ be the singlet state. Show that $R_{\hat{n}}(\varphi) \otimes R_{\hat{n}}(\varphi) |\psi_s\rangle = |\psi_s\rangle$.

What about entangled triplet states? Consider for instance the total spin-zero triplet state $|\psi_t\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle + |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle)$. What if we rotate it by $\pi/2$ about the \hat{x} axis? Will it change? Let us

Figure 3.2: Illustration of how a global change of basis (viewpoint) may undo a classical correlation. The visible geometrical shapes are initially correlated by inversion. If both shapes are rotated by $\pi/2$ around the vertical axis, the previously visible correlation is lost.

check. In preparation, we evaluate

$$R_{\hat{x}}(\pi/2)|\uparrow\rangle = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(|\uparrow\rangle - i|\downarrow\rangle); \quad R_{\hat{x}}(\pi/2)|\downarrow\rangle = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(-i|\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\rangle). \quad (3.4)$$

With this, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\hat{x}}(\pi/2)|\uparrow\rangle R_{\hat{x}}(\pi/2)|\downarrow\rangle &= \frac{1}{2}(-i|\uparrow\uparrow\rangle - i|\downarrow\downarrow\rangle + |\uparrow\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle); \\ R_{\hat{x}}(\pi/2)|\downarrow\rangle R_{\hat{x}}(\pi/2)|\uparrow\rangle &= \frac{1}{2}(-i|\uparrow\uparrow\rangle - i|\downarrow\downarrow\rangle - |\uparrow\downarrow\rangle + |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle). \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

The anti-symmetric combination gives the singlet $|\psi_s\rangle$. However, the symmetric combination yields a different entangled triplet

$$R_{\hat{x}}(\pi/2) \otimes R_{\hat{x}}(\pi/2)|\psi_t\rangle = -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\downarrow\rangle). \quad (3.6)$$

Hence, *the triplet states change under rotation, but the entanglement cannot be undone by a change of basis* [62]. Eq. (3.6) is a particular example. Therefore, just like in classical mechanics, a change of reference frame might change the states. However, quantum entanglement correlations cannot be undone by a global change of basis, which is an important difference with respect to classical correlations; see Fig. 3.2 for an analogy.

3.3 Correlations

3.3.1 Same reference frames

Now that A and B are entangled, particle A moves to lab L_A , and particle B to lab L_B . Labs L_A and L_B occupy space-like separated regions. In our simplified circuit in Fig. 3.1, the labs themselves are qubits. The labs interact with the respective qubits via a cnot, with the labs as the targets. The four-qubit network is described by the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_{L_A} \otimes \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B \otimes \mathcal{H}_{L_B}$. Before the labs interact with the qubits, the state of the network is $|\Psi_3\rangle = |\underline{\uparrow}\rangle \otimes |\underline{\psi_3}\rangle \otimes |\underline{\uparrow}\rangle$, where $|\underline{\psi_3}\rangle$ is specified in Eq. (3.3), and we underline the lab's states as a visual aid. After the interaction, the network evolves into the entangled state

$$|\Psi_4\rangle = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\underline{\uparrow}\underline{\uparrow}\underline{\downarrow}\underline{\downarrow}\rangle - |\underline{\downarrow}\underline{\downarrow}\underline{\uparrow}\underline{\uparrow}\rangle). \quad (3.7)$$

The labs' qubits are set up in such a way that if the qubit pointer is directed to position \uparrow after the interaction, then the lab measured the eigenvalue $+1$ of the qubit. Similarly, if the pointer points to \downarrow after the interaction, then the lab measured the -1 eigenvalue of the qubit. Looking at Eq. (3.7), we see two possibilities in the superposition. The first term is $|\underline{\uparrow}\underline{\uparrow}\underline{\downarrow}\underline{\downarrow}\rangle$, which informs us that if L_A measured $+1$ of A , then L_B necessarily measures the -1 eigenvalue of B . The other possibility is

given in $|\underline{\downarrow} \underline{\downarrow} \underline{\uparrow} \underline{\uparrow}\rangle$, where L_A observes -1 and L_B sees $+1$. In this situation, L_A and L_B used the same reference frames, and the measurement outcomes at the labs are perfectly anti-correlated.

A brief disclaimer is warranted. Real projective measurements are not unitary processes, as they involve decoherence due to interactions with an environment. However, the toy model presented in Fig. 3.1 assumes that the lab interactions are idealized as unitary processes. Consequently, for the purposes of this chapter, a cnot gate can be considered as an idealized measurement.

Let $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ be the unit vector defining the reference frame of L_A , and $\hat{\mathbf{b}}$ of L_B . Therefore, the setups at L_A and L_B measure the qubit observables $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{a}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}$, respectively. In Eq. (3.7), $\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \hat{\mathbf{b}} = \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. But this must not necessarily be so. Bell calls the respective eigenvalues observed at L_A and L_B as $A(\mathbf{a}) = \pm 1$ and $B(\mathbf{b}) = \pm 1$ [11]. If $\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \hat{\mathbf{b}}$, then there is a perfect anti-correlation of the observed eigenvalues, which is summarised in Tab. 3.1. Therefore, if the two labs use the same reference frame, there is always a correlation between the observations of the two labs.

$\hat{\mathbf{a}}$	$A(\hat{\mathbf{a}})$	$\hat{\mathbf{b}}$	$B(\hat{\mathbf{b}})$
$\hat{\mathbf{z}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$	+1	$\hat{\mathbf{z}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$	-1
$\hat{\mathbf{z}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$	-1	$\hat{\mathbf{z}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$	+1

Table 3.1: Entanglement correlations

Problem 3.2: Eigenvalues of qubit observables. Show that the eigenvalues of $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}$ are ± 1 .

Laboratories L_A and L_B need to communicate to confirm correlation, which is implemented as a final step using a cnot gate between L_A and L_B [41]. In our quantum circuit (see Fig. 3.1), L_B serves as the target qubit.

Problem 3.3: Final state of the four-qubit network. Show that the final state is

$$|\Psi_5\rangle = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\underline{\uparrow} \underline{\uparrow} \underline{\downarrow} \underline{\downarrow}\rangle - |\underline{\downarrow} \underline{\downarrow} \underline{\uparrow} \underline{\uparrow}\rangle), \quad (3.8)$$

Explain how this result confirms the anti-correlations via the communication channel between the labs.

Let us explain how L_A (the target) confirms the anti-correlation. The pointer of the measuring device of L_A points \uparrow (or \downarrow) before the interaction with L_B . After the interaction via the cnot, the pointer will either remain in the \uparrow (\downarrow) state, or will flip to \downarrow (\uparrow). If the measurement pointer transition is of the $|\downarrow\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow\rangle$ type, then due to the nature of the cnot, L_B knows that L_A is in the \uparrow state. If L_B flips as $|\uparrow\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow\rangle$, then this reveals that L_A is in the \downarrow state.

3.3.2 Different reference frames

What happens in the general case $\hat{\mathbf{a}} \neq \hat{\mathbf{b}}$, where the two labs might use different reference frames? As a particular example, let us consider $\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{b}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$. Then, let us first prepare L_B by rotating it by $\pi/2$ about the $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ axis making $R_{\hat{\mathbf{y}}}(\pi/2)|\uparrow\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\rangle)$.

Problem 3.4: Entanglement, but no correlations. Work out the four-qubit network state after the interaction with the labs for the case where $\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{b}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$. Then show that the table updates to Tab. 3.2.

$\hat{\mathbf{a}}$	$A(\hat{\mathbf{a}})$	$\hat{\mathbf{b}}$	$B(\hat{\mathbf{b}})$
$\hat{\mathbf{z}}$	+1	$\hat{\mathbf{x}}$	-1
$\hat{\mathbf{z}}$	-1	$\hat{\mathbf{x}}$	+1
$\hat{\mathbf{z}}$	+1	$\hat{\mathbf{x}}$	+1
$\hat{\mathbf{z}}$	-1	$\hat{\mathbf{x}}$	-1

Table 3.2: Entanglement, but no correlations.

Tab. 3.2 shows the outcome possibilities when $\hat{\mathbf{a}} = \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{b}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$. Now, from the point of view of the labs, for many repeated measurements, although the qubits are entangled, the outcomes seem random. By simply changing the reference frame in one of the labs, the correlation is lost.

The notion that a choice, such as changing the measurement basis in a lab that is space-like separated from another, can "undo" quantum correlations is often cited to support non-local interpretations of quantum mechanics [103]. However, as we will soon explore, such interpretations overlook the full structure of the four-qubit network state. If one presumes that only one term in the superposition of Eq. (3.7) survives, this exclusion of information indeed creates an appearance of non-locality, as it implies that an experiment on a subsystem influences the entirety of the system. Conversely, if all information present in Eq. (3.7) is retained and the measurement outcome is viewed as a projection, then although information from the other term in the superposition may become inaccessible, the principle of locality remains intact [116]. We will further examine this issue in the context of specific quantum mechanical theories and interpretations in subsequent chapters. This approach clarifies the critical distinction between interpretations that discard parts of the superposition and those that maintain the full network information, preserving locality within quantum mechanics.

3.4 The quantum mechanical expectation value

One usually refers to *quantum mechanics* as the combination of an equation of motion, such as the Schrödinger equation or the Heisenberg equation of motion, along with the Born rule to calculate expectation values. The calculation of expectation values via the Born rule is uncontroversial, but its meaning depends on a particular interpretation. For instance, the Copenhagen interpretation asserts that a measurement triggers a random collapse, and the outcome probability is postulated as the Born rule. On the other hand, unitary interpretations of quantum mechanics do not postulate the Born rule but seek to explain it instead [36, 46, 79, 110, 128].

The quantum mechanical expectation value for the entangled state $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle)$ of the product of the observables at different labs is

$$P(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{b}}) = \langle \psi | (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{a}})(\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}) | \psi \rangle = -\hat{\mathbf{a}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}, \quad (3.9)$$

which shows that the expectation value depends on the detector settings. The last equality is yet to be demonstrated. So far, there is no mention of hidden variables. A virtue of Eq. (3.9) is that $P(\hat{\mathbf{a}}, \hat{\mathbf{b}})$ does not depend on whether one is working in the Schrödinger or Heisenberg picture. To alleviate the notation, let us drop the hats on the unit vectors for the remainder of the chapter. Note that if $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$, then $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -1$, which shows a perfect anti-correlation of the singlet state. If $\mathbf{a} \perp \mathbf{b}$, then $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0$, which confirms the apparent randomness of Tab. 3.2.

We now turn to the calculation of the expectation value. Let $\mathbf{a} = \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ establish the z direction, such that $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{a} = \sigma_z$. Then, relative to \mathbf{a} , we may parametrize \mathbf{a} in spherical coordinates as $\mathbf{b} = \sin \theta \cos \varphi \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \sin \theta \sin \varphi \hat{\mathbf{y}} + \cos \theta \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. Without loss of generality, we may choose a fixed angle $\varphi = 0$, which allow us to simplify $\mathbf{b} = \sin \theta \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \cos \theta \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. Then, $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{b} = \sin \theta \sigma_x + \cos \theta \sigma_z$.

Problem 3.5: *Calculation of the quantum mechanical expectation value.* Based on the preparatory considerations in the previous paragraph, show that $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -\cos \theta = -\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}$.

What is referred to as quantum mechanics stops here. In the next section, quantum mechanics is extended to a hidden variable theory.

3.5 Hidden variable theories

The Copenhagen interpretation posits that there is no direct correspondence between the quantum state and an objective reality, implying that quantum theory is fundamentally incomplete [47]. This perceived incompleteness motivated the exploration of hidden variable theories, which aim to restore determinism, realism, and a complete description of physical systems. Bell guides us to modify quantum mechanics by assuming a set of local hidden variables λ , which compile all the necessary information to supposedly complete quantum mechanics. The variables now affect the eigenvalues $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$. The writing of $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ contains an implicit assumption: the eigenvalue $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$ at lab L_A does not depend on \mathbf{b} . Similarly, $B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)$ does not depend on \mathbf{a} . Then, Bell assumes that the hidden variable dependent expectation value can be calculated using [11]

$$P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \int d\lambda \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) B(\mathbf{b}, \lambda), \quad (3.10)$$

where $\rho(\lambda)$ is a normalised hidden variable distribution. By writing Eq. (3.10), Bell excluded the possibility of superdeterminism, for which the probability distribution $\rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) \neq \rho(\lambda)$ [63, 71, 72, 122].

If Bell's type local hidden variable theory is to reproduce quantum mechanics, then one expects $P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$. However, within the assumptions of Bell's hidden variable locality and statistical independence, this is generally not possible. Using simple manipulations [11], Bell showed that $P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ must satisfy the inequality

$$1 + P_H(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \geq |P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})|, \quad (3.11)$$

which today bears his name. We will derive the inequality shortly. By using the quantum mechanical expectation value $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ instead of the hidden variable expectation value $P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ in Eq. (3.11), it is easy to produce special cases where $P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ – usually, simply referred to as quantum mechanics – violates the inequality. Therefore, Bell's original theorem in Ref. [11] states that statistical predictions of quantum mechanics are incompatible with local hidden variable formulations that obey statistical independence. Hidden variable no-go theorems such as Eq. (3.11) impose restrictions on modifications of quantum mechanics, not on quantum mechanics itself.

Problem 3.6: *Quantum mechanics violates Bell's inequality.* Choose \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} such that the angle between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} is $\pi/2$, the angle between \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} is $\pi/4$, and between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{c} also $\pi/4$. Use $P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ and show that quantum mechanics violates Bell's inequality.

Problem 3.7: *Classical mechanics respects Bell's inequality.* Consider a ball spitting machine that emits pairs of tennis balls in opposite directions with angular momenta $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = \boldsymbol{\lambda}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = \boldsymbol{\lambda}_2$, respectively. The total angular momentum of the two-ball system is conserved and equal to zero, such that $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = \boldsymbol{\lambda}_1 = -\boldsymbol{\lambda}_2$. Lab 1 measures the projection of the angular momentum of ball 1 onto a reference frame set by \mathbf{a} . The value of the recorded measurement is $A(\mathbf{a}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \mathbf{a} \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda}$. Similarly, lab 2 measures the projection $B(\mathbf{b}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = -\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\lambda}$. In this classical exercise, the *hidden variable* is $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$, which may we parametrized in spherical coordinates as

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}(\theta, \varphi) = (\sin \theta \cos \varphi, \sin \theta \sin \varphi, \cos \theta). \quad (3.12)$$

Assume that the distribution of emission of ball pairs is uniform $\rho(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) \equiv \rho(\theta, \varphi) = 1/(4\pi)$. Show that

$$P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -\frac{1}{3} \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}, \quad (3.13)$$

and convince yourself that this always respects Bell's inequality. Feel free to use a symbolic computational aid for the evaluation of the integral.

3.5.1 Derivation of Bell's inequality

From Eq. (3.10), we see that $\min P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = -1$, which is only possible for the case $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$. Imposing this on Eq. (3.10), and if $P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ is to be consistent with the quantum mechanical expectation value $\min P(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$, we must have

$$P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) = \int d\lambda \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) B(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) = -1. \quad (3.14)$$

This is only satisfied if $A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) = -B(\mathbf{a}, \lambda)$. We then use this property in Eq. (3.10) and write

$$P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = - \int d\lambda \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda). \quad (3.15)$$

Now we consider

$$\begin{aligned} P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) &= \int d\lambda \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) [A(\mathbf{c}, \lambda) - A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)] \\ &\stackrel{A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)^2=1}{=} \int d\lambda \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) [A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{c}, \lambda) - 1]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

Taking the absolute value and using the Cauchy-Schwarz integral inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} |P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) - P_H(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c})| &= \left| \int d\lambda \rho(\lambda) A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) [A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{c}, \lambda) - 1] \right| \\ &\leq \int d\lambda \rho(\lambda) \overbrace{|A(\mathbf{a}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda)|}^1 |A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{c}, \lambda) - 1| \\ &= \int d\lambda \rho(\lambda) [1 - A(\mathbf{b}, \lambda) A(\mathbf{c}, \lambda)] = 1 + P_H(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

This completes the demonstration of Bell's inequality in Ineq. (3.11).

Violations of Bell's inequality have been confirmed by several experiments [3, 30, 64]. Ironically, a local-realistic non-hidden variable formulation of quantum mechanics exists [9, 41, 100]. Bell's inequality alone does not imply non-locality: it implies that, within the assumptions of the no-go theorem, there cannot be a local hidden variable theory. Other research programs might construct local hidden variable theories that break Bell's assumptions. One example is superdeterminism.

3.6 No-go theorems and quantum theories

Bell's 1964 results summarised in the previous section exclude the possibility of a local hidden variable theory admitting statistical independence. That being the case, quantum theories (extended or not) might still be:

- (A) Local quantum mechanics without hidden variables. This includes unitary quantum interpretations [17, 49, 55, 75, 82, 102, 128] or information approaches such as Qubism [52, 53];
- (B) Local hidden variable extensions of quantum mechanics that violate statistical independence, that is, superdeterminism [63, 111, 114]; or stochastic hidden variables [4–6];
- (C) Non-local quantum mechanics without hidden variables. In these interpretations, a collapse [7, 50, 57] or handshake [26, 74] implements non-locality;
- (D) Non-local hidden variable extensions of quantum mechanics. The most prominent example is Bohmian mechanics [15].

Based on surveys on interpretations of quantum mechanics [93, 108, 113], in Tab. 3.3, we distribute a sample of theories according to the four categories. We scanned the literature for recent developments related to Bell's inequality with interpretive claims, either explicit or implicit; see Ref. [87] and Refs. therein. One notices the following trend: the possibility of Bohmian mechanics (D) is usually recognised and either embraced [46], or rejected based on arguments beyond Bell's theorem. The possibility of superdeterminism (B) is frequently overlooked or rejected on philosophical grounds [76, 85]. Yet a resurgence in superdeterminism is undergoing [63, 69, 71, 72, 114]. A recent hidden variable theory by Barandes escapes Bell's assumptions by proposing laws that are intrinsically stochastic [4–6]. Rejecting hidden variables completely, current literature typically falls back to collapse interpretations (C), declaring that quantum mechanics must be intrinsically non-local [19, 61]. However, while collapse-type interpretations are popular ways of violating Bell's inequality, Tab. 3.3 also shows a category of local quantum mechanical interpretations (A), which also violate Bell's inequality.

Later Bell theorems (see Refs. [12, 87]) assume local determinism and causality to constrain not only hidden variable theories but also quantum mechanics itself. Other noteworthy no-go theorems include the CHSH theorem [22], the Pusey-Barrett-Rudolph theorem [97], and the Frauchiger-Renner no-go theorem [51].

The purpose here, however, is not to defend the feasibility of each of the aforementioned quantum theories by analysing how each one of them survives the most recent no-go theorems. For this, the reader might consult the specific references in Tab. 3.3. Here, we simply argue that Bell's 1964 no-go theorem of Ref. [11], as habitually used to advertise quantum non-locality, actually imposes no restrictions on category (A).

	No hidden variables	Hidden variables
	<u>(A) Unitary quantum mechanics</u>	<u>(B) Superdeterminism or stochasticism</u>
Local	Everettian quantum mechanics [17, 49, 75] Relational quantum mechanics [82, 102] Quantum Darwinism [128] Montevideo interpretation [55] Information approaches* [52, 53]	Ψ -ensemble interpretation [63] Cellular Automaton [114] Invariant set theory [111] Unistochastic quantum theory [4–6]
	<u>(C) Collapse or handshake</u>	<u>(D) Non-local hidden variables</u>
Non-local	Copenhagen interpretations [50] Objective-collapse theories [7, 57] Transactional interpretation [26, 74]	Bohmian mechanics [15]

Table 3.3: Categories of quantum theories with some examples.

Chapter 4

Bohmian mechanics

The foundational concepts of pilot-wave theory were originally formulated by Louis de Broglie over a century ago and subsequently expanded upon by David Bohm [15]. In specialised literature, there exists a nuanced distinction between pilot-wave theories and Bohmian mechanics, although this difference is not the focus of our discussion here. In this chapter, we use the terms *pilot-wave theory* and *Bohmian mechanics* interchangeably. This chapter is influenced by various sources, including Bohm [15], Holland [67], Dürr et al. [115], Betz [14], and Lazarovici [46].

Pilot-wave theory holds immense historical significance, representing one of the earliest comprehensive formulations of quantum mechanics that incorporates universality, unitarity, a well-defined ontology, non-locality, and dynamics. Even if it were to be supplanted by a competing theory (and in the next chapter we argue that it probably is), Bohmian mechanics remains a captivating subject for philosophers. Additionally, one might consider Bohmian mechanics as the elder sibling of Everettian mechanics, a relationship explored in the forthcoming chapter. There are good reasons to think that Bohmian mechanics is false, just like Newtonian mechanics. Yet, we still learn Newtonian mechanics. Similarly, just like Newtonian mechanics, even if Bohmian mechanics is false, it is still very useful.

The frustration with the dominance of instrumentalists during the early days of quantum mechanics is perhaps best articulated by Bell himself [12]:

..., the essential idea was one that had been advanced already by de Broglie in 1927, in his "pilot wave" picture. But why then had Born not told me of this "pilot wave?" If only to point out what was wrong with it? Why did von Neumann not consider it? More extraordinarily, why did people go on producing "impossibility" proofs, after 1952, and as recently as 1978? When even Pauli, Rosenfeld, and Heisenberg, could produce no more devastating criticism of Bohm's version than to brand it as "metaphysical" and "ideological?" Why is the pilot wave picture ignored in text books? Should it not be taught, not as the only way, but as an antidote to the prevailing complacency? To show that vagueness, subjectivity, and indeterminism, are not forced on us by experimental facts, but by deliberate theoretical choice?

4.1 Formulation

Pilot-wave theory is a hidden variable extension of unitary quantum mechanics, which is based on the Schrödinger equation. For a single particle universe, the Schrödinger equation reads

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \mathcal{H} \Psi(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad \mathcal{H} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (4.1)$$

where m is the mass of the particle. The field $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ operates as the pilot for the particle, taking the space-time coordinates (\mathbf{r}, t) as input. Although the pilot-wave $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is a fundamental

aspect of the ontology, it remains beyond direct experimental observation, at least for the present. Measurements, instead, reveal the presence of particles, which are also integral to the ontology. The existence of the pilot-wave becomes apparent only indirectly through its influence on particle positions. In Sec. 4.4, we will explore how the pilot-wave imparts additional properties to particles, such as spin. Due to this field-centric ontology, pilot-wave theory is inherently formulated within the Schrödinger picture.

The ontology is clear: There are particles and there is the pilot-wave. What about the dynamics of the particles and the pilot wave? The Schrödinger equation (4.1) provides the dynamics for the particle. But this cannot be all. Since there are also particles, the position of a particle $\mathbf{r}(t)$ must be determined by an additional equation, which is called *the guiding equation*, which we now motivate.

4.1.1 The current

The properties of the pilot-wave motivate the guiding equation. In this sub-section, we review some properties of the Schrödinger equation, which also applies to unmodified quantum mechanics. The wave is normalised in a volume V of the system, such that

$$\int_V d^3r |\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 = 1 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{d}{dt} \int_V d^3r |\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 = 0. \quad (4.2)$$

There is no artificial separation between a measuring apparatus and a quantum system. The volume V encompasses everything. Eq. (4.2) implies that $|\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2$ is a conserved quantity. The field $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ might of course redistribute over time. To see how, we evaluate

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} |\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Psi^* \Psi) = \Psi^* \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \Psi^*}{\partial t} \Psi = \frac{i\hbar}{2m} (\Psi^* \nabla^2 \Psi - \nabla^2 \Psi^* \Psi) \\ &= \nabla \cdot \underbrace{\left[\frac{i\hbar}{2m} (\Psi^* \nabla \Psi - \nabla \Psi^* \Psi) \right]}_{-\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}, t)}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where we used the Schrödinger equation, and identified a current \mathbf{J} that satisfies the continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0, \quad (4.4)$$

where $\rho(\mathbf{r}, t) = |\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2$ is the conserved *density*, and $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the *current*. In textbooks, $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is also called the probability current. So far, no particles.

4.1.2 The guiding equation

The continuity equation (4.4) is well-known in other fields of classical physics, such as hydrodynamics or electromagnetism. There, the current is made up of particles, which are distributed according to the density $\rho(\mathbf{r}, t)$. The pilot-wave theory looks at $\rho(\mathbf{r}, t)$ as the appealing opportunity to make the connection between the quantum, the pilot-wave, and "the classical" – the particles. In classical mechanics, it is the particles that make up the current via

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \rho(\mathbf{r}, t) \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{d\mathbf{r}(t)}{dt}, \quad (4.5)$$

where $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the velocity field of the particle. Therefore, one takes Eq. (4.5) as the guiding equation for the particle, but with the current provided by the wave:

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{i\hbar}{2m} (\nabla \Psi^* \Psi - \Psi^* \nabla \Psi). \quad (4.6)$$

Then, one can rewrite the particle's guiding equation Eq. (4.5) to see how the particle's position is determined by the wave as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} = \frac{\mathbf{J}}{|\Psi|^2} = \frac{i\hbar (\Psi\nabla\Psi^* - \nabla\Psi\Psi^*)}{2m|\Psi|^2} = \frac{\hbar \operatorname{Im}(\Psi^*\nabla\Psi)}{m|\Psi|^2} = \frac{\hbar}{m} \operatorname{Im} \nabla \ln \Psi. \quad (4.7)$$

Taking the wave Ψ as input, one then solves for $\mathbf{r}(t)$ which is the *Bohmian trajectory* of the particle. From the first equality of Eq. (4.7), we can also infer that the particle tends to accommodate ($\mathbf{v} \approx 0$), where $|\Psi|^2$ is extreme. This also serves as a partial motivation for how the Born rule comes about in the pilot-wave theory of many particles. In pilot-wave theory, the Born rule is not part of the theory, but must nonetheless be explained.

The final compact form of the guiding equation (4.7) also shows that particle motion necessarily requires a gradient and an imaginary part in the pilot-wave landscape. Otherwise, the wave does not *push* the particles.

Problem 4.1: *Bohmian trajectory of the free particle.* We wish to determine the Bohmian trajectory of the free particle. For this, we first solve the Schrödinger equation (4.1) with $V(\mathbf{r}, t) = 0$ for which we find $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = Ae^{i(\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r} - \omega t)}$. Use this as input to the guiding equation (4.7) to show that the Bohmian trajectory is $\mathbf{r}(t) = \mathbf{r}_0 + \frac{\mathbf{p}}{m}t$.

Problem 4.2: *Bohmian trajectories for the harmonic oscillator.* The energy eigenstates of the quantum harmonic oscillator are given by

$$\psi_n(\xi) = \left(\frac{m\omega}{\pi\hbar}\right)^{1/4} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n n!}} H_n(\xi) e^{-\xi^2/2}, \quad (4.8)$$

where $H_n(\xi)$ are the real Hermite polynomials, and $\xi = \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\hbar}}x$. The pilot-wave is of the form

$$\Psi(x, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n \psi_n(x) e^{-iE_n t/\hbar}, \quad E_n = \frac{1}{2}\hbar\omega \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right). \quad (4.9)$$

Consider the initial condition $x(t=0) = x_0$. Show that if the pilot-wave is in an energy eigenstate, then $x(t) = x_0$. Under what conditions does the particle move?

Problem 4.3: Particle in a box. Work out the Bohmian trajectories of a particle in a box (See Ref. [91]).

4.2 Many particles

The world evidently consists of more than one particle. Therefore, let us now formulate the pilot-wave theory for N particles. First, we specify the initial positions for the N particles through the list $\{\mathbf{r}_a(0)\}$, where $a = (1, \dots, N)$. The pilot-wave that governs the particles is given by the Schrödinger equation

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t) = \left[-\sum_{a=1}^N \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_a} \nabla_a^2 + V(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t) \right] \Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t). \quad (4.10)$$

The pilot-wave is now a map of the form $\Psi : \mathbb{R}^{3N} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. The pilot wave is now represented as a map of the form $\Psi : \mathbb{R}^{3N} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. For a single particle, the mapping simplifies to $\Psi : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$,

meaning that for each space-time coordinate (\mathbf{r}, t) , there exists a complex-valued field. However, when considering a universe with $N > 1$, the situation becomes more intricate. There is no longer an ordinary mapping from space-time coordinates to a complex value because each additional particle introduces an additional 3-dimensional spatial degree of freedom. Consequently, the configuration space grows to \mathbb{R}^{3N} , a higher-dimensional space. It is often said that the pilot wave encompasses many space-time foliations, a term borrowed from the language of differential geometry, to describe the relationship between the wavefunction and the underlying configuration space(s).

Problem 4.4: Continuity equation. Show that the continuity equation for the N particle system is given by

$$\frac{\partial |\Psi|^2}{\partial t} + \sum_{a=1}^N \nabla_a \cdot \mathbf{J}_a = 0, \quad (4.11)$$

where the current due to particle a is

$$\mathbf{J}_a(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t) = -\frac{i\hbar}{2m_a} (\Psi^* \nabla_a \Psi - \nabla_a \Psi^* \Psi) = \frac{\hbar}{m_a} \text{Im} (\Psi^* \nabla_a \Psi). \quad (4.12)$$

Problem 4.5: N guiding equations. Show that there is a guiding equation for each particle a , given by

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}_a(t)}{dt} = \frac{\mathbf{J}_a(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t)}{|\Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t)|^2} = \frac{\hbar}{m_a} \text{Im} (\nabla_a \ln \Psi). \quad (4.13)$$

The program to solve a problem in pilot-wave theory is thus summarised in the following steps:

1. Specify the initial conditions $\{\mathbf{r}_a(0)\}$;
2. Solve the Schrödinger equation to obtain the pilot-wave $\Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t)$;
3. Solve the N guiding equations to obtain the Bohmian trajectories.

Solving for all trajectories is a formidable task, yet unnecessary for practical purposes. Similarly to classical statistical mechanics, the collective properties can be obtained from typicality arguments, even though the microstate $\{\mathbf{r}_a(t), \mathbf{p}_a(t)\}$ remains unknown [46].

Pilot-wave theory is part of the class of hidden variable theories introduced in Sec. 1.7. In this framework, the addition of classical particles to quantum theories modifies quantum mechanics. The hidden variables in this theory are the particles themselves. However, some argue that the hidden variable could also be considered the pilot wave, as the particles are directly observed, while the wave remains *hidden*. For the purposes of Bell's 1964 theorem, however, the hidden variables must explicitly refer to the particles.

4.3 Connection to classical mechanics

The following analysis is frequently discussed in the context of standard quantum mechanics, and also applies to the pilot-wave. The complex field can be expressed as

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t) = R(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t) e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} S(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t)}, \quad (4.14)$$

where $R = |\Psi|$ is the real amplitude, and S is a real phase in units of an action (\hbar).

Problem 4.6: *Relation between the current and the phase.* Substitute Eq. (4.14) in Eq. (4.12) and (4.13) to show that

$$\mathbf{J}_a = \frac{|\Psi|^2}{m_a} \nabla_a S, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{p}_a = \nabla_a S. \quad (4.15)$$

Note that the momentum \mathbf{p}_a of the particles does not depend on the amplitude. Also, this confirms that motion requires a modulation of the phase landscape.

Substitution of Eq. (4.14) into the Schrödinger equation (4.10) yields

$$-R \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + i\hbar \frac{\partial R}{\partial t} = - \sum_a \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_a} \left(\nabla_a^2 R + 2 \frac{i}{\hbar} \nabla_a R \cdot \nabla_a S + \frac{i}{\hbar} R \nabla_a^2 S - R \frac{1}{\hbar^2} (\nabla_a S)^2 \right) + VR. \quad (4.16)$$

We now analyse the imaginary and real parts of this equation.

4.3.1 The imaginary part

The imaginary part of Eq. (4.16) gives

$$\frac{\partial R}{\partial t} = - \sum_a \frac{1}{2m_a} (2 \nabla_a R \cdot \nabla_a S + R \nabla_a^2 S). \quad (4.17)$$

To rewrite this, we may use the fact that $\rho = R^2$, such that in terms of ρ , we have

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = - \sum_a \frac{1}{m_a} (\nabla_a \rho \cdot \nabla_a S + \rho \nabla_a^2 S) = - \sum_a \frac{1}{m_a} \nabla_a \cdot (\rho \nabla_a S) = - \sum_a \nabla_a \cdot \mathbf{J}_a, \quad (4.18)$$

which recovers the continuity equation Eq. (4.11).

4.3.2 The real part

The real part of the Schrödinger equation above gives

$$-\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = \sum_a \frac{p_a^2}{2m_a} + V - \sum_a \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_a} \frac{\nabla_a^2 R}{R}; \quad (4.19)$$

Except for the last term, this is precisely the Hamilton-Jacobi equation from classical mechanics. For this reason, one defines the last term as a *quantum potential*

$$Q = - \sum_{a=1}^N \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_a} \frac{\nabla_a^2 R}{R}, \quad (4.20)$$

without which, the Bohmian particle would simply follow the classical trajectory. The quantum potential shows that a flat amplitude landscape leads to classical behaviour. Also, if $|\mathbf{p}_a| \gg \hbar$, the quantum potential is irrelevant. The discussion of this section can also be made in the context of orthodox interpretations [60] or Everettian mechanics [117].

Figure 4.1: The entangling of three particles A , B and C through local interactions. Here $t' > t > t_0$. (a) A and B are initially separable. (b) Entanglement through local interactions sets up the relative states $\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t)\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t)$ and $\phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t)\phi_{\uparrow}(x_2, t)$. The particles illustrated by blue disks move to space-like separated regions indicated by the shaded triangles. (c) Meiosis of the measurer C . The detector C verifies the B particle's spin eigenvalue by interacting with it in the space-like intersecting region. From t to t' , the only new foliation occurs in the measurer within the space-like intersecting region. The dashed line indicates the unfoliated detector C at time t , and the two thinner solid lines show the two new foliations joining the already foliated entangled state. The new spatially extended preferred foliation $\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t')\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t')\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')$ is shown as the thick grey line.

4.4 Entanglement

4.4.1 Unitary evolution leads to foliations

Let us now describe the entangled spin-singlet state $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle)$. The pilot-wave evolves autonomously according to Eq. (4.10). At time t_0 , the two-particle field is separable (See Fig. 4.1(a)):

$$\Psi(x_1, x_2; t_0) = \langle x_1, x_2 | \psi(t_0) \rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t_0) + \phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t_0)] \phi(x_2, t_0). \quad (4.21)$$

Next, the positions x_1 and x_2 are close enough for the particles A and B to interact. The local interaction, whose specific form is not relevant, is such that the field evolves to the entangled singlet state

$$\Psi(x_1, x_2; t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\underline{\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t)\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t)} - \phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t)\phi_{\uparrow}(x_2, t) \right]. \quad (4.22)$$

The underlined term will be explained shortly.

Problem 4.7: Unitary evolution. Show that if the pilot-wave evolved to $\Psi(x_1, x_2; t) = \phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t)\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t)$ instead of Eq. (4.22), the evolution would be non-unitary and hence violate the Schrödinger equation.

Figs. 4.1(a,b) illustrate the evolution of the position-dependent wave-packets in Eqs. (4.21) and (4.22). We know that particle A is in position $X_A(t)$ at lab L_A , and particle B is in position $X_B(t)$ at lab L_B . The particles' positions are indicated by the blue disks in Fig. 4.1. The positions are determined by their respective guiding equations. We have

$$m_A \frac{dX_A}{dt} = \hbar \operatorname{Im} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \ln \Psi(x_1, X_B(t), t) \Big|_{x_1=X_A(t)}; \quad (4.23)$$

$$m_B \frac{dX_B}{dt} = \hbar \operatorname{Im} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \ln \Psi(X_A(t), x_2, t) \Big|_{x_2=X_B(t)}. \quad (4.24)$$

The spin-singlet state ensures two possibilities:

1. The field $\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t)$ pilots the particle A and the field $\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t)$ pilots the particle B ;
2. The field $\phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t)$ pilots the particle A and $\phi_{\uparrow}(x_2, t)$ pilots the particle B .

These two options accessible to the particles determine the relative states $\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t)\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t)$ and $\phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t)\phi_{\uparrow}(x_2, t)$ in Eq. (4.22); see Fig. 4.1(b). The initial conditions of the Bohmian system determine which relative state the particles populate. Without loss of generality, we assume possibility one, which corresponds to the occupation of the underlined relative state in Eq. (4.22). The actual populated relative state would be calculated deterministically from the initial conditions and the specific form of the Hamiltonian. Also, from Eq. (4.23) we see that the particle at X_A likely accommodates ($\frac{dX_A}{dt} \approx 0$) where the derivative of the logarithm is zero, which happens when $\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t)$ is extreme; as shown in Fig. 4.1.

Since the particles occupy the underlined relative state in Eq. (4.22), one frequently labels it as the *preferred foliation* of the entangled state [45, 75]. The second empty foliation could have been the preferred one if the initial conditions were different, or could still evolve to be the preferred foliation if populated in the future. Also, note that it is the foliations that confer properties to the particles. Particle A is in a spin-up configuration because its corresponding wave-packet is $\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t)$. This shows that it is easy to incorporate spin in pilot-wave theory.

4.4.2 Non-locality, but local information flow

Due to the guiding Eqs. (4.23) and (4.24) (the particles), Bohmian mechanics is non-local. The trajectory $X_A(t)$ depends on the global pilot-wave Ψ , which includes field deformations that occur in space-like separated regions. Yet a frequently underappreciated property of pilot-waves is that fields of subsystems $\phi_{\uparrow(\downarrow)}(x, t)$ only interfere locally. This was also pointed out in Ref. [117] in the context of Everettian mechanics. As long as the information is processed by the pilot-wave, a local information flow is possible, even in a theory with non-local elements. In quantum information circuits, quantum information processing occurs via entanglement and interference effects [89], which are properties of the pilot-wave. For this reason, in Bohmian mechanics, although the particles make up the computing device, the information flows through the pilot-wave.

4.4.3 Meiosis of the measurer

We now consider a third subsystem C with its wave $\chi(x_3, t)$ guiding its particle (or collection of particles), that will act as the measurer of the particle at lab L_B . In Fig. 4.1(c), $\chi(x_3, t)$ is represented by the dashed line. The measurer C is sufficiently close to interact with B , but not with A , which is emphasised by the intersecting light-cones between B and C . At a certain time t , we must then consider the evolution of the augmented field $\Psi(x_1, x_2, t)\chi(x_3, t)$. The evolution of the pilot-wave is unitary, such that

$$\Psi(x_1, x_2, t)\chi(x_3, t) \longrightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\underline{\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t')\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t')\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')} - \phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t')\phi_{\uparrow}(x_2, t')\chi_{\uparrow}(x_3, t')} \right], \quad t' > t. \quad (4.25)$$

The local interaction between B and C causes $\chi(x_3, t)$ to undergo meiosis. That is, in Fig. 4.1(c), the dashed wave splits into two thinner copies that are indicated by the solid lines at C . Meiosis only happens in the regions of the intersecting light-cones, that is, locally. The wave of the measurer produces a thinner and empty copy of itself $\chi_{\uparrow}(x_3, t')$, whose only difference to $\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')$ is that it would have measured (if populated) $\phi_{\uparrow}(x_2, t')$ instead of $\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t')$. The augmented underlined relative state in Eq. (4.25) shows that $\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')$ has now locally joined the evolved preferred foliation. If not for the guiding equations and the particles they describe, pilot-wave theory mechanics would be a local theory, although not Bell-local, to which we will return later.

In Bohmian mechanics, although some foliations are preferred over others, the importance of empty foliations cannot be overstated. It is the empty foliations that generate interference effects in the double-slit experiment. Without empty foliations, there would be no Pauli exclusion principle and no periodic table. It is precisely a second empty foliation of the form in Eq. (4.22) that guarantees zero resistivity in macroscopic superconductors. Quantum computations that explore the size of the Hilbert space imply that, in Bohmian mechanics, quantum information must be processed by the pilot-wave – the foliations – not by the particles.

4.5 Common objections to pilot-wave theory

Typical objections to Bohmian mechanics highlight its incompatibility with relativity, the autonomy of the pilot-wave, and the obsolescence of the particles. Possible responses to these objections can be found in Ref. [59]. Another less-mentioned objection is that Bohmian mechanics is necessarily formulated in the Schrödinger picture. This complicates the connection of Bohmian mechanics with the methods of quantum field theory. Perhaps one might attempt to formulate Bohmian mechanics in the Heisenberg picture by replacing the Schrödinger equation with the Heisenberg equation of motion. Then, what would a guiding equation look like? This could be a project idea for the

interested reader. However, we speculate that a guiding equation in the Heisenberg picture would be an artificial introduction.

4.5.1 Incompatibility with relativity

Bohmian mechanics is based on the non-relativistic Schrödinger equation. For this reason, Bohmian mechanics is incompatible with relativity. However, non-relativistic quantum mechanics itself is of course also incompatible with relativity, which can be partially remedied in relativistic quantum mechanics via the Dirac equation. The question is then whether a relativistic quantum field theory might be formulated. Several studies attempted a first go at this issue [45, 46, 67, 115]. However, the main tension between relativity and Bohmian mechanics is that Bohmian mechanics is explicitly non-local, whereas relativity is a local theory. If not for the particles, then Bohmian mechanics could be made local, but this is then just Everettian mechanics. Also, by having particles, Bell's 1964 no-go theorem enforces pilot-wave theory to be non-local. It is even more non-local than Newtonian gravitation, because there, the interaction decreases with the square of the distance between the particles, whereas in Bohmian mechanics it does not. Therefore, because of Bell's theorem, even relativistic Bohmian mechanics will be non-local. Either an apparent locality of relativity emerges from non-local Bohmian mechanics, or non-local hidden variable programs must be abandoned for compatibility with relativity.

4.5.2 The autonomous pilot-wave

Recall the pilot-wave program to solve a Bohmian problem below Eq. (4.13). After specifying the initial conditions for the particle positions $\{\mathbf{r}_a(0)\}$, the pilot-wave $\Psi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N, t)$ evolves autonomously. The pilot-wave affects the particles via the guiding equations, but the particles do not affect the pilot-wave. Therefore, the pilot-wave is independent of the particles. Perhaps that is just the way it is. However, if the theory without the particles would lead to the same currently testable predictions, the pilot-wave theory seems to carry excess baggage. According to Sec. 1.3, the particles of Bohmian mechanics are easy to vary, that is, we may consider or ignore them. Then, the better rival theory would be the one without hidden variables, which would be simpler, and perhaps even local (as we shall see). Unless pilot-wave theory makes predictions other than standard quantum mechanics, Bohmian mechanics would be refuted by Everettian mechanics. A promising research program for pilot-wave theory consists of finding the experimental differences, and evaluating whether Bohmian action at a distance could be measured. This would likely require non-equilibrium situations.

4.5.3 The predictions are the same as standard quantum mechanics

In light of the philosophy exposed in Sec. 1.3, this is a weak objection. The statement might be true for current technology but is unlikely to remain the case. Bohmian mechanics, by having an extended ontology as compared to quantum mechanics, should yield different outcomes in non-equilibrium situations. This is an underdeveloped research area, that in my opinion would deserve more attention.

However, for the sake of the argument, suppose that the predictions of pilot-wave theory are the same as quantum mechanics. Even then, according to the three criteria to identify good theories established in Sec. 1.3, pilot-wave theory accounts for the objects of the explanation, whereas Copenhagen-type theories do not. Also, Copenhagen is much easier to vary than pilot-wave theory. Therefore, the criteria would refute Copenhagen, in favour of pilot-wave theory.

4.5.4 The theory is formulated in the Schrödinger picture

Quantum mechanics can be formulated in different pictures and formalisms, including Schrödinger, Heisenberg, the Dirac picture, path integrals, second quantisation, and others. Yet, pilot-wave theory necessarily relies on the Schrödinger wave picture. This potentially complicates the connection with the methods of quantum field theory. We will see that Everettian mechanics does not suffer from this limitation.

4.5.5 Bohmian mechanics is Everettian in disguise

This criticism is expressed by Deutsch [34], and elaborated in Ref. [18]. Quoting Ref. [34]:

Their proponents think of them as single-universe theories. The idea is that the 'pilot-wave', i.e. the wave function of the multiverse, guides Bohm's single universe along its trajectory. This trajectory occupies one of the 'grooves' in that immensely complicated multidimensional wave function. The question that pilot-wave theorists must therefore address, and over which they invariably equivocate, is what are the unoccupied grooves? It is no good saying that they are merely a theoretical construct and do not exist physically, for they continually jostle both each other and the 'occupied' groove, affecting its trajectory. For example, we may in principle arrange for complex computations to be performed in vast numbers of 'unoccupied grooves' (i.e. in parallel universes), and then observe the results directly. So the 'unoccupied grooves' must be physically real. Moreover they obey the same laws of physics as the 'occupied groove' that is supposed to be 'the' universe. But that is just another way of saying that they are universes too. In short, pilot-wave theories are parallel-universes theories in a state of chronic denial.

4.6 Non-locality

Bohmian mechanics is explicitly non-local, just as Newtonian gravitation. Newton's law of universal gravitation informs us that the gravitational force experienced by two masses m_1 and m_2 is given by

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}, \quad (4.26)$$

where r is the distance between the masses and G is the gravitational constant. The law is explicitly non-local because the forces act regardless of how large r . If one object moves, the universe moves together. However, Eq. (4.26) is *weakly non-local*, because the most influential forces are those in the immediate vicinity, due to the $\sim 1/r^2$ dependence.

Such a decay of non-local influence is lacking in Bohmian mechanics. The non-local guiding equations in Eqs. (4.23) and (4.24) have no decay parameter. The non-local influence remains the same, regardless of the distance. For this reason, Bohmian mechanics is even more non-local than Newtonian gravity.

Some authors highlight that although Bohmian mechanics is explicitly non-local, the pilot-wave does not permit communication faster than the speed of light [46, 115]. However, a careful study of non-equilibrium situations [2], indicates that instant non-local communication between Bohmian particles should be possible. This is an interesting open research area, which establishes a crucial experimental test for pilot-wave theory.

For reasons that will be explained in the next chapter, I find it unlikely that the laws of nature are intrinsically non-local. Yet, admittedly, I think it would be amazing if it were. Imagine a game developer writing an open-world game (such as Red Dead Redemption or Grand Theft Auto), but the programmer limits the character's speed to 1 mm/h. Most of the area of the open world would remain unexplored and useless from the point of view of the playable character. It is like a sloth

trying to explore the earth in its lifetime. This is a metaphor to compare the speed of light to the observable size of the cosmos. If we are to be restricted to the speed of light, and ignore speculated space-time bending technologies, then we are bound to be sloths in the universe. We are then forever limited to our little grain of sand. However, if true non-locality exists, such that instantaneous influence on space-like separated regions would be possible, humanity could gradually expand its bubble, and at least partially explore space. Live long and prosper.

Chapter 5

Everettian mechanics

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we apply Occam's razor to quantum theory and explore how unitary theory may be interpreted. Everettian mechanics, historically and perhaps regrettably, is more widely recognized as the *many-worlds interpretation* of quantum mechanics. This theory can be viewed as the simpler, younger sibling of Bohmian mechanics. Both theories share key characteristics: they are unitary, deterministic, and universal. The previous chapter was designed, in part, to prepare the groundwork for Everettian mechanics. Deriving Everettian mechanics from Bohmian mechanics requires removing the one element that is relatively straightforward to eliminate in the pilot-wave theory: the particles. What remains is the pilot-wave—without anything to pilot. In the Schrödinger picture, only the wave exists. What we traditionally refer to as particles are, in this framework, simply localized manifestations of the field. The resulting theory is remarkably resistant to variation.

Carroll refers to the theory as *mad-dog austere* minimal quantum mechanics [21]. Everettian mechanics is quantum state realism. Deutsch argues that Everettian is not even an interpretation, but the explanation of quantum mechanics [104]:

I'm not going to refer to Everett's discovery as an "interpretation" – nor even as the interpretation of quantum theory, though that's what it is (no other is known). That is because the term "interpretation" has come to have connotations that misrepresent not just quantum theory but science in general. We don't speak of the existence of dinosaurs millions of years ago as being "an interpretation of our best theory of fossils." We claim that it is the explanation of fossils. And the theory isn't primarily about fossils: it's about dinosaurs. We claim that there really were dinosaurs, even though there is an infinity of rival "interpretations" of the same data which make all the same predictions and yet say that the dinosaurs weren't there.

According to Wallace [121], Everettian mechanics "*is just quantum mechanics itself, read literally, straightforwardly—naively, if you will—as a direct description of the physical world, just like any other microphysical theory.*"

Given these introductory remarks, the reader may have noticed that the author, by the time of writing, is biased towards Everettian mechanics. I write this sentence in the hope that the reader is inoculated against my bias, so after being exposed to it, the reader can make up his/her own mind. Admittedly, according to my view, Everettian mechanics is currently the most promising deterministic and realistic view of quantum theory. Its ideas provoked the development of the decoherence program [109, 128], quantum computing and artificial intelligence [33, 37], and currently motivates more general theories such as constructor theory [42, 79].

Unlike frequently advertised, Everettian quantum theory is more testable than its rivals [40]. It explains why monitors observe certain outcomes, but not others. The Born rule is not part of the

theory, and yet, Everettian mechanics explains why rational observers associate a probability of a given outcome according to the Born rule [36]. The theory explains where quantum information is processed, with the same clarity as in classical mechanics. Also, it is a realistic and local non-hidden variable theory [9, 41, 75, 100], which facilitates the connection with general relativity. This was also one of Everett's original motivations [49].

Despite the growing success and adepts, Everettian theory is and will likely continue to be a controversial and perhaps even arcane subject. Since superpositions are intrinsic to quantum systems, and by extending the quantum theory to observers, one arrives at superpositions not only of the system under study but also of the observer itself. This escapes the *common sense* of the instrumentalist. One of the speculated reasons for controversy might be that for many, "common sense realism comes first, i.e., before scientific realism: all our reasons to *believe* our scientific theories are based on observations of the macroscopic world (including of course, positions of pointers and meter readings) [16]." This instrumentalist stance contrasts with the realist philosophy outlined in Chap. 1, where according to Deutsch: "Our best theories are not only truer than common sense, they make more sense than common sense. [35]" This is an example where clarifying each philosophy of science would be helpful before entering a heated debate. As Brown puts it [17]:

But shocks in physics come and go. There must have been similar incredulity on the part of many medieval scholars in relation to the Copernican world-view. And not just because of the claim that the Earth moves; unless wedded to an Aristotelian cosmos or having religious scruples based on scripture, careful thinkers would probably have been more shocked by the size of the Copernican cosmos – involving 'vast useless voids' – required to explain the visual absence of stellar parallax over the course of the year. And according to modern cosmology, the universe is far vaster than even Galileo estimated. This may be a source of wonder, but today few scientists if any regard it as unbelievable; the scientific community has gotten used to the idea. (It is notable, by the way, that some of the strongest advocates of Everettian quantum mechanics are cosmologists, who like Everett envisage a quantum cosmology that is internally complete, i.e. needs no reference to observers external to the universe.)

5.2 Motivation: single slit diffraction

If a quantum particle moves through a narrow single slit, it generally deviates from its initially rectilinear movement. This phenomenon is called diffraction. It is a general wave phenomena, and happens whenever a wave encounters an obstruction. Waves are an emergent collective phenomena. Everettian quantum theory recognizes that the diffraction of a single particle through a slit, is actually a collective phenomena, where the perturbations/excitations of the wave-field are particles. We motivate this idea in this section.

We first recall the classical theory of wave diffraction through a single slit [65]. The Huygens–Fresnel principle states that every point on a wavefront can be considered a source of secondary spherical waves, which propagate outward with the same frequency as the original wavefront. The overall field at any subsequent point in space is determined by the superposition of all these secondary waves, resulting in the new wavefront. All the points taken together make up the wave. Fig. 5.1 shows an initial plane wave with wavelength λ diffracting through a slit of size \overline{AB} . On each point on the incoming wave, we could draw points from which the secondary wave of equal wavelength emanate. The scale of the wavelength is adapted for visualization in Fig. 5.1. Then, the secondary waves emanating from the points going through the slit will travel different distances up to a point P , where they interfere. The maximum path difference is $\Lambda = |\overline{AP} - \overline{BP}|$, which comes from particles at the extremes of the aperture. From the figure we see that $\Lambda \leq \overline{AB}$, where \overline{AB} is the slits' size. If for simplicity we assume that $\lambda > \overline{AB}$, then we know that $\lambda > \Lambda$. This guarantees

Figure 5.1: Single slit wave diffraction.

that wherever P is, the secondary waves interfere constructively at that point, with varying degrees. Due to the diffraction, that is, the effect an element of the wave feels from the other elements, only a small amount of point streamlines will follow a perfectly straight trajectory.

Now let us consider quantum theory, and recall what happens for a single particle going through a single slit. By repeating the experiment many times, we know that just like in the classical case, most of the particles diffract. Even more, if the quantum experiment is repeated as many times as there are particles in the classical wave, a continuous wave interference pattern is reconstructed. The single particle quantum experiment behaves as if there existed a collective wave, with the only difference that all other points on the wave are transparent. In Ref. [35], Deutsch calls the transparent particles *shadows*.

The reader may wonder whether the red particle simply corresponds to the Bohmian particle in pilot-wave theory. It does not, because here, the particles make up the wave. The wave is all there is, and there is no extra Bohmian particle riding it. However, why is only one particle among a host of many visible? To understand this we must investigate how the interaction of the host of particles interacts with the measurer.

5.3 Stratification of the wave

In this section, we discuss the entangling of the three interacting sub-systems discussed in Sec. 4.4 and Fig. 4.1 in the context of Bohmian mechanics. Perhaps the reader may review Sec. 4.4 first.

Given that foliations appear to play the central role in quantum phenomena, one can examine what happens if one gets rid of the Bohmian particles, and with them, the guiding equations. Then one is left with a local non-hidden variable theory called Everettian mechanics [49]. At most, one might use Bohmian test particles to track a particular foliation; in analogy to electrostatics, where we use test charges to track electric fields at a particular position. Everettian mechanics has evolved into a family of unitary quantum mechanics interpretations of which some are considered to be non-local and others local [118]. Here we only consider Oxford-type Everettian mechanics [9, 17, 41, 75, 121], which is a local theory.

The entangled state in Eq. (4.25), reproduced here:

$$\Psi(x_1, x_2, t)\chi(x_3, t) \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t')\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t')\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t') - \phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t')\phi_{\uparrow}(x_2, t')\chi_{\uparrow}(x_3, t')], \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.2: Analogy of foliations with strata. The fact that an ant walks through a particular stratum, does not mean that other strata don't exist. In Bohmian mechanics, the foliations represent the wave, and the ant the particle. Image taken from Ref. [112].

still defines two foliations, but none of them now receive preferred status. The part of $\chi(x_3, t)$ involved in the interaction with B (the region of the intersecting light-cones) foliates into the thinner $\chi_{\uparrow}(x_3, t')$ and $\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')$ states. It is the characteristic length scale of the local interactions that sets the physical size of local foliations [75, 117]. Unlike frequently advertised, foliations are better thought of as local bubbles, not as the entire universe splitting [75], which would be a non-local process. In the absence of further interactions, the two foliations evolve autonomously.

In Bohmian mechanics, the particle selects a preferred foliation, either $\chi_{\uparrow}(x_3, t')$ or $\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')$. In Everettian mechanics, the measuring particle is the packet $\chi(x_3, t)$. In a very small region of space, set by the local interactions, $\chi(x_3, t)$ is divided into two branches. An analogy can be drawn with tree roots, where the main root divides into other branches. The way the root branches depends on how it interacts with the local environment (the soil). These branches are then best imagined as local bubbles, in contrast to the entire universe branching as some many-worlds interpretations induce us to think.

It may help to think of the bubbles and foliations as strata in rocks. Local interactions inevitably stratify the wave. In Bohmian mechanics, the particles populate a minority of strata. In Fig. 5.2 we illustrate the analogy of Everettian foliations with rock strata. Strata may sometimes look approximately parallel, they bifurcate, and sometimes they even merge, just as the foliations in quantum mechanics. It is not because the ant walks through a specific stratum, that the other layers do not exist. In tree branches and strata, phenomena happening on each layer may evolve autonomously. However, when there is interference between foliations, distinguishing between them becomes blurry, and the entire tree or rock is necessary to explain what happens in the world. It would be weird to call a tree or a rock a *multiverse* composed of *many worlds*. This is why we prefer *Everettian mechanics*. The size of the world is set by the dimension of Hilbert space.

Foliations (or relative states) can be understood both in the Schrödinger [49] and in the Heisenberg picture [75]. Although not yet explicitly formulated, there are no expected difficulties in other representations, such as the interaction picture and second quantization. One of the advantages of formulating observables in the Heisenberg picture is that all observables are local, even entangled observables [9, 41, 75]; we will see this explicitly in later chapters. Nonetheless, the locality of Everettian mechanics can also be understood in the Schrödinger picture [117].

5.3.1 Where are the foliations?

Similar to the complex logarithm, the global wave-function $\mathcal{W}(x_1, x_2; t) = \Psi(x_1, x_2, t)\chi(x_3, t)$ is multi-valued at the positions. Where do these values occur? Well, exactly at the specified positions. If $\chi_{\uparrow}(x_3, t')$ registered \uparrow at x_3 , where does $\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')$ register \downarrow ? By just reading off the arguments of $\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')$, the answer is also at x_3 . In the absence of further interactions $\chi_{\uparrow}(x_3, t')$ and $\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t')$ evolve independently at x_3 .

The Everettian explanation leads us to recognise that each point in space-time has a huge internal Hilbert space structure. In the paragraph above, there are two strata at x_3 , but only one stratum is locally accessible for a particular observer. This should not strike us as too unfamiliar. To show this, let us consider an imperfect analogy from classical mechanics: the projectile motion of a rod. The centre of mass of the rod describes a parabola, but a generic point on the rod does not. For each centre of mass position, there is an internal structure relative to that position. Although the sensors at the rod extremities register a different trajectory, they can always be described relative to the centre of mass. An observer which is far away from the rod will hardly access the rods internal structure, and will only see a parabola.

5.3.2 Do foliations exist?

Are lightbulbs in video games real? Perhaps many of us will hastily come to the apparently self-evident conclusion: of course not. The purportedly superficial reason is that the lightbulb only exists in the game. It is considered virtual because, although it shares similar properties with a real lightbulb, the virtual lightbulb has no physical instantiation in the real world.

However, a more meticulous analysis reveals that the virtual system is just as physical as the real lightbulb. Despite differing properties from its non-game counterpart, the virtual system must find physical instantiation on hardware. Furthermore, toggling the lightbulb in the game necessitates actual work from the hardware; in other words, lightbulbs in a game consume electrical energy. What we commonly refer to as games are essentially specific and simplified physical instantiations of their non-game counterparts. According to this rationale, games are just as real.

Some may argue that Everettian foliations do not truly exist; instead, they are considered virtual machinery designed to simulate the correct result on the actual preferred foliation. According to this inconsistent perspective, the structure of Hilbert space functions akin to a game, ultimately conveying a result to the purported real world at the conclusion of the computation. However, in Everettian mechanics, the stratified copies are not simplified instantiations; they are identical, differing only in potentially recording a distinct value of the projection. If a computation occurred, its must have occurred on something that exists. Information is physical. For those interested in further exploring the consequences of the physical instantiations of information, may consult the references on constructor theory [38, 42, 79, 80]. Another startling consequence of the existence of foliations is the electron degeneracy pressure due to the Pauli exclusion principle, which we briefly discuss in Sec. 5.5.

5.4 Common objections

Most objections to Everettian mechanics relate to an instrumentalist stance [37, 40]. Part of the unease towards Everettian mechanics is that whereas in orthodox views a measurement interaction changes the system, in unitary quantum mechanics, a measurement changes the observer. See Fig. 4.1(c). Let us now discuss specific objections to Everettian quantum theory.

5.4.1 There are too many foliations

A way to differentiate interpretations of quantum mechanics is to ask how a particular interpretation does away with the many foliations. Everettian mechanics recognises all foliations. Bohmian mechanics prefers certain foliations. In superdeterminism, foliations are an average description of the hidden variables. Collapse-type interpretations obliterate all foliations upon measurement or event, except for one. As for the unitary quantum interpretations, relational quantum mechanics has a reduced ontology as compared to Everettian mechanics [82].

Foliations were neither assumed nor added to quantum mechanics; they are a consequence of associating physical significance with Hilbert space. The same foliations are also present in Bohmian mechanics. They are also present in the Copenhagen interpretation until the system is measured. Copenhagen is Everettian until a special type of interaction happens. It is just not clear what makes some interactions special. Interference and entanglement arise due to the physics of interacting foliations. There appears to be no way to discuss quantum effects without involving foliations. Asserting that there are too many foliations is a rather subjective and weak objection. A popular escape from the foliations is to change the philosophy of science altogether, stating that science is about gambling, prediction, and the agents personal subjective experience. To learn more about this attitude, the reader may consult Ref. [29].

Do particles exist?

In classical mechanics, we might abstain from saying that particles exist. However, it remains remarkably practical to describe the world as if particles existed. Likewise, in unitary quantum mechanics, we might abstain from saying that the superposition principle applies to observers and that foliations exist. However, it remains terribly useful to describe the world as if foliations existed. In Everettian quantum theory, mathematics means something.

5.4.2 The theory is not falsifiable

Everettian mechanics assumes a philosophical realist stance by recognising that all mathematical elements map to reality. This makes Everettian mechanics a delicate interpretation since the observation of collapse, hidden variables, non-local phenomena, or an unexpected saturation of quantum computation times would falsify it. Possible experimental tests proposed for Everettian mechanics include Wigner's friend-type experiments [32] that could perhaps soon be simulated in a quantum computer [92], or an artificial intelligence running on a quantum computer [33]. Other proposals suggest looking at the energy balance of a measurement [20], and contrasts with objective collapse theories [40]. An interesting mathematical direction might be to design no-go theorems specifically targeted for Everettian mechanics [56].

Perhaps what some mean is that Everettian mechanics makes predictions that are currently untestable with our existing technology. This is indeed true, but it's important to note that many well-established scientific theories share this characteristic. For instance, general relativity describes events within a black hole, even though these phenomena are currently beyond our observational capabilities. It is rather uncontroversial that some stars have iron cores, although the iron remains undetected. However, we have confidence in these claims because they are consistent with our best available theories of star formation. Likewise, the vast majority of people believe in the effectiveness of vaccines, despite the unobservable counterfactual consequences of not vaccinating. In science, the predictive power and explanatory value of a theory often extend beyond what can be immediately observed or tested.

There is considerable confusion regarding how Popper's criterion of falsifiability applies to scientific theories. According to Popper, if a crucial test falsifies even a single, specific prediction of a theory, the entire theory is considered falsified. For instance, in the case of general relativity,

the bending of light due to spacetime curvature is a testable prediction, which lends the theory its scientific character. However, many aspects of general relativity remain untestable. This does not imply that the untestable components are unscientific. Attempting to divide a single, self-consistent theory into "scientific" and "non-scientific" parts is arbitrary and subjective, often leading to contradictions. Popper's criterion is most effectively applied to the theory as a whole. The application of Popper's philosophy of science to the logic of experimental testing in Everettian quantum theory is discussed in detail in Ref. [40].

5.4.3 The preferred basis problem

This was a historical and important critique of the Everettian program that was solved by understanding the properties of entanglement, which we discussed in Sec. 3.2. In the earlier stages of Everettian mechanics [43], foliations were thought to arise from superposition states. Consider again the system in Fig. 4.1. Before interactions, the three particle wave-function is

$$\mathcal{W}(x_1, x_2; t_0) = \overbrace{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t_0) + \phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t_0)]}^A \overbrace{\phi(x_2, t_0)}^B \overbrace{\chi(x_3, t_0)}^C. \quad (5.2)$$

Here, the foliations indeed emerged because particle A is in a superposition state when described relative to B and C . However, A is in a superposition relative to a particular basis (reference frame). We might very well just rotate the system A to get rid of the superposition, and hence, of the foliations. If this were so, then foliations would be rather arbitrary and basis-dependent, which would be a very unappealing aspect of the theory.

The fact that there is no basis problem is best appreciated considering the wave-function after all interactions, where

$$\mathcal{W}(x_1, x_2; t') = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\phi_{\uparrow}(x_1, t')\phi_{\downarrow}(x_2, t')\chi_{\downarrow}(x_3, t') - \phi_{\downarrow}(x_1, t')\phi_{\uparrow}(x_2, t')\chi_{\uparrow}(x_3, t')]. \quad (5.3)$$

A change of basis of \mathcal{W} may change the wave-packets, which is unsurprising, but it does not get rid of the entanglement. As long as one defines foliations from entanglement, there is no basis problem.

The basis problem still plagues orthodox interpretations, where a particular basis is chosen at the user's convenience [109]. There, the problem might be alleviated, but not fully solved in the decoherence program.

5.4.4 What is probability?

Unitary quantum mechanics is inherently deterministic, suggesting that the Born rule is not fundamental but rather emergent. Consequently, it must account for the apparent stochasticity of measurement outcomes. Various complementary approaches have been proposed to explain the Born rule. One class of reasoning involves self-locating uncertainty, as discussed in [110], while others rely on methods grounded in decoherence [128]. The philosophy of probability in mathematics and physics remains an open problem, which propagates to quantum theory, partially explaining the diversity of approaches to the Born rule in unitary quantum theory. Among these approaches, the decision-theoretic framework, initially introduced by Deutsch [36] and further developed by Wallace [121] and Marletto [79], offers a particularly notable perspective.

This decision-theoretic approach can be traced back to Gerolamo Cardano's original motivations for developing probability theory in a deterministic context. Cardano's aim was to maximize his gains in card games, where probability arose due to the player's ignorance of other players' cards. Despite the unpredictability of outcomes, Cardano demonstrated a rational way to associate probabilities with game outcomes.

In a lecture titled *Physics without probability* [39], Deutsch offers an illustrative scenario involving a gambling machine in a casino. The game is played by inserting a casino token into the machine. When we pull the machine's handle, the machine prepares a quantum state in the eigenbasis of an observable \hat{X} , say $|\psi\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3}}|2.7\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|5.9\rangle$. The machine then measures the observable \hat{X} , so we already know in advance that the result displayed by the machine must be either 2.7 or 5.9. The quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ is no secret to the player. It is then a rational decision-theoretic problem to associate probabilities with these two possible outcomes with the aim of maximising the player's gains. The payoff of the machine will be the resulting eigenvalue in casino tokens displayed by the machine, which does not have to be an integer number. All the machines in the casino are identical, except for the quantum system $|\psi\rangle$ they prepare. If a machine happens to prepare a state $|\psi\rangle = |1.4\rangle$, then this is no game of chance since it is just a matter of inserting a token and receiving the payoff of 1.4 tokens. Such a machine may be called *classical*, because it can be implemented without quantum technology. In general, a rational player should be willing to play if the eigenvalue of \hat{X} is larger than one. Deutsch showed that a rational decision-maker behaves "as if he believed that each possible outcome x_a had a probability given by the Born rule $|\langle x_a|\psi\rangle|^2$, and as if he were maximising the probabilistic expectation value of the pay-off." This proves the Born rule without collapse, and in addition, explains how it comes about.

An alternative way to discuss the same issue is via sleeping beauty like arguments, as presented by Max Tegmark in Ref. [104]. The paraphrased argument goes like this. You go to a highly technological clinic, say in São Paulo, with the objective of constructing a perfect clone of yourself. The procedure will be done while you sleep. The only difference between the now two identical subjects (including their memories) is that one stays in São Paulo, whereas the other is transferred to Rio de Janeiro. You wake up, and you know with certainty that you are either in São Paulo or Rio de Janeiro. The anaesthesiologist now asks you to bet on the chance you woken up in São Paulo. What probability will you choose? Its 50%. The argument can be generalized using decision theory to show that all copies will always bet according to the Born rule. Once a clone discovers in which city that it is, the result will feel just like a random outcome.

5.4.5 Conservation laws

Doesn't the meiosis of the measurer violate conservation laws such as the number of systems and the total energy? No. If the Hilbert space of the system is finite, the number of foliations is fixed by the dimension of the Hilbert space. Foliation locally differentiate or, in coherent quantum-controlled experiments, become fungible again. There is no loss or creation of foliations. If the Hilbert space is infinite, each foliation has a smooth measure. As for energy, it is conserved on average, as described in the textbooks [62]. However, during a measurement, energy is not conserved in quantum mechanics, nor in the Copenhagen interpretation, or in Everettian mechanics. The energy balance behaves differently in these theories, allowing for experimental tests based on the lack of energy conservation [20].

Problem 5.1: In Chap. 3, we discussed the quantum evolution of a four-qubit computational network. See Fig. 3.1. Describe and interpret the state of the network for each time step in the context of Everettian mechanics.

5.5 Electron degeneracy pressure

At absolute zero, an ideal gas of electrons has a finite pressure. Where does this pressure come from? We are usually informed that the pressure is a consequence of the Pauli exclusion principle. Since Everett provided us with a clear physical substrate, we may now understand what causes the pressure.

Let particle A be initially described by the wave-packet $\psi_\mu(A)$ and particle B by $\psi_\nu(B)$, where μ, ν encode all the quantum numbers. A quantum number may encode for instance the momenta and spin or site and spin in a lattice model. If the particles are brought together, they interact and evolve to a generic entangled state

$$\Psi = \alpha\psi_\mu(A)\psi_\nu(B) + \beta\psi_\mu(B)\psi_\nu(A), \quad (5.4)$$

where α, β are complex coefficients. Due to the permutation symmetry of the two identical particles, there are two possibilities for the combined state, namely:

$$\Psi_\pm = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\psi_\mu(A)\psi_\nu(B) \pm \psi_\mu(B)\psi_\nu(A)]. \quad (5.5)$$

The particles with the Ψ_+ entangled state are *bosons*, and Ψ_- are *fermions*.

For $\mu = \nu$, $\Psi_- = 0$, which shows that fermions cannot have the same quantum numbers. The more similar $\psi_\mu(A)$ becomes to $\psi_\nu(B)$, the stronger the exchange interaction between the particles.

If bosons become too similar ($\mu = \nu$), the entangled state in Eq. (5.5) defining two foliations might fuse together to form a single stratum. In the language of Everettian mechanics, we say that the particles are *fungible* since it becomes senseless to distinguish between them, just like it is meaningless to distinguish two tree branches that rejoined [37]. However, fermions cannot become fungible. Fermions are forced to remain in the entangled state in Eq. (5.5). What one usually refers to as the Pauli exchange interaction is actually one foliation pressing against the other, thereby avoiding fungibility (unentangling). The electron degeneracy pressure arises not from any electromagnetic interaction but from electrons being kicked by other foliations. This is a striking macroscopic example of the necessity of understanding all interacting foliations. If there were a collapse, there would be no Pauli pressure.

5.6 The superposition principle as multiplicity

5.6.1 Multiplicity vs. counterfactuals

The measurement problem outlined in Sec. 1.7 is typically presented as a quandary. It seems that we are faced with two options: either replace quantum theory with an alternative, such as a hidden variable theory or a future theory of quantum gravity, or reconsider our philosophy of science, as demonstrated in the Qubism program [53, 54]. Hugh Everett's paper [49] demonstrated that this dilemma is false.

To discuss this, I employ an example akin to the one presented by Wallace [121]. Consider a classical electromagnetic field that is a superposition of two other fields $\mathbf{R}(x, t) = 0.5\mathbf{R}_A(x, t) + 0.5\mathbf{R}_B(x, t)$. Here, \mathbf{R}_A represents the field configuration of a radio station signal A , and \mathbf{R}_B represents radio station B . Does the fact that \mathbf{R} contains coexisting radio stations imply that if someone is listening to A , B does not exist? Of course not. There is a mundane description of \mathbf{R} . Contrary to frequent misconceptions, \mathbf{R} does not describe indefiniteness; rather, \mathbf{R} denotes *multiplicity*.

A critic might contend that, unlike radio signals where a listener can switch stations at any moment, we currently lack the ability to detect quantum foliations. However, this limitation is only temporary, contingent on our current technological capabilities. We are in the early stages of developing devices with the capacity to *change frequencies*, exemplified by emerging technologies like quantum computers, albeit currently plagued by significant noise and decoherence. In this context, Everettian quantum theory is just quantum mechanics, akin to our interpretation of classical waves. No change in philosophy or quantum theory is required.

A more nuanced critique may interpret superposition as counter-factuality, instead of multiplicity. For instance, in a chess game, the player chooses his move based on what could happen (counterfactuals). Then, although most of the things that could happen actually did not, the counterfactuals influenced the actual move (the fact). How do we know if quantum mechanics describes multiplicity or counter-factuality? In a quantum computer, all its foliations process information, whereas the chess board only processes the user's final decision. A chess board is a different information medium than a quantum computer, which is the subject of constructor theory. However, even in chess, one can argue that the player's brain physically worked out all counterfactuals, which consumed more calories than if the player only would have thought of a single line.

5.6.2 The double-slit experiment

How does unitary quantum mechanics explain the paradigmatic double-slit experiment? In Sec. 5.5 we saw that two particles set up two foliations, see Eq. (5.5). We do not know whether the Hilbert space of the cosmos is finite or infinite. Let us assume that the observable universe has of the order of 10^{80} particles. Also, assuming that it is the number of particles that determines the size of Hilbert space, and hence also the number of foliations, we could estimate the universe (or an interacting multi-verse) to have about $2^{10^{80}}$ foliations, which larger than a googol (but smaller than a googolplex). Therefore, when considering a single particle double-slit interference experiment, we must take into account all the foliations where exactly the same experiment is taking place at the same time.

If someone on a particular branch of the wave-function decides to perform a single-particle interference experiment, there will be (almost) a continuum of both fungible and very similar foliations doing the same. If on one foliation, a particle is shot in the direction of the slits, there a collection of particles on other foliations that accompany the particle. These collectively form a wave packet that undergoes diffraction at the slits. Contrary to the common imagery of a single electron splitting at the slits, it is more illustrative to envision a multitude of particles from different foliations converging towards the slits, showcasing how quantum dynamics diversify the ensemble's behaviour.

The collection of particles described by the packet enlarges, and by the time it reaches the slits, the packet is large enough to go through both slits. From the perspective of a single branch, the particle only goes through one slit, but interferes with the once fungible copies that went through the other slit on another branch. For this reason, the particle on a particular branch does not follow a straight line, because its slightly different copies are close enough to have a causal influence on it. The same is true for a single slit experiment, which was motivated in Sec. 5.2.

The presence of a particle detector near one of the slits eliminates the interference pattern, raising the question of how detection disrupts the interaction among particles across branches. When the detector (along with its fungible counterparts) interacts with the wave packet, it becomes entangled, leading to the branching of the detector into distinct copies on separate branches. This branching process, known as decoherence, prevents the previously coherent states from interfering. Decoherence occurs whether the interaction is at the slits or later at a detection screen, although placing a detector at the slits prompts earlier decoherence, causing each branch to evolve independently immediately afterward.

Why can't the detector predict where it will detect the particle? Because the detector does not know into which copy it will evolve into. The uncertainty principle does not mean that nature is intrinsically stochastic. It means that the detector copies must be sufficiently diverse. Uncertainty is a feature of a single-branch view.

Problem 5.2: *Atomic orbitals.* Provide the Everettian explanation for atomic orbitals.

5.7 Conclusion

I conclude this section with an analogy. Consider two identical transverse pulses on a string moving towards each other. The only difference between the pulses is that they have opposite amplitudes, such that when the pulses are perfectly superposed, they cancel each other out. If one takes a picture of the string at the moment of complete destructive interference, the camera registers a perfectly straight string. Is there any physical difference between the interfering string and another perfectly straight string hosting no progressing waves? From the perspective of a camera at the moment of destructive interference, there is not. However, the physical situations are drastically distinct. In the interfering string, the internal tensions are such that, at later times, the two pulses continue to progress as if they never interacted. Moreover, there is energy transport through the interfering string. As for the undisturbed straight string that never hosted pulses, it remains straight at later times and does not transfer energy. At the time of destructive interference, a conventional camera would say that both strings are identical. But a physicist would recognize the deeper underlying physics. The camera represents the orthodox view, and the physicist in an Everettian.

Chapter 6

The Schrödinger picture

The two basic pictures of quantum mechanics are the Schrödinger and the Heisenberg pictures. There are also higher-level formalisms, such as second quantization, path integral methods, and others. The low-level pictures, Heisenberg and Schrödinger, are often said to be equivalent. This is indeed the case for the purposes of calculating expectation values. However, if one wishes to understand what occurs *under the hood*, then Schrödinger and Heisenberg are not equivalent. This is less known in the physics community but has been long known since Dirac [44].

In this preparatory chapter, we discuss the Schrödinger and Heisenberg pictures of quantum mechanics and show how they differ. We argue that the Heisenberg picture is the better one to understand the foundational issues. On the other hand, the Schrödinger picture is largely used in the decoherence program via density matrices. For this reason, we take the opportunity to introduce the necessary elements of mixed states in preparation for the next chapters.

6.1 Expectation values

The Schrödinger picture is the most familiar one, since it is mostly used in introductory textbooks [62]. The reason for this is that it is remarkably simple to solve single and two-particle problems in the Schrödinger picture. In contrast, it is exceptionally hard to solve for instance a particle in a box in the Heisenberg picture [101]. The Heisenberg picture and Schrödinger-Heisenberg hybrids (the interaction picture) become more useful for many-particle systems. Most toy examples in quantum information are also discussed in the Schrödinger picture [90]. This however leads to conceptual misunderstandings of the underlying physics, as for instance thinking that quantum teleportation is a non-local effect [10]. In Chap. 8 we show that this is not the case.

Consider a system initialised in the state $|0\rangle$. Any other state might be found by unitarily ($UU^\dagger = 1$) evolving the initial state $|\Psi\rangle = U|0\rangle$. The time-dependent state vector evolves according to the Schrödinger equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} |\Psi(t)\rangle = \mathcal{H} |\Psi(t)\rangle. \quad (6.1)$$

The expectation value of an observable \hat{A} , when the state is $|\Psi\rangle$ is given by:

$$\langle \hat{A} \rangle = \langle \Psi | \hat{A} | \Psi \rangle = \langle 0 | U^\dagger \hat{A} U | 0 \rangle. \quad (6.2)$$

In the Schrödinger picture, if the Hamiltonian is time independent, then the observables are also fixed, and the state vector $|\Psi(t)\rangle$ carries the time dependence. To access all quantum information associated with an observable, we must specify not only the observable \hat{A} , but also the time-dependent state vector $|\Psi(t)\rangle$. In the Schrödinger picture, information is split between the observable \hat{A} and the state vector $|\Psi(t)\rangle$. We will soon see that because of this information splitting, the information flow is less transparent in the Schrödinger picture.

Problem 6.1: Show that if \mathcal{H} is independent of time, then $U(t) = \exp(-i\mathcal{H}t/\hbar)$. See Ref. [62].

6.2 The density matrix

Consider the orthonormal basis set $\{|\psi_i\rangle\}$. We may express any pure state in terms of the basis as $|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^d c_i |\psi_i\rangle$, where d is the dimension of Hilbert space, and $\sum_i |c_i|^2 = 1$. From this pure state, we may construct a matrix

$$\hat{\rho} = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| = \sum_{i,j} c_i c_j^* |\psi_i\rangle\langle\psi_j|, \quad (6.3)$$

which is called the density matrix. The off-diagonal $i \neq j$ terms in the density matrix are often called interference elements. We must keep in mind that the existence of such terms is basis-dependent.

Problem 6.2: Show that the trace of the density matrix $\text{tr } \hat{\rho} = 1$.

Consider an observable \hat{A} with its corresponding eigenbasis $\{|a_i\rangle\}$, such that $\hat{A}|a_i\rangle = a_i|a_i\rangle$, where a_i are the eigenvalues. The expectation value of the observable \hat{A} when the system is in the arbitrary pure state $|\psi\rangle$ is

$$\langle\hat{A}\rangle = \langle\psi|\hat{A}|\psi\rangle = \sum_i a_i |\langle a_i|\psi\rangle|^2 = \sum_i a_i p_i, \quad p_i = |\langle a_i|\psi\rangle|^2, \quad (6.4)$$

where we utilised the resolution of the identity $\mathbb{I} = \sum_i |a_i\rangle\langle a_i|$. The main use of the density matrix is that it allows us to calculate the expectation value.

Problem 6.3: *Expectation value of a pure state.* Show that the expectation value of a pure state may be alternatively calculated as

$$\langle\hat{A}\rangle = \text{tr}(\hat{\rho}\hat{A}). \quad (6.5)$$

We may use either Eq. (6.4) or Eq. (6.5) to calculate $\langle\hat{A}\rangle$. The latter is especially useful because it generalises also to mixed states.

6.2.1 The generalised density matrix for mixed states

Consider the classical ensemble of pure states $\{|\phi_i\rangle\}$ with probability distribution $\sum_i w_i = 1$. A mixed quantum state is a probabilistic mixture of pure states. The nature of the mixture statistic is classical. The expectation value that generalises Eq. (6.4) is [103]

$$[\hat{A}] = \sum_i w_i \langle\phi_i|\hat{A}|\phi_i\rangle = \sum_{i,\nu} w_i |\langle a_\nu|\phi_i\rangle|^2 a_\nu. \quad (6.6)$$

The w_i are the classical probabilities, whereas $|\langle a_\nu|\phi_i\rangle|^2$ are the quantum probabilities. The classical probability distribution arises from statistical mechanics, where uncertainty arises not because nature is intrinsically stochastic, but because we are ignorant about the exact microstates of the system. The quantum probability distribution comes from the Born rule $p_{i,\nu} = |\langle a_\nu|\phi_i\rangle|^2$. Orthodox interpretations say that this distribution arises from the intrinsic indeterminism of quantum mechanics. However, in unitary Everettian quantum mechanics, there is nothing intrinsically stochastic.

Again, unpredictability does not arise from intrinsic randomness, but from the observer's ignorance. A particular system hardly has access to the entire density matrix. Therefore, in unitary quantum mechanics, although the two probability distributions have different origins, none of them arises from intrinsic indeterminism, but rather from ignorance.

The generalised density matrix for mixed-states is

$$\hat{\rho} = \sum_i w_i |\phi_i\rangle\langle\phi_i|. \quad (6.7)$$

Problem 6.4: *Expectation value for mixed-states.* Show that

$$[\hat{A}] = \text{tr}(\hat{\rho}\hat{A}), \quad (6.8)$$

where $\hat{\rho}$ is given by Eq. (6.7).

Whatever the density matrix, pure or mixed, the expectation value of an observable \hat{A} can be calculated using Eq. (6.8).

6.3 Reduced density matrices

Consider two systems A and B described by the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B$. The two systems might be entangled, such that

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|a_1\rangle|b_1\rangle + |a_2\rangle|b_2\rangle), \quad (6.9)$$

where $|a_i\rangle$ and $|b_i\rangle$ are arbitrary states. We frequently wish to calculate the expectation values of the A system only. We now show that for this purpose, A does not need the complete knowledge of the density matrix $\hat{\rho} = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ (whew!). All A needs is the reduced density matrix $\hat{\rho}_A$, which we derive now.

We first proceed as if the global density matrix $\hat{\rho}$ is known, from which we know how to calculate the expectation values, see Eq. (6.5). We have

$$\hat{\rho} = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^2 |a_i\rangle\langle a_j| \otimes |b_i\rangle\langle b_j|. \quad (6.10)$$

Now suppose that there is some observable of system A , $\hat{A} = \hat{O}_A \otimes I$. Then, the expectation value, see Eq. (6.5), is

$$\langle\hat{A}\rangle = \text{Tr}(\hat{\rho}\hat{A}) = \text{Tr}(\hat{\rho}\hat{O}_A \otimes I). \quad (6.11)$$

To perform the trace, we introduce the orthonormal basis sets $\{|\psi_k\rangle\} \in \mathcal{H}_A$ and $\{|\phi_l\rangle\} \in \mathcal{H}_B$, such that

$$\langle\hat{A}\rangle = \sum_{k,l} \langle\psi_k| \otimes \langle\phi_l| \left(\hat{\rho}\hat{O}_A \otimes I \right) |\psi_k\rangle \otimes |\phi_l\rangle = \sum_k \langle\psi_k| \left(\underbrace{\sum_l \langle\phi_l|\hat{\rho}|\phi_l\rangle}_{\text{Tr}_B(\hat{\rho})} \right) \hat{O}_A |\psi_k\rangle, \quad (6.12)$$

where $\text{Tr}_B(\hat{\rho})$ is the partial trace of the full density matrix $\hat{\rho}$ over the Hilbert space of B , which still is an operator acting on \mathcal{H}_A . Hence, we may identify the reduced density matrix $\hat{\rho}_A = \text{Tr}_B(\hat{\rho})$, such that

$$\langle \hat{A} \rangle = \text{Tr}_A(\hat{\rho}_A \hat{O}_A). \quad (6.13)$$

Therefore, all we need to calculate an expectation value of an observable of A is its observable \hat{O}_A and the local reduced density matrix $\hat{\rho}_A$. The same, of course, applies to B with $\langle \hat{B} \rangle = \text{Tr}_B(\hat{\rho}_B \hat{O}_B)$.

Problem 6.5: *Locally mixed states.* Consider a two-qubit system initially in the singlet state. Calculate the reduced density matrices for each sub-system. If one of these reduced matrices is treated as the global density matrix, determine whether the quantum state is pure or mixed.

The description of two non-interacting, yet entangled systems A and B , is local if A is unaffected by any interaction system B undergoes, and vice versa. Moreover, the description is said to be *complete*, if the description of A put together with B may reconstruct the properties of the global system [8]. In the present context, $\hat{\rho}_A$ and $\hat{\rho}_B$ are the local descriptions of A and B , respectively. Whatever happens to B , does not affect the expectation value at \hat{A} , which can be seen from Eq. (6.13). However, it is not possible to reconstruct the global density matrix $\hat{\rho}$ from $\hat{\rho}_A$ and $\hat{\rho}_B$, which makes of the reduced density matrices a local but *incomplete* description of the whole.

If instead of using the reduced density matrices as the local descriptions of A and B one uses the global vector $|\psi\rangle$, then the description would be complete because we can reconstruct $\hat{\rho}$. However, this would be a non-local description, since $|\psi\rangle$ is not a description of a sub-system alone. This establishes an apparent quandary. In the Schrödinger picture, we are either stuck with a local but incomplete description or a complete and non-local description.

Perhaps one of the most arcane facts of quantum theory is that the Heisenberg picture of quantum mechanics provides both a local and complete description. And all of this without hidden variables.

6.3.1 Reduced density matrices of qubits in the Pauli basis

The 2×2 reduced density matrices describe qubits. Suppose that a qubit Q is described by the reduced density matrix

$$\hat{\rho}_Q = \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 & 1/2 \\ 1/2 & 1/2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6.14)$$

It is possible to express $\hat{\rho}_Q$ in terms of Pauli matrices. In the case of $\hat{\rho}_Q$, it is easy to guess the result $\hat{\rho}_Q = (\hat{\sigma}_0 + \hat{\sigma}_z)/2$. Guessing the result becomes increasingly harder for larger matrices. Therefore, let us obtain a general expression for the reduced density matrix of a qubit, which can also be generalized to higher dimensions.

Let us denote the reduced density matrix of the qubit by $\hat{\rho}_A$. We may parametrise any 2×2 in terms of the Pauli basis as

$$\hat{\rho}_A(t) = \sum_{i=0}^3 c_i(t) \hat{\sigma}_i, \quad (6.15)$$

where the c_i are coefficients yet to be determined. To find them, we evaluate

$$\hat{\rho}_A \hat{\sigma}_j = \left(\sum_i c_i \hat{\sigma}_i \right) \hat{\sigma}_j = \sum_i c_i (\delta_{ij} \hat{\sigma}_0 + i \epsilon_{ijk} \hat{\sigma}_k) = c_j \hat{\sigma}_0 + i \hat{\sigma}_k \sum_i c_i \epsilon_{ijk}. \quad (6.16)$$

Taking the trace of Eq. (6.16), we find

$$c_i(t) = \frac{1}{2} \text{tr} [\hat{\rho}_A(t) \hat{\sigma}_i] \quad (6.17)$$

where we used the fact that Pauli matrices are traceless, and $\text{tr}(\hat{\rho}_A \hat{\sigma}_0) = 1$. With this, we update Eq. (6.15)

$$\hat{\rho}_A(t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\hat{\sigma}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^3 \text{tr} [\hat{\rho}_A(t) \hat{\sigma}_j] \hat{\sigma}_j \right). \quad (6.18)$$

We will use this result in later chapters to express reduced density matrices in terms of Heisenberg observables. As mentioned before, for the 2×2 case, it is much easier to guess the result directly instead of using Eq. (6.18).

6.4 Projection-valued measure

Consider a qubit Ω_M with associated Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_M that will act as a measurer of another qubit Ω_S with Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_S and computational variable \hat{q}_z . The eigenstates of \hat{q}_z form the basis $\{|1\rangle, |-1\rangle\}$. At a time t , the composite system is subjected to a measurement interaction which ends at $t + 1$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi(t)\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} |M\rangle \otimes (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle) \xrightarrow{\text{measurement}} \\ |\psi(t+1)\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|M_\uparrow\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + |M_\downarrow\rangle \otimes |-1\rangle). \end{aligned} \quad (6.19)$$

Such an evolution can be achieved by a cnot. Here, $|M_\uparrow\rangle$ and $|M_\downarrow\rangle$ are orthonormal eigenstates of a pointer observable \hat{M} of the measurer, whose eigenvalues M_\uparrow and M_\downarrow carry the information of the observed spin eigenvalue. The term *relative states* can be used in different ways: (i) $|M_\uparrow\rangle$ is the relative state of the measurer in relation to the eigenvalue (+1) of the spin observable \hat{q}_z . Analogously, for $|M_\downarrow\rangle$; (ii) $|1\rangle$ is relative to the eigenvalue M_\uparrow of the pointer observable \hat{M} . Likewise for $|-1\rangle$; (iii) $|M_\uparrow\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$ is the relative state of the composite system. Likewise for $|M_\downarrow\rangle \otimes |-1\rangle$. The quantum state $|\psi(t+1)\rangle$ after a measurement with well-defined outcomes (a perfect measurement) is a sum of relative states.

The relative states $|M_\uparrow\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$ and $|M_\downarrow\rangle \otimes |-1\rangle$ are eigenstates of \hat{q}_z , that is: $\hat{q}_z |M_\uparrow\rangle \otimes |1\rangle = |M_\uparrow\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$ and $\hat{q}_z |M_\downarrow\rangle \otimes |-1\rangle = -|M_\downarrow\rangle \otimes |-1\rangle$. We may define projection operators

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}_{+1(-1)}(\hat{q}_z) = \frac{1}{2} (\hat{1} \pm \hat{q}_z), \quad (6.20)$$

such that

$$\frac{\hat{\mathcal{P}}_{+1(-1)}(\hat{q}_z) |\psi(t+1)\rangle}{\langle \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{+1(-1)}(\hat{q}_z) |\psi(t+1)\rangle} = |M_{\uparrow(\downarrow)}\rangle \otimes |+1(-1)\rangle. \quad (6.21)$$

Note that $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_1(\hat{q}_z) + \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1}(\hat{q}_z) = \hat{1}$. A set $\{\hat{\mathcal{P}}_1(\hat{q}_z), \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1}(\hat{q}_z)\}$ with this property is called a *projection-valued measure (PVM)*. In non-unitary quantum theory, Eq. (6.21) is frequently introduced as a measurement postulate. In unitary quantum mechanics, while this is indeed a projection, it does not correspond to a collapse.

Chapter 7

Descriptors

The content of this chapter is largely based on Refs. [8, 9, 41, 75]. In the Heisenberg picture, the observables encode all dynamical information of the system. For this reason, in the context of quantum information, Heisenberg observables are also called *descriptors*. We will show that in this picture (Chap. 8), quantum mechanics is not only local but also complete [9], which is perhaps one of the most arcane facts about quantum theory. This has been known now for more than 20 years [41], and was recently re-explained in Refs. [8, 9, 28, 66, 75, 100].

The concepts of quantum computation and information are usually discussed in the Schrödinger picture, which obscures some of the foundational concepts in unitary quantum mechanics. For this reason, here we introduce quantum computational networks and the effect of logical quantum gates in the Heisenberg picture.

7.1 The Heisenberg equation of motion

In the Heisenberg picture, the expectation values are still calculated using Eq. (6.2), which is why, for the purpose of calculating expectation values, the two pictures are equivalent. The Heisenberg state vector is a fixed initial condition $|0\rangle$, that may coincide with the state vector at time zero in the Schrödinger picture. The reference state $|0\rangle$ does not evolve in time, and its role is to set a reference basis and initial condition. All time dependence is incorporated into the Heisenberg observable $\hat{A}_H(t) = U^\dagger(t)\hat{A}_S U(t)$, where we included the subscripts H and S to distinguish between Heisenberg and Schrödinger observables, respectively. In contrast to the Schrödinger picture, all dynamical quantum information is now encapsulated by a single object: the Heisenberg observable $\hat{A}_H(t)$. Therefore, in the Heisenberg picture, we have a fixed reference state vector $|0\rangle$, and a time-dependent observable $\hat{A}_H(t)$, just like in classical mechanics! In classical mechanics, the state vector establishes the reference frame, and the observables such as position and momenta carry the time dependence. Due to the similarity with classical mechanics, the quantum-classical correspondence is more transparent in the Heisenberg picture. One of the main advantages of the Heisenberg picture is that since $\hat{A}_H(t)$ contains all dynamical quantum information, it is straightforward to track how information flows, which we explicitly work out in Chap. 8.

The discussion of this section is similar to the one of Ref. [25]. Since the state vector is fixed, we must find the equation of motion for the set of observables $\hat{A}_H(t)$ of interest. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}A_H(t) &= \frac{d}{dt} [U^\dagger(t)A_S(t)U(t)] \\ &= \frac{dU^\dagger(t)}{dt}A_S(t)U(t) + U^\dagger(t)\frac{dA_S(t)}{dt}U(t) + U^\dagger(t)A_S(t)\frac{dU(t)}{dt}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.1)$$

Here we included the possibility that even the Schrödinger observables $A_S(t)$ depend on time, which occurs when the Hamiltonian is explicitly time-dependent. We now use $i\hbar\frac{dU(t)}{dt} = \mathcal{H}_S(t)U(t)$ and

$UU^\dagger = 1$ to write

$$\frac{dA_H(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{i\hbar} [A_H(t), \mathcal{H}_H(t)] + U^\dagger(t) \frac{dA_S(t)}{dt} U(t). \quad (7.2)$$

This is the Heisenberg equation of motion for observables. The evolution of the expectation value $\langle A(t) \rangle = \langle 0|A_H(t)|0 \rangle$ is

$$\frac{d\langle A(t) \rangle}{dt} = \frac{1}{i\hbar} \langle [A_H(t), \mathcal{H}_H(t)] \rangle + \left\langle \frac{dA_S(t)}{dt} \right\rangle. \quad (7.3)$$

Examples

Problem 7.1: *Equations of motion for a single particle.* Using $[x_H, p_H] = i\hbar$ and $[x_H, V] = 0$, show that the equations of motion for the position and momentum Heisenberg observables are:

$$\frac{dx_H(t)}{dt} = \frac{p_H(t)}{m}, \quad \frac{dp_H(t)}{dt} = -\frac{\partial V(x_H, t)}{\partial x_H}. \quad (7.4)$$

Any similarity with classical mechanics?

Problem 7.2: *The free particle.* Show that the position observable for the free particle ($V(x_H) = 0$) evolves as

$$x_H(t) = x_0 + \frac{p_0}{m}(t - t_0). \quad (7.5)$$

The result in Eq. (7.5) makes the connection with classical mechanics explicit. But make no mistake, Eq. (7.5) is deceptive. If we repeated the analysis for initially two parallel moving and non-interacting particles with an overlapping initial state vector, we would not obtain a classical-looking result. From the Schrödinger wave picture, we already know that the two wave packets will interfere, complicating significantly the evolution of $x_H(t)$ for each particle. Also, contrary to classical mechanics, the observables such as $x_H(t)$ are not just numbers, but matrices, revealing the richer internal degrees of freedom in quantum mechanics.

Problem 7.3: *The Harmonic oscillator in the Heisenberg picture.* Consider the harmonic oscillator $\mathcal{H} = \frac{p^2}{2m} + \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2 x^2$. Show that the equations of motions are [103]

$$x_H(t) = x_0 \cos \omega t + \frac{p_0}{m\omega} \sin \omega t, \quad p_H(t) = -m\omega x_0 \sin \omega t + p_0 \cos \omega t. \quad (7.6)$$

In Tab. 7.1 we summarise the Schrödinger, Heisenberg and interactive pictures of quantum mechanics. We did not elaborate on the interaction picture here. The interaction picture is very powerful to treat many-body systems, but is of limited value when studying foundational aspects.

7.2 Quantum computational networks

Consider a quantum computational network \mathfrak{N} composed by n interacting qubits Ω_n , illustrated in Fig. 7.1. A physical implementation of such a network might be an Ising model or a quantum circuit. They are certainly not the most general system. They are just a collection of interacting qubits. However, the advantage of studying these systems is that they can simulate any physical system, such that one can then map any desired real physical system to a quantum computational

Representation	Operators	States
Schrödinger	A_S (constant)	$i\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi_S(t)\rangle = \mathcal{H} \psi_S(t)\rangle$
Heisenberg	$i\frac{\partial A_H(t)}{\partial t} = [A_H(t), \mathcal{H}]$	$ \psi_H\rangle$ (constant)
Interaction	$i\frac{\partial A_I(t)}{\partial t} = [A_I(t), \mathcal{H}_0]$	$i\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi_I(t)\rangle = V_I(t) \psi_I(t)\rangle$

Table 7.1: Comparison of the Schrödinger, Heisenberg and interaction (Dirac) pictures of quantum mechanics.

Figure 7.1: A quantum computational network \mathfrak{N} .

network [33]. By being universal quantum computers, such networks can also simulate non-physical games.

Each isolated qubit Ω_a may be described by its 2×2 Heisenberg observable $\hat{q}_a^{(t)}$. If the qubits are spin-half particles, then the Heisenberg observable are the spin projections. From now on, we call $\hat{q}_a^{(t)}$ the descriptor of qubit Ω_a . In 3D, the descriptor has three components

$$\hat{q}_a^{(t)} = (\hat{q}_{ax}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{ay}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{az}^{(t)}). \quad (7.7)$$

At the time $t = 0$, the descriptor coincides with the Schrödinger observables, which for qubits are

$$\hat{q}_{ax}^{(0)} = \hat{\sigma}_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \hat{q}_{ay}^{(0)} = \hat{\sigma}_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \hat{q}_{az}^{(0)} = \hat{\sigma}_z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7.8)$$

A qubit at time $t = 0$ in a network \mathfrak{N} has the dimension of Hilbert space (2^n)

$$\hat{q}_a^{(0)} = \hat{1}^{a-1} \otimes \hat{\sigma} \otimes \hat{1}^{n-a}, \quad \hat{1}^k = \underbrace{\hat{1} \otimes \hat{1} \otimes \hat{1} \otimes \dots \otimes \hat{1}}_{k \text{ times}}. \quad (7.9)$$

The entire network is specified by the collection of all descriptors $\{\hat{q}_a^{(t)}\}$ with an initial condition for the Heisenberg state vector. We may choose an eigenbasis $\{|\hat{q}_{1z}, \hat{q}_{2z}, \dots, \hat{q}_{nz}; t\rangle\}$ for the state vector, and fix the Heisenberg state to $|\Psi\rangle = |1, 1, \dots, 1; 0\rangle$. The choice of the initial condition is rather unimportant because one can always evolve the network to the desired initial state.

In classical mechanics, each component of a bit descriptor has dimension 1. However, in unitary quantum mechanics, each component has dimension 2^n . If one wishes to establish a mapping between classical and quantum mechanics, we may copy the classical system 2^n times, and map it to the quantum system. This is discussed for instance in Ref. [117]. Because of the size of Hilbert space, qubits have vastly more degrees of freedom than bits [9]. In Everettian quantum mechanics, there are 2^n fungible qubits, which through the interactions in the network might stratify. Therefore, there are at most 2^n strata. In the rare case where all *branches* of the original stratum are different, the only option is to recombine. This is a peculiarity of Everettian quantum mechanics, which might produce testable consequences if a Hilbert space is sufficiently small.

7.3 Evolution of descriptors

When studying the evolution of descriptors by modelling the interactions via the action of quantum gates, we can consider time in discrete integer time steps. Consider the action of a particular gate

G , which is to evolve the descriptor of the qubit $\Omega_a \hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t)}$. Then, in the Heisenberg picture, the gate G (which might act on multiple qubits), evolves Ω_a individually as

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t+1)} = U_G^\dagger \left[\hat{\mathbf{q}}_1^{(t)}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_n^{(t)} \right] \hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t)} U_G \left[\hat{\mathbf{q}}_1^{(t)}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_n^{(t)} \right], \quad (7.10)$$

where U_G is the unitary evolution matrix. At $t = 0$, the descriptor components are the Pauli matrices in Eq. (7.8), which together with the identity matrix σ_0 span any 2×2 matrix. This allows us, if convenient, to express U_G in the basis $\{\sigma_0, \sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z\}$, or more generally, we express U_G as a function of the descriptors at time t . Then, $U_G \left[\hat{\mathbf{q}}_1^{(t)}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_n^{(t)} \right]$ is called *the functional representation* of gate G . The optional advantage of using this representation is that one can use the algebra formed by the descriptors to compute the evolution, which avoids computing matrix-matrix multiplications. For a single qubit, multiplying 2×2 matrices is of course no hard task, but matrix multiplication becomes intractable for large networks, yet the algebra remains simple. We will illustrate this with a few examples.

The evolution in the Heisenberg picture in Eq. (7.10) also shows that each qubit evolves independently and locally. This contrasts with the Schrödinger picture where the state vector of the entire network evolves (see Sec. 3.1).

7.3.1 The algebra of descriptors

The descriptors of single qubits are 2×2 unitary matrices that relate to the special unitary group $SU(2)$, which is defined as the set of matrices

$$SU(2) = \left\{ e^{i\gamma} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & -\beta^* \\ \beta & \alpha^* \end{bmatrix}, \quad \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}, \quad \gamma \in \mathbb{R}, \quad |\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1 \right\}. \quad (7.11)$$

The numebms a and b are known as the Cayley-Klein parameters. We can verify that the set $\{\sigma_0, i\sigma_x, i\sigma_y, i\sigma_z\}$ satisfies Eq. (7.11). We already know from the theory of angular momentum that the descriptors must satisfy the $SU(2)$ algebra. A computational network with n qubits than satisfies the $SU(2)^{\otimes n}$ algebra, which is specified by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{ai}^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{aj}^{(t)} &= \delta_{ij} \hat{1} + i \sum_k \epsilon_{ijk} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{ak}^{(t)}, \quad (i, j, k \in \{x, y, z\}); \\ [\hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t)}, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_b^{(t)}] &= 0, \quad (a \neq b), \end{aligned} \quad (7.12)$$

where ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol. The great advantage of the algebra is that it remains valid at all times t .

Problem 7.4: *Cayley-Klein parameters for spin-1/2 rotation matrices.* Obtain the Cayley-Klein parameters for $R_{\hat{n}}(\varphi) = e^{-i\sigma \cdot \hat{n} \frac{\varphi}{2}}$. See Eq. (2.6) and Ref. [103].

7.4 Gates

We now discuss the action of the gates discussed in Chap. 2 in the Heisenberg picture.

7.4.1 Pauli gates

Recall the action of the Pauli gates (X, Y, Z) in the Schrödinger picture discussed in Sec. 2.2.1. The X -gate, also called the not gate N , evolves the Schrödinger state as

$$N|1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = |-1\rangle. \quad (7.13)$$

Similarly, $N|-1\rangle = |1\rangle$, which, just recalling, shows that the not gate toggles the states $|-1\rangle \leftrightarrow |1\rangle$. In the Heisenberg picture, the states remain fixed, and the z-component of the descriptor evolves as

$$\hat{q}_z^{(0+1)} = N^\dagger \hat{q}_z^{(0)} N = N^\dagger \hat{\sigma}_z N = -\hat{\sigma}_z = -\hat{q}_z^{(0)}. \quad (7.14)$$

Therefore, in the Heisenberg picture, the action of the not toggles the z-component of the qubit descriptor. The z-component is not the only one. The effect of the not gate on a generic qubit Ω_a all components is summarised as

$$\text{not} : \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t+1)} = (\hat{q}_{ax}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{ay}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{az}^{(t)}), \quad (7.15)$$

which shows that the not toggles not only the z-component, but also the y-component, whereas the x-components remains unchanged. To show that the not evolves the descriptor of Ω_a as Eq. (7.15) for generic times, we may write the functional representation for $G = \text{not}$, such that

$$U_{\text{not},a} [\hat{\mathbf{q}}_1^{(t)}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{q}}_n^{(t)}] = \hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t)}, \quad (7.16)$$

and use the algebra Eq. (7.11) to perform the evolution in Eq. (7.10) for each descriptor component. The property $\hat{q}_i \hat{q}_j = \delta_{ij} I + i \sum_k \epsilon_{ijk} \hat{q}_k$ may be handy for the manipulations. For the z-component:

$$U_{\text{not}}^\dagger [\hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(0)}] \hat{q}_z^{(0)} U_{\text{not}} [\hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(0)}] = \hat{q}_x^{(0)} \hat{q}_z^{(0)} \hat{q}_x^{(0)} = \hat{q}_x^{(0)} i \hat{q}_y^{(0)} = i^2 \hat{q}_z^{(0)} = -\hat{q}_z^{(0)}, \quad (7.17)$$

where we omitted a for the manipulations. Eqs. (7.14) and (7.17) show two equivalent ways of evolving the descriptor components. For most cases, we henceforth prefer using the functional representation.

Problem 7.5: *Effect of the Pauli gates.* Show that the X, Y and Z gates evolve the descriptor $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t)}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} X : \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t+1)} &= (\hat{q}_{ax}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{ay}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{az}^{(t)}); \\ Y : \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t+1)} &= (-\hat{q}_{ax}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{ay}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{az}^{(t)}); \\ Z : \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t+1)} &= (-\hat{q}_{ax}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{ay}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{az}^{(t)}). \end{aligned} \quad (7.18)$$

In summary, an i -Pauli gate toggles all components except for i .

7.4.2 Rotation operator gates

Now consider the effect of a rotation $R_{az}(\theta) = e^{-i\sigma_z \theta/2} = \sigma_0 \cos(\theta/2) - i\sigma_z \sin(\theta/2)$ over Ω_a , which evolves the descriptor as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q}_a^{(1)} &= R_{az}^\dagger(\theta) \mathbf{q}_a^{(0)} R_{az}(\theta) = [\cos \theta q_{ax}^{(0)} - \sin \theta q_{ay}^{(0)}, \sin \theta q_{ax}^{(0)} + \cos \theta q_{ay}^{(0)}, q_{az}^{(0)}] \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & e^{i\theta}(1-i) \\ e^{-i\theta}(1+i) & -1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.19)$$

The rotation affects the x and y components of the descriptor. However, this information is lost when taking the expectation value $\langle \mathbf{q}_a^{(1)} \rangle$. The quantity θ is an example of *locally inaccessible information*, which is information that cannot be retrieved from a measurement on the system alone [41]. It is not because information might be locally inaccessible, that nature itself is non-local. For instance, in classical mechanics, the values of potentials can only be accessed relative to another system. It is not because of this, that classical mechanics is non-local.

7.4.3 The Hadamard gate

The functional representation of the Hadamard might be readily identified via its definition

$$\hat{H} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{\hat{q}_x^{(0)} + \hat{q}_z^{(0)}}{\sqrt{2}} \equiv U_H[\hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(0)}]; \quad \Rightarrow \quad U_H[\hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(t)}] = \frac{\hat{q}_x^{(t)} + \hat{q}_z^{(t)}}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (7.20)$$

Since the functional representation is valid for all times, it sufficed to express the Hadamard matrix in terms of the initial descriptors, and then generalise to arbitrary times. In the Schrödinger picture, the Hadamard operation creates and undoes superposition states, which of course will not be the case in the Heisenberg picture.

Problem 7.6: *Effect of the Hadamard.* Show that the Hadamard operation evolves the descriptor of Ω_a as

$$H : \hat{\mathbf{q}}_a^{(t+1)} = (\hat{q}_{az}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{ay}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{ax}^{(t)}). \quad (7.21)$$

Note that, unlike the Pauli gates that just toggled descriptor components, the Hadamard exchanged the x and z components, and toggled the y component. This exchange of components is what produces the effects of interference/superpositions in the Schrödinger picture.

7.5 Sharp and blunt observables

What in the Schrödinger picture corresponds to superposition state, originates from the properties of the descriptors relative to the Heisenberg state $|\Psi\rangle$. Consider the single qubit descriptor component $\hat{q}_z = \hat{\sigma}_z$ and the Heisenberg state $|1\rangle$. If the Heisenberg state vector is an eigenstate of the descriptor component, then the descriptor component is said to be *sharp* with respect to the state. In this case, $\hat{q}_z|1\rangle = 1|1\rangle$ and $\langle\hat{q}_z\rangle = \langle 1|\hat{q}_z|1\rangle = 1$. Of course, \hat{q}_z is also sharp with respect to $|-1\rangle$, since $\hat{q}_z|-1\rangle = -1|-1\rangle$. The observable \hat{q}_z is not sharp with respect to $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)$, since this is not an eigenstate of \hat{q}_z . Now consider the descriptor $\hat{q}_x = \hat{\sigma}_x$ and the state $|1\rangle$. We know that $\hat{q}_x|1\rangle = |-1\rangle$. Hence, $|1\rangle$ is not an eigenstate of \hat{q}_x and $\langle\hat{q}_x\rangle = \langle 1|\hat{q}_x|1\rangle = 0$. In this case, we say that \hat{q}_x is *blunt* (non-sharp) with respect to $|1\rangle$ ¹. The descriptor \hat{q}_x would be sharp if the Heisenberg state were $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)$.

In standard textbook language, one defines a dispersion $\sigma^2 = \langle(\delta\hat{A})^2\rangle = \langle\hat{A}^2\rangle - \langle\hat{A}\rangle^2$, for an observable \hat{A} . If $\sigma = 0$, in the Schrödinger picture one says that the system is in a determinate state [62], which would correspond to the sharp observable here. A situation with a dispersion $\sigma \neq 0$ corresponds to a blunt observable. The uncertainty principle that follows from this does not necessarily mean that nature is intrinsically stochastic. It means that the outcomes of blunt observables must be diverse.

7.6 Entanglement

In the Heisenberg picture, two qubits Ω_a and Ω_b are said to be *entangled* at time t , if there exists a pair of descriptor components such that

$$\langle\hat{q}_{ai}^{(t)}\hat{q}_{bj}^{(t)}\rangle \neq \langle\hat{q}_{ai}^{(t)}\rangle\langle\hat{q}_{bj}^{(t)}\rangle. \quad (7.22)$$

We saw in Sec. 2.3 that the simplest two-qubit gate leading to entanglement between two qubits is the cnot gate.

¹I learned the subject from Ref. [75], which does not speak of *blunt* observables. I introduced the terminology here to contrast with *sharp*.

7.6.1 The controlled-NOT gate

To describe the cnot, we consider a control Ω_C and a target qubit Ω_T . Their descriptors are initialised as

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(0)} &= (\hat{\sigma}_x \otimes \hat{\sigma}_0, \hat{\sigma}_y \otimes \hat{\sigma}_0, \hat{\sigma}_z \otimes \hat{\sigma}_0) \equiv (\hat{q}_{Cx}, \hat{q}_{Cy}, \hat{q}_{Cz}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_T^{(0)} &= (\hat{\sigma}_0 \otimes \sigma_x, \hat{\sigma}_0 \otimes \sigma_y, \hat{\sigma}_0 \otimes \sigma_z) \equiv (\hat{q}_{Tx}, \hat{q}_{Ty}, \hat{q}_{Tz}).\end{aligned}\quad (7.23)$$

Note that each component of the control and target qubit is a 4×4 matrix. Using the same strategy we used for the Hadamard in Eq. (7.20), we write the cnot matrix as

$$\begin{aligned}\text{cnot} &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\sigma_0 + \sigma_z}{2} \otimes \sigma_0 + \frac{\sigma_0 - \sigma_z}{2} \otimes \sigma_x \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[I + q_{Cz}^{(0)} + q_{Tx}^{(0)} - q_{Cz}^{(0)} q_{Tx}^{(0)} \right] \equiv U_{\text{cnot}}[\mathbf{q}_C^{(0)}, \mathbf{q}_T^{(0)}].\end{aligned}\quad (7.24)$$

With this, we write the functional representation of the cnot as

$$U_{\text{cnot}}[\mathbf{q}_C^{(t)}, \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}] = \frac{1}{2} \left[I + q_{Cz}^{(t)} + q_{Tx}^{(t)} - q_{Cz}^{(t)} q_{Tx}^{(t)} \right] = \frac{1}{2} \left(I + q_{Cz}^{(t)} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(I - q_{Cz}^{(t)} \right) q_{Tx}^{(t)}, \quad (7.25)$$

where $I = \sigma_0 \otimes \sigma_0$. This allows us to work out the evolution of the three descriptor components of the Ω_C and the target qubit Ω_T , in total six descriptors. That is some work to do, but unlike in the Schrödinger picture, we only do it once! In analogy to the Schrödinger picture (see Eq. (6.21)) we also may identify the projection operators in the Heisenberg picture as

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}_{1(-1)} \left(\hat{q}_{Cz}^{(t)} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(I \pm \hat{q}_{Cz}^{(t)} \right). \quad (7.26)$$

This allows us to express the functional representation of the cnot in terms of the projection operators as

$$U_{\text{cnot}}[\mathbf{q}_C^{(t)}, \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}] = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_1 \left(q_{Cz}^{(t)} \right) + U_{\text{not},T}[\mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}] \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1} \left(q_{Cz}^{(t)} \right). \quad (7.27)$$

Eq. (7.27) has an intuitive interpretation. The cnot has no effect on the target qubit if the projection of the control qubit has value +1. The cnot performs a not operation on the target qubit if the control qubit has projection -1. Compare this with Prob. 2.4. Moreover, Eq. (7.27) explicitly shows how the cnot splits the target into two simultaneously existing instances. One experiences the not operation, and the other does not. This reveals, how in the Heisenberg picture, measurements change the targets.

Problem 7.7: *Effect of controlled- U operations on the control and target qubits.* A generic controlled- U operation may be written as

$$U_{\text{cU}}[\mathbf{q}_C^{(t)}, \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}] = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_1 \left(q_{Cz}^{(t)} \right) + U_T[\mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}] \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1} \left(q_{Cz}^{(t)} \right), \quad (7.28)$$

where $U_T[\mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}]$ is the operation of the generic unitary gate over the target. Assume that $U_T = U_T^\dagger$, and show that the effect on the control and target qubit descriptors are

$$\begin{aligned}\text{cU} : \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(t+1)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{Cx}^{(t)} U_T, \hat{q}_{Cy}^{(t)} U_T, \hat{q}_{Cz}^{(t)} \right); \\ \hat{q}_{T,i}^{(t+1)} &= \hat{q}_{T,i}^{(t)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_1 + U_T^\dagger \hat{q}_{T,i}^{(t)} U_T \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1}.\end{aligned}\quad (7.29)$$

Eq. (7.29) serves as preparatory work for both the controlled-not and the controlled-Hadamard operation.

Problem 7.8: *Effect of the cnot on the control and target qubits.* Use the functional representation for the cnot to show that the descriptors evolve as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{cnot} : \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(t+1)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{C_x}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{T_x}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{C_y}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{T_x}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} \right); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_T^{(t+1)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{T_x}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{T_y}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (7.30)$$

The underlined terms indicate the copied information.

Problem 7.9: *Basis change.* Using Eqs. (7.21) and (7.30), show that

which shows that the role of the control and target qubits may be interchanged upon a basis change.

7.6.2 Entanglement in the Heisenberg picture

After the action of the cnot, are the two qubits entangled? It depends. To analyse this, we look at the z-components of the control and target qubits and evaluate

$$\left\langle \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t+1)} \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t+1)} \right\rangle \stackrel{?}{=} \left\langle \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t+1)} \right\rangle \left\langle \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t+1)} \right\rangle. \quad (7.31)$$

If the equality does not hold, then the qubits are entangled. Let us evaluate each term. The terms on the right side of Eq. (7.31):

$$\left\langle \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t+1)} \right\rangle = \left\langle \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} \right\rangle = \langle 1, 1 | \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} | 1, 1 \rangle = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} \text{ is sharp} \\ 0, & \text{if } \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} \text{ is blunt} \end{cases}. \quad (7.32)$$

And the target:

$$\left\langle \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t+1)} \right\rangle = \langle 1, 1 | \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t)} | 1, 1 \rangle = \langle 1 | \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} | 1 \rangle \langle 1 | \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t)} | 1 \rangle = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if both are sharp} \\ 0, & \text{if at least one is blunt} \end{cases}. \quad (7.33)$$

The term on the left side of Eq. (7.31) is

$$\left\langle \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t+1)} \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t+1)} \right\rangle = \left\langle \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)} \right\rangle = \left\langle \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t)} \right\rangle = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t)} \text{ is sharp} \\ 0, & \text{if } \hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t)} \text{ is blunt} \end{cases}. \quad (7.34)$$

Let us assume that $\hat{q}_{T_z}^{(t)}$ is sharp before the action cnot. In this case, Eq. (7.33) informs us that the target remains sharp only if the control $\hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)}$ was also sharp before the interaction. In this case, the equality in Eq. (7.31), which shows that the cnot did not entangle the control and target.

However, if the control $\hat{q}_{C_z}^{(t)}$ is blunt, the right side of Eq. (7.31) gives zero, whereas Eq. (7.34) yields one, attesting the entanglement. This confirms what we already knew from the Schrödinger picture. As we shall see in the next chapter, the Heisenberg picture allows us to follow the location of quantum information explicitly.

Problem 7.10: *Correlations between the y descriptor components.* Repeat the discussion of Sec. 7.6.2 for

$$\langle \hat{q}_{Cy}^{(t+1)} \hat{q}_{Ty}^{(t+1)} \rangle \stackrel{?}{=} \langle \hat{q}_{Cy}^{(t+1)} \rangle \langle \hat{q}_{Ty}^{(t+1)} \rangle. \quad (7.35)$$

Problem 7.11: *Recovering the reduced density matrix for a qubit with descriptors.* Start from Eq. (6.18) and show that

$$\hat{\rho}_A(t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\hat{\sigma}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^3 \langle \hat{q}_{A,j}^{(t)} \rangle \sigma_j \right), \quad (7.36)$$

where $\hat{q}_{A,j}^{(t)}$ are the descriptor components of qubit A. Also see Ref. [10]. Also verify that after the action of any Bell gate in Fig. 2.2, $\langle \hat{q}_A^{(t)} \rangle = 0$.

Chapter 8

Locality, memory and completeness

In this chapter we explore some of the most interesting statements the Everettian programs makes about reality. In contrast to collapse quantum theory and Bohmian mechanics, Everettian mechanics is Einstein-local at the expense of multiplicity. It is precisely for paying for multiplicity that quantum mechanics is not local in the Bell sense, which is more strict, and prohibits multiplicity. We state what is meant by Einstein locality in Sec. 8.1. Then, in Sec. 8.2, we use a paradigmatic three qubit network typically used to motivate non-local phenomena to show that within the Everettian interpretation, all of physics is local. Although here we only deal with qubit toy models, the conclusions drawn here apply to any quantum system, including fermions [116]. The relative state construction in the Schrödinger picture was introduced in previous chapters. In Sec. 8.3, we show how the relative state construction is achieved in the Heisenberg picture. Relative descriptors show that foliations are defined from entangled states, but not all entangled states foliate sharply, which is very hard to see in the Schrödinger picture. Because quantum foliations may be sharp or blurry, the concept of a continuous memory of a quantum agent must be revisited. For this reason, in Sec. 8.4 we discuss how volatile quantum memory is. With a local quantum theory, we then ask, is it also complete? In Sec. 8.5 we answer in the affirmative, which perhaps solves one of the longest standing historical conundrums surrounding quantum theory. In the literature, there are many paradigmatic experiments that purportedly show that quantum theory is non-local. The contents of this chapter turn these claims innocuous. One example is the CHSH inequality. Therefore, in Sec. 8.6, we discuss the exercise of expressing the CHSH inequality in terms of descriptors, showing that in all these examples, quantum theory is transparent, local and complete.

8.1 Locality in physics

What is meant by a local theory in physics in general? According to Raymond-Robichaud [100], local realism is summarised by the following principles:

- (i) *There is a real-world;*
- (ii) *It can be decomposed into various parts, called systems;*
- (iii) *A system may be decomposed into subsystems;*
- (iv) *Every system is a subsystem of the global system consisting of the entire world;*
- (v) *At any given time, each system is in some state;*
- (vi) *The state of a system determines, and is determined by, the state of its subsystems;*
- (vii) *What is observable in a system is determined by the state of the system;*
- (viii) *The state of the world evolves according to some law;*

Figure 8.1: Locality of a quantum circuit of a three-qubit network.

- (ix) *The evolution of the state of a system can only be influenced by the state of systems in its local neighbourhood.*

We refrain from assessing whether this is a good definition of local realism or not, but we do use it to clarify what here is meant by a *local theory*. Applied to relativity, this definition implies that an action performed at some point cannot affect another point faster than the speed of light. Yet when applied to quantum mechanics, the above definition *does not* imply that local theories must be described by hidden variables.

While this definition of locality may appear conservative, it should be noted that it is not equivalent to the assumptions of *Bell-locality*. In Bell's seminal *The Theory of Local Beables* [12], he demonstrates that quantum mechanics cannot be described as locally causal when implicitly assuming that measurements yield single outcomes. This results in a more stringent interpretation of local causality, in which quantum mechanics is indeed not locally causal according to Bell's criteria.

However, if one is open to relaxing the assumption of single outcomes and embrace multiplicity, then according to Raymond-Robichaud's definition, quantum mechanics can be considered local and compatible with the principles of relativity. Consequently, it is possible to discuss local, deterministic, and causal theories that do not adhere to Bell-locality, such as the ones listed in categories (A) and (B) of Tab. 3.3. The categorisation refers to a broader concept of local causality such as Raymond-Robichaud's and not to Bell-locality. Then, in the context of a local theory, one can explore how information encoded in physical states flows within causally connected local regions.

8.2 Is quantum mechanics a local theory?

A local flow of information refers to the process of carrying information from one location to another through local interactions, as stated in Ref. [41]. For a deeper discussion on the definition of information and its relation with physical laws, we refer the reader to Ref. [42].

This chapter is motivated by the following problem: *suppose that first two systems A and B interact with each other and become entangled, and then are sent to space-like separated regions. After this, system B gets entangled with a third system C. Although A and C never interacted with each other, they are now entangled. Is this a non-local effect? We show that within superdeterminism, Bohmian mechanics and Everettian mechanics, the answer is no.*

The locality of quantum mechanics is best appreciated in the Heisenberg picture. This is because whereas in the Schrödinger picture quantum information is split between the state vector and the observable, in the Heisenberg picture all dynamical information is carried by a single object: the Heisenberg observable. In this picture, quantum mechanics is not only local but also complete [9]. This has been known now for more than 20 years [41], and was recently re-explained in Refs. [8, 9, 66, 75, 100]. Since our objective is to emphasise the locality of quantum mechanics, we discuss

the physics of Fig. 4.1 in the Heisenberg picture by means of a quantum circuit illustrated in Fig. 8.1.

The systems A , B and C may be regarded as three qubits with Heisenberg observables (or descriptors)

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t)} = \left(\hat{q}_{ix}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{iy}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{iz}^{(t)} \right), \quad (8.1)$$

with $i = \{A, B, C\}$. The index i implicitly contains the positions of the three qubits (x_1, x_2, x_3) . The three-qubit network is initialised with the descriptors

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(0)} &= (\hat{\sigma}_x \otimes \hat{1} \otimes \hat{1}, \hat{\sigma}_y \otimes \hat{1} \otimes \hat{1}, \hat{\sigma}_z \otimes \hat{1} \otimes \hat{1}) \equiv (\hat{q}_{Ax}, \hat{q}_{Ay}, \hat{q}_{Az}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(0)} &= (\hat{1} \otimes \hat{\sigma}_x \otimes \hat{1}, \hat{1} \otimes \hat{\sigma}_y \otimes \hat{1}, \hat{1} \otimes \hat{\sigma}_z \otimes \hat{1}) \equiv (\hat{q}_{Bx}, \hat{q}_{By}, \hat{q}_{Bz}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(0)} &= (\hat{1} \otimes \hat{1} \otimes \hat{\sigma}_x, \hat{1} \otimes \hat{1} \otimes \hat{\sigma}_y, \hat{1} \otimes \hat{1} \otimes \hat{\sigma}_z) \equiv (\hat{q}_{Cx}, \hat{q}_{Cy}, \hat{q}_{Cz}); \end{aligned} \quad (8.2)$$

where $(\hat{\sigma}_x, \hat{\sigma}_y, \hat{\sigma}_z)$ are the Pauli matrices, and $\hat{1}$ is the 2×2 identity matrix; and the fixed Heisenberg state is $|\psi\rangle = -|1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$. This state is chosen to reproduce the entangled state Eq. (4.22) after the evolution of the descriptors, which, in this section's notation is $|\Psi^{(3)}\rangle = (|1\rangle| -1\rangle - | -1\rangle|1\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$.

Problem 8.1: *Reduced density matrices.* Consider the system of qubits A and B up to $t = 3$. Show that the reduced density matrices at time $t = 3$ are

$$\hat{\rho}_A^{(3)} = \frac{1}{2} [|1\rangle\langle 1| + | -1\rangle\langle -1|], \quad \hat{\rho}_B^{(3)} = \frac{1}{2} [| -1\rangle\langle -1| + |1\rangle\langle 1|]. \quad (8.3)$$

Explain why it is not possible to reconstruct $\hat{\rho}^{(3)}$ from $\hat{\rho}_A^{(3)}$ and $\hat{\rho}_B^{(3)}$.

In Fig. 8.1 we show a quantum circuit of a three-qubit network that is equivalent to Fig. 4.1. The dashed box is a type of Bell-gate that entangles the qubits A and B into a singlet configuration, and it serves as a simple model for local interactions. We now evolve the locally specified descriptors according to the protocol in Fig. 8.1. Below we summarise the effect of the gates of Fig. 8.1 on the descriptors. The single qubit gates, which can be consulted in Eq. (7.18), evolve the descriptors as

$$\begin{aligned} X: \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t+1)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{ix}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{iy}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{iz}^{(t)} \right); \\ Z: \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t+1)} &= \left(-\hat{q}_{ix}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{iy}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{iz}^{(t)} \right); \\ H: \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{(t+1)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{iz}^{(t)}, -\hat{q}_{iy}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{ix}^{(t)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (8.4)$$

The controlled not gate cnot is a simultaneous operation on two neighbouring qubits. One is the control qubit C and the other the target qubit T . Recall that the effect of the cnot on the control and target qubits is given by Eq. (7.30). From $t = 0$ to $t = 1$, qubit A is subjected to a Hadamard gate H and qubit B to a Pauli- X gate X . Using the properties of Eq. (8.4), we can write the descriptors at $t = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(1)} &= (\hat{q}_{Az}, -\hat{q}_{Ay}, \hat{q}_{Ax}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(1)} &= (\hat{q}_{Bx}, -\hat{q}_{By}, -\hat{q}_{Bz}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(1)} &= (\hat{q}_{Cx}, \hat{q}_{Cy}, \hat{q}_{Cz}). \end{aligned} \quad (8.5)$$

Because the descriptors are specified locally, one can write the descriptors in Eq. (8.5) on the circuit legs; see Fig. 8.1. From $t = 1$ to $t = 2$, Pauli- Z gates operate on qubits A and B , such that at

$t = 2$, the descriptors evolve to

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(2)} &= (-\hat{q}_{Az}, \hat{q}_{Ay}, \hat{q}_{Ax}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(2)} &= (-\hat{q}_{Bx}, \hat{q}_{By}, -\hat{q}_{Bz}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(2)} &= (\hat{q}_{Cx}, \hat{q}_{Cy}, \hat{q}_{Cz}).\end{aligned}\tag{8.6}$$

In the Heisenberg picture, two qubits A and B are entangled at time t if there is a pair of descriptors such that $\langle \psi | \hat{q}_{A\mu}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{B\nu}^{(t)} | \psi \rangle \neq \langle \psi | \hat{q}_{A\mu}^{(t)} | \psi \rangle \langle \psi | \hat{q}_{B\nu}^{(t)} | \psi \rangle$ [66, 75]. With this, one can check that there is no entanglement at $t = 2$. Next, a local interaction between qubits A and B is modelled by a cnot operation on A as the control, and B as the target. This evolves the qubit network to:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(3)} &= (\hat{q}_{Az} \hat{q}_{Bx}, -\hat{q}_{Ay} \hat{q}_{Bx}, \hat{q}_{Ax}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(3)} &= (-\hat{q}_{Bx}, \hat{q}_{By} \hat{q}_{Ax}, -\hat{q}_{Bz} \hat{q}_{Ax}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(3)} &= (\hat{q}_{Cx}, \hat{q}_{Cy}, \hat{q}_{Cz}).\end{aligned}\tag{8.7}$$

This corresponds to Fig. 4.1(b). Qubits A and B are now entangled, but unlike in the Schrödinger representation (see Eq. (4.22)), the descriptors are still locally specified because the positions (x_1, x_2, x_3) are implicitly contained in (A, B, C) . Finally, from $t = 3$ to $t = 4$, qubits B and C interact locally via a cnot that evolves the descriptors to

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(4)} &= (\hat{q}_{Az} \hat{q}_{Bx}, -\hat{q}_{Ay} \hat{q}_{Bx}, \hat{q}_{Ax}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(4)} &= (-\hat{q}_{Bx} \hat{q}_{Cx}, \hat{q}_{By} \hat{q}_{Ax} \hat{q}_{Cx}, -\hat{q}_{Bz} \hat{q}_{Ax}); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(4)} &= (\hat{q}_{Cx}, -\hat{q}_{Cy} \hat{q}_{Bz} \hat{q}_{Ax}, -\hat{q}_{Cz} \hat{q}_{Bz} \hat{q}_{Ax}).\end{aligned}\tag{8.8}$$

This corresponds to the situation in Fig. 4.1(c), where the three qubits are now entangled. Although qubit C never interacted with A , they are now entangled, but not due to a non-local effect. To understand this we must analyse the local information flow of the circuit. When A interacted locally with B , $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(3)}$ acquired a copy of A in its y and z components. After this, A was sent away so as to never interact again with B or C . Next, B moved to the vicinity of C transporting along with it information about A . Therefore, when C interacted locally with B , not only did $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(4)}$ acquire a copy of B in its y and z components, but it also acquired a copy of A ! Information was transported locally and causally from qubit A to qubit C by qubit B .

Problem 8.2: *Not all information is copied.* In Prob. 3.4, we constructed Tab. 3.2 in the Schrödinger picture. The table illustrates that, despite the entanglement of qubits A and B , the labs cannot always verify this entanglement when L_A uses the $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ reference frame and L_B uses $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$. Using the descriptors for qubits A and B outlined in Eq. (8.7), reconstruct Tab. 3.2. Explain the reason behind the absence of correlations despite entanglement. Additionally, provide the list of reference frame combinations capable of verifying the entanglement correlations.

8.3 Relative descriptors

Relative states are easy to identify in the Schrödinger picture. For instance, the global state vector corresponding to the descriptors in Eq. (8.7) is $|\Psi^{(3)}\rangle = (|1\rangle| - 1\rangle - | - 1\rangle|1\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$, where the two terms in the state vector are precisely the relative states. How do we construct the corresponding relative descriptors in the Heisenberg picture? Here we follow the construction of relative descriptors that was developed in Ref. [75].

8.3.1 Construction

For this section's purpose, assume that the target has not yet interacted with the control at time t , that is, $\mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}$ has no copies of $\mathbf{q}_C^{(t)}$, and vice-versa. In the Schrödinger picture, $|\Psi^{(3)}\rangle$ was obtained after the action of the cnot. Similarly, in the Heisenberg picture, the cnot evolves the target descriptor $\mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}$ according to Eq. (7.27):

$$\mathbf{q}_T^{(t+1)} = U_{\text{cnot}}^\dagger \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)} U_{\text{cnot}} = \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Cz}^{(t)}] + \left(U_{\text{not},T}^\dagger \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)} U_{\text{not},T} \right) \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Cz}^{(t)}]. \quad (8.9)$$

We denote the original instance of the target qubit described by $\mathbf{q}_T^{(t)}$ by Ω_T . Eq. (8.9) shows how the cnot split Ω_T into two simultaneous existing instances

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\Omega_{T,1}} &= \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Cz}^{(t)}]; \\ I_{\Omega_{T,-1}} &= \left(U_{\text{not},T}^\dagger \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)} U_{\text{not},T} \right) \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Cz}^{(t)}], \end{aligned} \quad (8.10)$$

where $\Omega_{T,1}$ recorded the $+1$ eigenvalue of the $q_{Cz}^{(t)}$ observable, while $\Omega_{T,-1}$ recorded the -1 eigenvalue of the $q_{Cz}^{(t)}$ observable while also undergoing a not operation. $\Omega_{T,1}$ and $\Omega_{T,-1}$ are fully fledged qubits that are in different *histories* of Ω_T (see Sec. 8.3.3). We know from experiment that measurers record a single value at a time, which is why one associates measurement outcomes with relative histories.

Motivated by Eq. (8.9) one then defines the relative descriptors corresponding to instances $\Omega_{T,1}$ and $\Omega_{T,-1}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{T,1} : \quad \mathbf{q}_{T,1}^{(t+1)} &:= \mathbf{q}_T^{(t+1)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Cz}^{(t+1)}]; \\ \Omega_{T,-1} : \quad \mathbf{q}_{T,-1}^{(t+1)} &:= \mathbf{q}_T^{(t+1)} \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Cz}^{(t+1)}], \end{aligned} \quad (8.11)$$

where $t+1$ is the time *after* the cnot. Using Eq. (8.9), we may readily verify that these definitions yield Eq. (8.10). The projections may be contrasted with the Schrödinger picture in Eq. (6.21).

Consider the descriptors in the particular example of Eq. (8.7), after which qubits Ω_A and Ω_B entangle into a singlet state. We wish to find the relative descriptor of qubit B that observed the $+1$ eigenvalue of the $q_{Az}^{(2)}$ observable. Then, we have that

$$\Omega_{B,1} : \mathbf{q}_{B,1}^{(3)} := \mathbf{q}_B^{(3)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(3)}] = (-q_{Bx}, q_{By} q_{Ax}, -q_{Bz} q_{Ax}) \frac{1}{2} (I + q_{Ax}) = (-q_{Bx}, q_{By}, -q_{Bz}) \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(3)}]. \quad (8.12)$$

Similarly, for the other foliation, we have

$$\Omega_{B,-1} : \mathbf{q}_{B,-1}^{(3)} := \mathbf{q}_B^{(3)} \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Az}^{(3)}] = (q_{Bx}, -q_{By}, q_{Bz}) \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Az}^{(3)}]. \quad (8.13)$$

The projected relative descriptors for $\Omega_{B,1}$ and $\Omega_{B,-1}$, conditioned by their relative eigenvalue observation, lost their copies of Ω_A .

8.3.2 Conditional expectation values

The expectation value of the z component of $\Omega_{B,1}$ with respect to the global Heisenberg state is

$$\langle \mathbf{q}_{B,1,z}^{(3)} \rangle = \langle q_{Bz} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(3)}] \rangle = \langle q_{Bz} \rangle \langle \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(3)}] \rangle = \langle \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(3)}] \rangle = \frac{1}{2} (1 + \langle q_{Ax} \rangle) = \frac{1}{2}. \quad (8.14)$$

Moreover, note that the expectation value of the full descriptor is blunt $\langle \mathbf{q}_{B,z}^{(3)} \rangle = 0$. Because $\langle \mathbf{q}_{B,1,z}^{(3)} \rangle \neq \langle \mathbf{q}_{B,z}^{(3)} \rangle$, the expectation value of the descriptors of the full network differ from those of

the relative descriptors. An observable may be blunt in the full network, but sharp in the relative states (foliations). Motivated by this, one defines the conditional expectation value $\langle \dots \rangle_{B,1}$ for an arbitrary descriptor component $q_{Bi}^{(t)}$ of Ω_B , given that the z component of Ω_A was measured to be +1 as

$$\langle q_{Bi}^{(t)} \rangle_{B,1} := \frac{\langle q_{Bi}^{(t)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(t)}] \rangle}{\langle \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(t)}] \rangle} = \frac{\langle q_{Bi,1}^{(t)} \rangle}{\langle \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(t)}] \rangle}, \quad (8.15)$$

such that $\langle q_{Bz}^{(3)} \rangle_{B,1} = 1$ is sharp relative to $q_{Az}^{(3)}$. The denominator in Eq. (8.15) takes into account that $q_{Az}^{(t)}$ is blunt with respect to the global network.

As long as no further (un)entangling interactions occur, the expectation values of $\Omega_{B,1}$ are the same as if the Heisenberg state $|\mathbf{0}\rangle$ reduced to

$$|\mathbf{0}\rangle \longrightarrow |\mathbf{0}_{B,1}\rangle = \frac{\mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(t)}]|\mathbf{0}\rangle}{|\mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}^{(t)}]|\mathbf{0}\rangle|}, \quad (8.16)$$

where $|\mathbf{0}_{B,1}\rangle$ is the relative Heisenberg state with respect to the result +1 of $q_{Az}^{(t)}$. It may be instructive to compare this with Eq. (6.21).

8.3.3 The algebra of relative descriptors

Note that $q_{B,1,i}^2 = \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}]$, where we omitted the time label for clarity. For this reason, they do not satisfy the algebra of the descriptors introduced in Eq. (7.12). However, they do satisfy

$$q_{B,1,i}^{(t)} q_{B,1,j}^{(t)} = \delta_{ij} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}] + i \sum_k \epsilon_{ijk} q_{B,1,k}, \quad (i, j, k \in \{x, y, z\}), \quad (8.17)$$

where the only difference with respect to the algebra of descriptors is $\mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}]$ instead of $\hat{1}$. Therefore, we may define $\hat{1}_{B,1} = \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Az}]$, such that for each set of relative descriptors, there is a projected algebra of qubits, with the only difference that the matrix representation for relative descriptors has a smaller dimension than that of the full descriptors.

8.3.4 The construction for the control

From the point of view of the control qubit, an analogous construction to Eq. (8.11) holds:

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{C,1} : \quad \mathbf{q}_{C,1}^{(t+1)} &:= \mathbf{q}_C^{(t+1)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Tz}^{(t+1)}]; \\ \Omega_{C,-1} : \quad \mathbf{q}_{C,-1}^{(t+1)} &:= \mathbf{q}_C^{(t+1)} \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Tz}^{(t+1)}]. \end{aligned} \quad (8.18)$$

Here, $\Omega_{C,1}$ saw the +1 eigenvalue of the $q_{Tz}^{(t+1)}$ observable, and $\Omega_{C,-1}$ observed -1 . Applying this to $\mathbf{q}_{A,1}^{(3)}$ (analogously for $\mathbf{q}_{A,-1}^{(3)}$) in Eq. (8.7), we obtain

$$\mathbf{q}_{A,1}^{(3)} = \mathbf{q}_A^{(3)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Bz}^{(3)}] = (q_{Az} q_{Bx}, -q_{Ay} q_{Bx}, q_{Ax}) \frac{1}{2} (I - q_{Bz} q_{Ax}). \quad (8.19)$$

Ω_A is also foliated, because it contains a copy of Ω_B , and the product of the z component of Ω_A with z observable of Ω_B is sharp. We may then label one foliation with $\Omega_{A,1}/\Omega_{B,-1}$ and the other with $\Omega_{A,-1}/\Omega_{B,1}$, which reflect the singlet nature of the particular case. Also, the conditional expectation

values for Ω_A are well defined because $\langle \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Bz}^{(3)}] \rangle \neq 0$. Furthermore, the relative descriptors for the control also obey the appropriate projected Pauli algebra.

Defining the foliations $\Omega_{A,1}/\Omega_{B,-1}$ and the other with $\Omega_{A,-1}/\Omega_{B,1}$ was only possible because Ω_A and Ω_B are entangled. The foliating process is spatially local, because all the systems that were not involved in the interaction remain unchanged. By locality, here we use the definition by Einstein [105], which was rephrased in Sec. 8.1. However, foliations are not Bell-local, because Bell-locality implicitly assumes single measurement outcomes [12].

Problem 8.3: Conditions to define sharp foliations. Based on the discussion of Sec. 8.3, there are two conditions for interacting systems to sharply foliate into the relative descriptors with corresponding conditional expectation values at time t :

$$\begin{aligned}
\Omega_{T,1}: \quad \mathbf{q}_{T,1}^{(t)} &:= \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Cz}^{(t)}], & \langle \mathbf{q}_{Ti}^{(t)} \rangle_{T,1} &= \frac{\langle q_{Ti,1}^{(t)} \rangle}{\langle \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Cz}^{(t)}] \rangle}; \\
\Omega_{T,-1}: \quad \mathbf{q}_{T,-1}^{(t)} &= \mathbf{q}_T^{(t)} \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Cz}^{(t)}], & \langle \mathbf{q}_{Ti}^{(t)} \rangle_{T,-1} &= \frac{\langle q_{Ti,-1}^{(t)} \rangle}{\langle \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Cz}^{(t)}] \rangle}; \\
\Omega_{C,1}: \quad \mathbf{q}_{C,1}^{(t)} &= \mathbf{q}_C^{(t)} \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Tz}^{(t)}], & \langle \mathbf{q}_{Ci}^{(t)} \rangle_{C,1} &= \frac{\langle q_{Ci,1}^{(t)} \rangle}{\langle \mathcal{P}_1[q_{Tz}^{(t)}] \rangle}; \\
\Omega_{C,-1}: \quad \mathbf{q}_{C,-1}^{(t)} &= \mathbf{q}_C^{(t)} \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Tz}^{(t)}], & \langle \mathbf{q}_{Ci}^{(t)} \rangle_{C,-1} &= \frac{\langle q_{Ci,-1}^{(t)} \rangle}{\langle \mathcal{P}_{-1}[q_{Tz}^{(t)}] \rangle}. \tag{8.20}
\end{aligned}$$

The conditions are:

1. A non-zero expectation value of the projections $\langle \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1}[q_{Tz}^{(t)}] \rangle \neq 0$ and $\langle \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1}[q_{Cz}^{(t)}] \rangle \neq 0$;
2. a sharp product of the z components $\langle q_{Cz}^{(t)} q_{Tz}^{(t)} \rangle = 1$.

Explain why these two conditions must be satisfied.

8.4 Memory

Descriptors for a quantum computational network can teach us how the memory of a system works in unitary quantum mechanics. We may ask how much do two descriptors have in common? For this, we may utilize the Frobenius inner product between two matrices A and B , which is defined as

$$\langle A, B \rangle_F = \sum_{i,j} A_{ij}^* B_{ij} = \text{Tr}[A^\dagger B]. \tag{8.21}$$

The Frobenius product generalises the inner product for vectors to matrices, and serves as a measure of the overlap between matrices. Consider an arbitrary descriptor component $q_i^{(t)}$. At a later time $t' > t$, the descriptor evolves to $q_i^{(t')}$. If $\langle q_i^{(t)}, q_i^{(t')} \rangle_F = 0$, we may say that the qubit has no memory (nothing in common) of its past. Otherwise, if $\langle q_i^{(t)}, q_i^{(t')} \rangle_F \neq 0$, the qubit has a memory quantified by the product value. The concept may be extended to any pair of qubits $\langle q_{Ai}^{(t)}, q_{Bj}^{(t')} \rangle_F$, where the pair is not necessarily the same qubit at a later time.

For a concrete example, let us work out how the quantum memory works for the protocol illustrated in Fig. 8.1. All the descriptors for qubits A , B and C are known for all times, and can be consulted in Sec. 8.2. First, we may check that

$$\langle q_{Q_i}^{(t)}, q_{Q'_j}^{(t')} \rangle = 0, \quad Q \neq Q', \quad (8.22)$$

which means that qubits on different lines have nothing in common. In other words, different qubits have nothing in common, which is of course an oxymoron serving as a sanity check.

What about the evolution of a single qubit? Intuitively, we would expect a qubit having at least partial memory of itself after a single time step. Let us check, using qubit B as example. The descriptors of B at different times are:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{q}_B^{(0)} &= (\hat{q}_{Bx}, \hat{q}_{By}, \hat{q}_{Bz}); \\ \hat{q}_B^{(1)} &= (\hat{q}_{Bx}, -\hat{q}_{By}, -\hat{q}_{Bz}); \quad \left[\hat{q}_{Bx}^{(0)}, \hat{q}_{By}^{(0)}, \hat{q}_{Bz}^{(0)} \right] \\ \hat{q}_B^{(2)} &= (-\hat{q}_{Bx}, \hat{q}_{By}, -\hat{q}_{Bz}); \quad \left[\hat{q}_{Bx}^{(1)}, \hat{q}_{By}^{(1)}, \hat{q}_{Bz}^{(1)} \right] \\ \hat{q}_B^{(3)} &= (-\hat{q}_{Bx}, \hat{q}_{By} \hat{q}_{Ax}, -\hat{q}_{Bz} \hat{q}_{Ax}); \quad \left[\hat{q}_{Bx}^{(2)}, -, - \right] \\ \hat{q}_B^{(4)} &= (-\hat{q}_{Bx} \hat{q}_{Cx}, \hat{q}_{By} \hat{q}_{Ax} \hat{q}_{Cx}, -\hat{q}_{Bz} \hat{q}_{Ax}); \quad \left[-, -, \hat{q}_{Bz}^{(3)} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (8.23)$$

The square brackets indicate what components the qubit remembers from the previous time-step. For this example, we see that the qubit remembers at least something from its immediate past. However, note that

$$\langle \hat{q}_B^{(0)}, \hat{q}_B^{(4)} \rangle_F = 0, \quad (8.24)$$

which means that given sufficient time, the qubit will forget about its more distant past. Yet, we may wonder, does the relative (to A) descriptor $q_{Bz,1}^{(4)}$ remember $q_{Bz}^{(0)}$? First we determine

$$q_{Bz,1}^{(4)} = q_{Bz}^{(4)} \mathcal{P}_1 \left[q_{Az}^{(4)} \right] = -q_{Bz} \mathcal{P}_1 \left[q_{Az}^{(4)} \right]. \quad (8.25)$$

Then we obtain

$$\langle q_{Bz}^{(0)}, q_{Bz,1}^{(4)} \rangle_F \neq 0, \quad (8.26)$$

which means that whereas $q_{Bz}^{(4)}$ forgot, $q_{Bz,1}^{(4)}$ has some memory of itself. Memory is easily lost as a qubit *diffuses* through Hilbert space through interactions, but the memory on a particular foliation is more robust.

8.5 Is quantum mechanics complete?

We now show how to reconstruct the global density matrix from a bipartite entangled system from the local descriptors. A similar discussion can also be found in Refs. [10, 66, 68]. Following an analogous strategy of Sec. 6.3.1, we may parametrize the density matrix of a bipartite system as

$$\hat{\rho}(t) = |\psi(t)\rangle\langle\psi(t)| = \sum_{i,j=0}^3 \rho_{ij}(t) \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j. \quad (8.27)$$

Description	Local	Complete
Reduced density matrices $\hat{\rho}_A$ and $\hat{\rho}_B$	✓	×
Descriptors \mathbf{q}_A and \mathbf{q}_B	✓	✓

Table 8.1: Locality and completeness of the Heisenberg descriptors.

To find the coefficients ρ_{ij} , we evaluate

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(\hat{\rho} \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j) &= \text{Tr} \left(\sum_{a,b} \rho_{ab} \hat{\sigma}_a \otimes \hat{\sigma}_b \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j \right) = \text{Tr} \left(\sum_{a,b} \rho_{ab} \hat{\sigma}_a \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_b \hat{\sigma}_j \right) \\ &= \sum_{a,b} \text{tr}_A(\rho_{ab} \hat{\sigma}_a \hat{\sigma}_i) \text{tr}_B(\hat{\sigma}_b \hat{\sigma}_j) = \sum_{a,b} \rho_{ab} (2\delta_{ai})(2\delta_{bj}) = 4\rho_{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (8.28)$$

Therefore, the density matrix in Eq. (8.27) may be rewritten as

$$\hat{\rho}(t) = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 \text{Tr}[\hat{\rho}(t) \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j] \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j. \quad (8.29)$$

We can now express the trace in terms of the descriptors of sub-systems A and B and the Heisenberg reference vector $|\mathbf{0}\rangle$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}[\hat{\rho}(t) \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j] &= \text{Tr} \left[\hat{U}(t) |\mathbf{0}\rangle \langle \mathbf{0}| \hat{U}^\dagger(t) \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j \right] = \langle \mathbf{0} | \hat{U}^\dagger(t) \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j \hat{U}(t) | \mathbf{0} \rangle \\ &= \langle \mathbf{0} | \hat{q}_{Ai}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{Bj}^{(t)} | \mathbf{0} \rangle = \langle \hat{q}_{Ai}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{Bj}^{(t)} \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (8.30)$$

Then, the global density matrix is expressed in terms of local descriptors as

$$\hat{\rho}(t) = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 \langle \hat{q}_{Ai}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{Bj}^{(t)} \rangle \hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \hat{\sigma}_j, \quad (8.31)$$

which also establishes the explicit connection between the Schrödinger and Heisenberg pictures.

Problem 8.4: *Reconstruction of the density matrix.* Feed the descriptors of A and B of Eqs. (8.7) into Eq. (8.31) to reconstruct the density matrix. *Suggestion:* Note that due to the Heisenberg state $|\mathbf{0}\rangle$, only one element of the 4×4 matrix $\hat{q}_{Ai}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{Bj}^{(t)}$ contributes to the sum.

This solves the historic locality versus completeness dilemma of the Schrödinger picture. In this picture, we may regard the reduced density matrices as local descriptions. However, we cannot reconstruct the global density matrix from the local reduced density matrices. This means that the tracing out of the density matrix loses crucial information that would be necessary to compute a joint expectation value, which is only possible with the global density matrix. The conundrum of the Schrödinger picture lies in the fact that we have to supplement the local reduced density matrices with the global state vector $|\psi\rangle$, which then renders a non-local description.

The conundrum is solved in the Heisenberg picture. The observables \mathbf{q}_A and \mathbf{q}_B are local descriptions. If they are to be complete, then one must be able to reconstruct the density matrix from the local descriptors, which is what Eq. (8.31) achieves. Therefore, the Heisenberg picture is a local and complete description of unitary quantum mechanics. Hidden variable or collapse theories unnecessarily implement non-locality. The descriptions are summarised in Tab. 8.1.

8.6 The CHSH inequality

The CHSH inequality is a Bell-type no-go theorem due to Clauser, Horne, Shimony and Holt published in 1969 [23], five years after Bell's 1964 theorem [11]. This section serves as an exercise of how to understand the CHSH in terms of descriptors. This part is inspired by the lecture notes in Ref. [48]. The CHSH inequality is designed to test the nature of correlations. The main assumptions here are locality and that observables have single definite values (which is not the case in quantum mechanics). The combination of these assumptions is what one frequently means as *classical correlations*.

Here is the description of the experiment. Suppose Alice has access to two qubit observables $\{A_1, A_2\}$. She can choose (implicit assumption) which one to measure. The possible values for the A_k ($k = 1, 2$) are ± 1 . Similarly, Bob, that occupies a space-like separated region from Alice, has access to the observables $\{B_1, B_2\}$, which likewise assume values $B_k = \pm 1$. One may then define a new variable, with joint information, called the *CHSH variable*

$$S = A_1(B_1 - B_2) + A_2(B_1 + B_2). \quad (8.32)$$

It is fairly straightforward to work out that S may only assume the values $S = \pm 2$. Its expectation value is then restricted to $|\langle S \rangle| \leq 2$; which is the *CHSH inequality*, which is obeyed by classical correlations. In the experiment, each expectation value $\langle A_j B_k \rangle$ must be obtained from a different sub-experiment.

The nature of the production process behind the A_k and B_k , and may be classical or not. Violation of the inequality, just like in 1964's Bell's theorem, indicates that the production process cannot be explained by a classical model.

8.6.1 Quantum mechanics violates the CHSH inequality

Let us formulate the quantum mechanical version of the CHSH variable. Since each observable has the outcomes (eigenvalues) of a qubit, the observables A_k and B_k are upgraded to 2×2 qubit observables \hat{A}_k and \hat{B}_k . The CHSH observable is then

$$\hat{S} = \hat{A}_1 \otimes (\hat{B}_1 - \hat{B}_2) + \hat{A}_2 \otimes (\hat{B}_1 + \hat{B}_2), \quad (8.33)$$

where $\hat{A}_1 = \mathbf{a}_1 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$, and analogously for the others. Suppose now that the production process of both eigenvalues of $\{\hat{A}_k\}$ and $\{\hat{B}_k\}$ are qubits prepared in the singlet state $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle)$, just as in Sec. 3.1. We also know from Sec. 3.4 that $\langle \psi | \hat{A}_j \otimes \hat{B}_k | \psi \rangle = -\mathbf{a}_j \cdot \mathbf{b}_k$, where \mathbf{a}_k and \mathbf{b}_k are the measurement setups of \hat{A}_k and \hat{B}_k . We then find that

$$\langle \hat{S} \rangle = \langle \psi | \hat{S} | \psi \rangle = -\mathbf{a}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{b}_1 - \mathbf{b}_2) - \mathbf{a}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{b}_1 + \mathbf{b}_2). \quad (8.34)$$

Then, if one chooses

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = \hat{\mathbf{z}}, \quad \mathbf{a}_2 = \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \quad \mathbf{b}_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}} + \hat{\mathbf{z}}), \quad \mathbf{b}_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}} - \hat{\mathbf{z}}), \quad (8.35)$$

when we find $|\langle \hat{S} \rangle| = 2\sqrt{2} > 2$, which violates the classical CHSH inequality. In classical probability theory, the absolute value of the expectation value of the CHSH variable is bounded by 2. In quantum mechanics, the expectation value of the CHSH observable is $2\sqrt{2}$, which is also called the *Tsirelson bound*.

The CHSH inequality is frequently used to discard local and realist descriptions of quantum mechanics. All we have to do to refute this is to express the inequality violation in terms of descriptors.

Problem 8.5: *The CHSH observable in terms of descriptors. Show that*

$$\langle \psi | \hat{A}_j \otimes \hat{B}_k | \psi \rangle = \langle \mathbf{0} | \left(\mathbf{a}_j \cdot \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(t)} \right) \left(\mathbf{b}_k \cdot \hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(t)} \right) | \mathbf{0} \rangle, \quad (8.36)$$

where $|\mathbf{0}\rangle = |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$ is the Heisenberg state, and $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(t)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(t)}$ are the descriptors of qubits A and B, respectively. After this, use the descriptor components of the singlet state in Eq. (8.7) to show that

$$\langle \mathbf{0} | \left(\mathbf{a}_j \cdot \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(3)} \right) \left(\mathbf{b}_k \cdot \hat{\mathbf{q}}_B^{(3)} \right) | \mathbf{0} \rangle = -\mathbf{a}_j \cdot \mathbf{b}_k. \quad (8.37)$$

Then, the expectation value of the CHSH observable is expressed in terms of the descriptors as

$$\langle \hat{S} \rangle = \left\langle \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{A,a_1}^{(3)} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{B,b_1-b_2}^{(3)} + \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{A,a_2}^{(3)} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_{B,b_1+b_2}^{(3)} \right\rangle, \quad (8.38)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_{A,r}^{(3)} = \mathbf{r} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(3)}$.

8.7 Concluding remarks

To conclude, I paraphrase a section of an already a quarter century old paper by Deutsch and Hayden [41]:

Given that quantum theory is entirely local when expressed in the Heisenberg picture, but appears non-local in the Schrödinger picture, and given that the two pictures are mathematically equivalent, are we therefore still free to believe that quantum theory (and the physical reality it describes) is non-local? We are not – just as we should not be free to describe a theory as "complex" if it had both a simple version and a mathematically equivalent complex version. The point is that a "local" theory is defined as one for which there exists a formulation satisfying the locality conditions. If we were to classify theories as non-local whenever it was possible to reformulate them in terms of non-local quantities, then no theory would qualify as local.

Chapter 9

Thought experiments

In 2018, Frauchiger and Renner (FR) introduced a new quantum paradox, which is an extended Wigner’s friend paradox [51, 56, 92]. Their paradox demonstrates that if one adopts a set of seemingly conservative assumptions about the interpretation of quantum theory, at least one of these assumptions must be violated to maintain the consistency of quantum mechanics.

The implications and derivation of this no-go theorem continue to be debated. Notably, the paper’s most significant contribution may not be the no-go theorem itself, but rather its role in revitalizing interest in quantum foundations. The study underscores that the interpretation of quantum mechanics transcends philosophical discourse, presenting itself as a genuine problem within physics. For these reasons, we dedicate this chapter to exploring quantum thought experiments within the framework of unitary quantum mechanics.

9.1 Wigner’s friend

The origin of paradoxes involving different quantum observers is Wigner’s friend paradox [123]. Wigner starts postulating a universe with two subsystems. The first is Alice, which takes the role as an agent. The other is a qubit R , which is prepared in the state

$$|+\rangle_R = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_R, \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_R = (\sigma_z, -\sigma_y, \sigma_x)_R, \quad (9.1)$$

where we show both the Schrödinger and the Heisenberg representation. If Alice uses the $\{|1\rangle, |-1\rangle\}_R$ basis, or measures $\hat{\mathbf{z}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{q}}_R(\sigma_x^R)$, then Alice will observe the result $+1$ or -1 . In the Schrödinger picture, the observable that has the chosen basis as eigenvectors is σ_z . Since $|+\rangle_R$ is not an eigenstate of σ_z , we know that it must be a superposition state. In the Heisenberg picture, the reference state is $|1\rangle$. Alice measures σ_x , which has eigenvalues ± 1 . Moreover, σ_x is blunt with respect to $|1\rangle$, which corresponds to the superposition in the Schrödinger picture.

We extend the universe to include Wigner, a second agent that has Alice as friend, hence, *Wigner’s friend*. Wigner looks at the qubit (R) and Alice (A) as an enlarged quantum system. Wigner views Alice performing the measurement on the qubit. Because the qubit and Alice are a quantum system, they evolve unitarily and entangle, such that

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_R |1\rangle_A \xrightarrow{\text{cnot}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle_R |1\rangle_A + |-1\rangle_R |-1\rangle_A). \quad (9.2)$$

Here, for simplicity, we modelled Alice as a qubit, and we omit the Kronecker products. Alice’s pointer after her measurement reveals the eigenvalue of the qubit R . The measurement is modelled by a cnot, with the qubit R as the control, and Alice as the target. In the Heisenberg picture, using Eq. (7.30), we obtain

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}}_R = (\sigma_z^R \sigma_x^A, -\sigma_y^R \sigma_x^A, \sigma_x^R), \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A = (\sigma_x^A, \sigma_y^A \sigma_x^R, \sigma_z^A \sigma_x^R). \quad (9.3)$$

We do not track the time labels of the descriptors, and we underline the copied parts.

Wigner's friend thought experiments serves as the simplest historical example to distinguish between interpretations of quantum mechanics. In the Copenhagen interpretation, there is no universality, and speaking of the universe is disallowed. One then artificially has to introduce the so called *Heisenberg cut*, that separates the quantum system from the classical. In the Wigner's friend experiment, the position of the cut is arbitrary and subjective. For instance, if the cut is placed above Alice, then she entangles with the qubit. But since there are two terms for Alice, then Copenhagen disqualifies her as an agent. If the cut is placed below Alice, then she belongs to the classical domain, which does not allow her to entangle with the qubit. This shows that for some interpretations such as Copenhagen, Wigner's friend scenarios are paradoxes, whereas in unitary quantum theory, there is a self-consistent description. In unitary Bohmian mechanics, all subsystems may classify as agents. Their observations are determined by which foliations their particles groove. In Everettian mechanics, there are two Alices. QBism is fine with Alice and Wigner making different statements about an experiment, similar to relational mechanics.

9.2 The Wigner-Deutsch thought experiment

We now present an extension of Wigner's friend scenario by Deutsch, which adds another subsystem – a notebook N – to the universe [32, 92], which now has four subsystems. The role of the notebook is to establish a limited information flow between Alice and Wigner, and resolve whether Alice is a genuine agent (records definite outcomes), and whether Alice entangled with the qubit after her measurement. Although this thought experiment may still elude technological implementation, the experiment is allowed by quantum theory, and may provide a crucial experimental test in the future.

The notebook N is also modelled as a qubit and initialised in a ready state $|\downarrow\rangle_N$. The interaction between Alice and the notebook is such that

$$|1\rangle_A |\downarrow\rangle_N \xrightarrow{\text{not}(N)} |1\rangle_A |\uparrow\rangle_N \quad \text{and} \quad |-1\rangle_A |\downarrow\rangle_N \xrightarrow{\text{not}(N)} |-1\rangle_A |\uparrow\rangle_N. \quad (9.4)$$

That is, when Alice writes something down on the notebook, a not operation flips the notebook's qubit. This records (in N) that Alice saw a definite outcome when measuring R . However, whereas the notebook's content reveals that Alice performed a successful measurement, it does not reveal what Alice saw. Therefore, by including the notebook in Eq. (9.2), Wigner sees the other three subsystems evolving as

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_R |1\rangle_A |\downarrow\rangle_N \longrightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle_R |1\rangle_A + |-1\rangle_R |-1\rangle_A) |\uparrow\rangle_N. \quad (9.5)$$

Although the notebook interacted with Alice, it did not entangle with the Alice-qubit system. The notebook evades entanglement by abstaining from copying Alice's descriptor, which after the the interaction is $\hat{q}_N = (\sigma_x, -\sigma_y, -\sigma_z)_N$, and has no direct information about Alice. By reading the notebook, Wigner then attests that Alice saw a definite outcome, and classifies her as a genuine agent.

To answer the question whether Alice is entangled (in a superposition state) with the qubit, a last step is added to the thought experiment. Wigner already knows that Alice is a genuine agent. In the last step, the interaction between Alice and the notebook (not), and Alice and the qubit (cnot) is undone unitarily, such that the final state of the three subsystems coincides with their initial state $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_R |1\rangle_A |\downarrow\rangle_N$. Wigner now can check whether the system evolved unitarily with Alice going through a superposition (entangled) state, or whether Alice's measurement triggered a collapse. How? Wigner now measures the x -observable of the R qubit. If the state is $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_R |1\rangle_A |\downarrow\rangle_N$, then the outcome is 1 with probability 1. If there were a collapse,

Figure 9.1: Illustration of the eight qubits in the Frauchiger-Renner thought experiment. The stick figures were taken from freepik.com.

then Wigner would see a random outcome. Deutsch's thought experiment allows one to distinguish between collapse theories and Everettian mechanics.

A perhaps controversial topic still under discussion is the fact that Alice's memory was erased. This made Scott Aaronson coin the phrase "*It's hard to think when someone Hadamards your brain*", or in this case *cnotted* [1]. To this, Renner replied "*Yes, it is hard to think after someone Hadamarded your brain, but certainly not before!*". If Wigner asks Alice what is her state, she will always answer $|1\rangle_A$, even though Wigner knows that if the experiment is repeated many times, roughly half of the times her state would have been $| - 1\rangle_A$ at some point. This suggests that in unitary quantum mechanics, agents described by a small Hilbert subspace will inevitably suffer from memory loss. The larger the agents, the more stable will be their memory.

Problem 9.1: *The Wigner-Deutsch experiment in a different basis.* Suppose that the entire thought experiment is performed in a different reference frame, for instance, apply a Hadamard to the entire setup in Eq. (9.5). The cnot and not interaction must also be transformed accordingly (See Prob. 7.9). Can Wigner still reliably check whether Alice is an agent and if she was in a superposition state?

9.3 The Frauchiger-Renner thought experiment

One of the downsides of the Wigner-Deutsch protocol is that Wigner cannot simultaneously uncover what Alice observed, and confirm that she was in a superposition state. The reason is that Wigner can only check what Alice observed by entangling with her, after which Wigner cannot confirm the superposition. The FR experiment is designed to overcome this difficulty. The experiment includes four agents and two qubits, a total of six subsystems.

An additional feature of the FR experiment is that agents, in addition to measuring other subsystems, also make statements about the outcomes of other agents. Agents use three simple rules in their reasoning: (Q) they use quantum theory and the Born rule; (C) an agent may adopt the conclusions drawn by another agent; (S) when measuring, an agent sees an unequivocal outcome. The Wigner-Deutsch experiment already taught us that we must be very careful with (C), because Alice's memory was erased. Therefore, Alice, or similar agents, should use (C) before erasure.

9.3.1 The Schrödinger picture

Because the protocol is more elaborate compared to the Wigner-Deutsch setting, we restore the time-labels. At time $t = 0$, the R qubit is in the state $|1\rangle_R$. Next, R is prepared in a superposition state by the action of a rotation

$$R_{\hat{y}}(\varphi)|1\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right)|1\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right)|-1\rangle, \quad (9.6)$$

with $\varphi = 2 \arcsin(\sqrt{2/3}) \approx 1.91$ rad. At $t = 1$ the R qubit is in the state

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|-1\rangle \right)_R. \quad (9.7)$$

Immediately after with $t \in (1, 2)$, Alice measures the qubit via a cnot, such that

$$\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|-1\rangle \right)_R |1\rangle_A \xrightarrow{\text{cnot}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle_R|1\rangle_A + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|-1\rangle_R|-1\rangle_A; \quad (9.8)$$

Using rule (S), Alice writes either I unequivocally saw $+1$ or -1 into her memory.

Based on the outcome Alice observed, she prepares a qubit S to be sent to another agent Bob. If $|1\rangle_A$, Alice prepares $|1\rangle_S$. If $|-1\rangle_A$, she prepares $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_S$. The conditional that was just described defines a *controlled Hadamard* operation. Therefore, the evolution before and after the action of the controlled Hadamard (cH) at $t \in (2, 3)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle_R|1\rangle_A + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|-1\rangle_R|-1\rangle_A \right) |1\rangle_S \xrightarrow{\text{cH}} \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle_R|1\rangle_A|1\rangle_S + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|-1\rangle_R|-1\rangle_A \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_S. \end{aligned} \quad (9.9)$$

In the time interval $t \in (3, 4)$, Bob measures his qubit S prepared by Alice in the computational basis $\{|1\rangle, |-1\rangle\}_S$ using rule (S). The measurement is again modelled by a cnot with S as the control, and Bob as the target. The extended system now evolves as ($t = 4$)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle_R|1\rangle_A|1\rangle_S + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}|-1\rangle_R|-1\rangle_A \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_S \right] |1\rangle_B \longrightarrow \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|1\rangle_R|1\rangle_A|1\rangle_S|1\rangle_B + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|-1\rangle_R|-1\rangle_A (|1\rangle_S|1\rangle_B + |-1\rangle_S|-1\rangle_B) = \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} [|1, 1\rangle_{RA}|1, 1\rangle_{SB} + |-1, -1\rangle_{RA} (|1, 1\rangle + |-1, -1\rangle)_{SB}]. \end{aligned} \quad (9.10)$$

To abbreviate things a little, we write $|1, 1\rangle_{RA} = |1\rangle_R|1\rangle_A$ and $|-1, -1\rangle_{RA} = |-1\rangle_R|-1\rangle_A$. Note that in Eq. (9.10), the labs only admit states of the $|\pm 1, \pm 1\rangle$ type. Then, someone measuring these labs may ask whether the labs' states are in the states $|1, 1\rangle$, $|-1, -1\rangle$, or in superpositions among the two, which form Bell states. For this reason, we introduce a new basis for Alice's (RA) or Bob's (BS) lab as

$$|\checkmark\rangle_{RA} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1, 1\rangle - |-1, -1\rangle)_{RA}; \quad |\times\rangle_{RA} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1, 1\rangle + |-1, -1\rangle)_{RA}. \quad (9.11)$$

Note that the new basis $\{|\checkmark\rangle, |\times\rangle\}_{RA}$ does not span the entire Hilbert space of the two qubit lab, but it does not matter here. The inverse relations are

$$|1, 1\rangle_{RA} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\times\rangle + |\checkmark\rangle)_{RA}, \quad |-1, -1\rangle_{RA} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\times\rangle - |\checkmark\rangle)_{RA}. \quad (9.12)$$

In the new basis, the last line of Eq. (9.10) at $t = 4$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} [(|\times\rangle + |\checkmark\rangle)_{RA} (|\times\rangle + |\checkmark\rangle)_{SB} + (|\times\rangle - |\checkmark\rangle)_{RA} 2|\times\rangle_{SB}] = \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} [3|\times\rangle_{RA}|\times\rangle_{SB} - |\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\times\rangle_{SB} + |\times\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_{SB} + |\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_{SB}]. \end{aligned} \quad (9.13)$$

We may check the weights of all the terms in Eq. (9.13) and verify that it is normalized.

Problem 9.2: Normalization. Verify that Eq. (9.13) is normalized.

9.3.2 How to measure Bell states in the computational basis

In quantum circuit protocols such as in Fig. 9.2, the memories are usually configured to measure the computational basis $\{|1\rangle, |-1\rangle\}$, not the Bell basis. Yet, such a circuit may still perform measurements in the Bell basis by performing the appropriate preparations. Recall that the gates that are necessary to prepare the Bell state $|\times\rangle_{RA}$ in Eq. (9.11) is a cnot followed by a Hadamard, as discussed in Sec. 2.4. To undo such a Bell state we the apply the cnot followed by the Hadamard $H \otimes I$. The reader may then check that this preparation allows the measurers set up in the computational basis to verify if the labs find themselves in one of the Bell states. To show this explicitly, we perform the following preparation on the first line of Eq. (9.10). First, apply a cnot between R and A , with A as the target. Do the same for S and B , with B as the target. Then, apply the Hadamard H to R and A and also to S and B . The resulting state is

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} [3|1, 1\rangle_{RA}|1, 1\rangle_{SB} - |-1, 1\rangle_{RA}|1, 1\rangle_{SB} + |1, 1\rangle_{RA}|-1, 1\rangle_{SB} + |-1, 1\rangle_{RA}|-1, 1\rangle_{SB}]. \quad (9.14)$$

By comparing this with the last line of Eq.(9.13), we may draw the identification $|\times\rangle \leftrightarrow |1, 1\rangle$ and $|\checkmark\rangle \leftrightarrow |-1, 1\rangle$. Ursula, who is about to measure R and A , is initialised in the state $|1, 1\rangle_{UR, UA}$. We see that Ursula's sensor organ must have enough internal structure to interact with R and A separately. If the U_R part of Ursula's sensor records the -1 eigenvalue of R , then she knows that the lab is in the $|\checkmark\rangle_{RA}$ state.

9.3.3 Ursula's and Wigner's measurement in the Bell basis

Here, we use the Bell basis introduced in Eq. (9.11). We will use the computational basis when analysing the protocol in the Heisenberg picture.

Between $t \in (4, 5)$ we introduce the additional agent Ursula (U), who has full quantum control of Alice's lab. Ursula measures Alice's entire lab (RA) in the $\{|\checkmark\rangle, |\times\rangle\}_{RA}$ basis via a cnot. This gives (from Eq. (9.13))

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} [(|\times\rangle + |\checkmark\rangle)_{RA} (|\times\rangle + |\checkmark\rangle)_{SB} + 2 (|\times\rangle - |\checkmark\rangle)_{RA} |\times\rangle_{SB}] |\checkmark\rangle_U \longrightarrow \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} [(|\times\rangle_{RA}|\times\rangle_U + |\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_U) (|\times\rangle + |\checkmark\rangle)_{SB} + 2 (|\times\rangle_{RA}|\times\rangle_U - |\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_U) |\times\rangle_{SB}]. \end{aligned} \quad (9.15)$$

In the same time interval, another external agent, Wigner (W), has full quantum control over Bob's lab (SB), and measures it in the $\{|\checkmark\rangle, |\times\rangle\}_{SB}$ basis via a cnot. This yields the final state containing all six subsystems:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} [(|\times\rangle_{RA}|\times\rangle_U + |\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_U) (|\times\rangle + |\checkmark\rangle)_{SB} + 2 (|\times\rangle_{RA}|\times\rangle_U - |\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_U) |\times\rangle_{SB}] |\checkmark\rangle_W \longrightarrow \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} [(|\times\rangle_{RA}|\times\rangle_U + |\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_U) (|\times\rangle_{SB}|\times\rangle_W + |\checkmark\rangle_{SB}|\checkmark\rangle_W)] \\ & + \frac{2}{\sqrt{12}} [(|\times\rangle_{RA}|\times\rangle_U - |\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_U) |\times\rangle_{SB}|\times\rangle_W]. \end{aligned} \quad (9.16)$$

The end result has six types of relative states. Let us check how the end state in Eq. (9.16) looks like in the $\{|1, 1\rangle, |-1, -1\rangle\}$ basis. After the calculations, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} [(|11\rangle_{RA}|11\rangle_U + |-1, -1\rangle_{RA}|-1, -1\rangle_U) (|11\rangle_{SB}|11\rangle_W + |-1, -1\rangle_{SB}|-1, -1\rangle_W)] \\ & + \frac{2}{\sqrt{12}} [(|11\rangle_{RA}|-1, -1\rangle_U - |-1, -1\rangle_{RA}|11\rangle_U)] \times \\ & \frac{1}{2} [|11\rangle_{SB}|11\rangle_W + |-1, -1\rangle_{SB}|-1, -1\rangle_W + |11\rangle_{SB}|-1, -1\rangle_W + |-1, -1\rangle_{SB}|11\rangle_W], \end{aligned} \quad (9.17)$$

which has 12 inequivalent relative states. Note that this basis has terms such as $|-1, -1\rangle_{SB}|11\rangle_W$, which means that Wigner sees $(1, 1)$ by measuring $(-1, -1)$, an issue we must be careful about.

9.3.4 The apparent paradox

Let us now go through a particular run of the experiment that leads to an apparent paradox. In this run, one assumes that the agents are allowed to use the following rules [93]:

- (Q-Quantum) Any agent may describe any system around them using the formalism of quantum theory and, based on this description, infer predictions (or retrodictions) of measurement outcomes using the quantum-mechanical Born rule;
- (C-Conclusions) An agent can use conclusions obtained by admitting the view of another agent;
- (S-Single) A measurement carried out by an agent has a definitive outcome from the viewpoint of the measuring agent.

In advance, we *italicize* the problematic statements.

We start with the situation in Eq. (9.9), which is before Ursula and Wigner enter the protocol. Suppose that Alice measured the -1 eigenvalue of the R qubit, which is supported by rule (S). Then, looking at the state

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} |1, 1\rangle_{RA} |1\rangle_S + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} |-1, -1\rangle_{RA} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_S, \quad (9.18)$$

we infer that Alice must have prepared the S qubit in the $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle + |-1\rangle)_S$ state. Now, looking at Eq. (9.10), Bob and S evolved to the entangled state $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|1\rangle_S |1\rangle_B + |-1\rangle_S |-1\rangle_B) \equiv |\times\rangle_{SB}$. Since it is Wigner who measures SB , Wigner will necessarily see the \times eigenvalue. *Alice, which is aware of the experiment's protocol, can use rule (Q), and predict that if she measures -1 , Wigner will measure \times .* The statement is problematic because, as we will soon see, the first term in Eq. (9.18) influences Wigner's measurement.

Now we turn to Bob's inference. Using rule (S), suppose he measured the -1 eigenvalue of qubit S . By looking at the last term of Eq. (9.10), and using (Q), Bob then concludes that Alice obtained the -1 eigenvalue of the R qubit. *Using rule (C), he may therefore adopt Alice's conclusion that Wigner will measure \times .*

We now turn to Ursula's inference, for which we may look at Eq. (9.15). Suppose that Ursula measures \checkmark by rule (S). Then, the only corresponding RA relative state is $|\checkmark\rangle_{RA}$, so that using (Q), Ursula is sure that the RA lab is in the \checkmark state. We may then look for the $|\checkmark\rangle_{RA}$ state in Eq. (9.10). *For this, one changes the RA part of Eq. (9.10) to Ursula's basis, but maintains the SB in the computational basis.* The only part relative to $|\checkmark\rangle_{RA}$ is

$$-\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}}|\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|-1, -1\rangle_{SB}. \quad (9.19)$$

Therefore, using (C), Ursula infers that Bob measured -1 , and hence Ursula also comes to the conclusion that Wigner will measure \times . Up to now, everyone seems to have consistent conclusions. Wigner may now adopt Ursula's conclusion that he will measure \times .

Note, however, that in the end state in Eq. (9.16), there is one relative state that admits

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{12}}|\checkmark\rangle_{RA}|\checkmark\rangle_U|\checkmark\rangle_{SB}|\checkmark\rangle_W. \quad (9.20)$$

In this state, Ursula observed \checkmark , from which Wigner, using (C), should be able to infer that he will measure \times , but using (S) he actually measured \checkmark , which is a contradiction.

Within unitary quantum interpretations, the paradoxes' origin lies in (C). The reason is that one cannot adopt statements obtained by other agents, if the other agents has a different reference frame (basis) to start with. In other words, one cannot chain together statements from incompatible bases. To see an implemented illustration of the incompatibility using a quantum circuit, see Ref. [120]. In the words of Lazarovici [77]: "If different *agents* make inconsistent predictions by applying a quantum theory that makes a consistent prediction, it can only mean that at least one of the agents applies the theory incorrectly." Another way to understand this is noticing that when Alice measures -1 in Eq. (9.10), she cannot ignore the first term in Eq. (9.10) that affects future measurement outcomes. This is also nicely stated by Vedral's abstract [119]: "Unperformed measurements have no results. Unobserved results can affect future measurements." The FR thought experiment is an ongoing research topic. For recent developments, the reader may check Refs. [31, 96].

9.4 Descriptors fo the Frauchiger-Renner protocol

We now discuss the protocol using the Heisenberg picture and the circuit in the computational basis illustrated in Fig. 9.2. At time $t = 0$, the R qubit is in the state $|1\rangle_R$, with $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_R^{(0)} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)_R$, and so are all other qubits. To construct the descriptor $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_R^{(1)}$, we first write the functional representation of the rotation operator

$$U_{R_y(\varphi)}[\hat{\mathbf{q}}^{(t)}] = I \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right) - i\hat{q}_y^{(t)} \sin\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right). \quad (9.21)$$

With this, we can work out how a rotation about y evolves the qubit descriptor. We obtain

$$R_{\hat{y}}(\varphi) : \hat{\mathbf{q}}_R^{(t+1)} = \left(\hat{q}_{R_x}^{(t)} \cos \varphi + \hat{q}_{R_z}^{(t)} \sin \varphi, \hat{q}_{R_y}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{R_z}^{(t)} \cos \varphi - \hat{q}_{R_x}^{(t)} \sin \varphi \right). \quad (9.22)$$

With $\varphi = 2 \arcsin(\sqrt{2/3})$, we have

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}}_R^{(1)} = (\sigma_x \cos \varphi + \sigma_z \sin \varphi, \sigma_y, \sigma_z \cos \varphi - \sigma_x \sin \varphi)_R. \quad (9.23)$$

Figure 9.2: The Frauchiger-Renner protocol. Ursula performs the measurements over Alice's lab, and Wigner performs the measurements over Bob's lab. Ursula's relative state $|1, 1\rangle_{U_R, U_S}$ corresponds to $|\times\rangle_{RA}$, and $|-1, 1\rangle_{U_R, U_S}$ corresponds to $|\checkmark\rangle_{RA}$. The analogous correspondence applies to Wigner. The grey region prepares the Bell-basis. The qubit legs for Ursula and Wigner are only displayed at the end for clarity.

In the interval $t \in (1, 2)$, Alice measures the qubit via a cnot, such that

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{q}}_R^{(2)} &= \left[(\sigma_x^R c + \sigma_z^R s) \underline{\sigma}_x^A, \sigma_y^R \underline{\sigma}_x^A, \sigma_z^R c - \sigma_x^R s \right]; \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(2)} &= \left[\sigma_x^A, \sigma_y^A (\sigma_z^R c - \sigma_x^R s), \sigma_z^A (\sigma_z^R c - \sigma_x^R s) \right].\end{aligned}\quad (9.24)$$

We abbreviated $c = \cos\left(2 \arcsin(\sqrt{2/3})\right) = -1/3$ and $s = \sin\left(2 \arcsin(\sqrt{2/3})\right) = 2\sqrt{2}/3$, which satisfy $c^2 + s^2 = 1$. Note that only $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_R^{(2)}$ clearly reveals how the qubit changed after Alice's measurement.

To work out the descriptors for A and S after the action of the controlled-Hadamard, we must first obtain its functional representation and action on the control and target qubits. Using the result of Prob. 7.7, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\text{cH} : \quad \hat{\mathbf{q}}_C^{(t+1)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{Cx}^{(t)} \hat{U}_{H,T}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{Cy}^{(t)} \hat{U}_{H,T}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{Cz}^{(t)} \right); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_T^{(t+1)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{Tx}^{(t)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_1^{(t)} + \hat{q}_{Tz}^{(t)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{Ty}^{(t)} \hat{q}_{Cz}^{(t)}, \hat{q}_{Tz}^{(t)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_1^{(t)} + \hat{q}_{Tx}^{(t)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1}^{(t)} \right).\end{aligned}\quad (9.25)$$

At time $t = 2$, the descriptor of Bob's qubit S is $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_S^{(2)} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)_S$. Then, after Alice's preparation of S at $t \in (2, 3)$, the descriptors update to

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{q}}_R^{(3)} &= \left[(\sigma_x^R c + \sigma_z^R s) \underline{\sigma}_x^A, \sigma_y^R \underline{\sigma}_x^A, \sigma_z^R c - \sigma_x^R s \right]; \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(3)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{Ax}^{(2)} \hat{U}_{H,S}^{(2)}, \hat{q}_{Ay}^{(2)} \hat{U}_{H,S}^{(2)}, \hat{q}_{Az}^{(2)} \right); \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_S^{(3)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{Sx}^{(2)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{1,A}^{(2)} + \hat{q}_{Sz}^{(2)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1,A}^{(2)}, \hat{q}_{Sy}^{(2)} \hat{q}_{Az}^{(2)}, \hat{q}_{Sz}^{(2)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{1,A}^{(2)} + \hat{q}_{Sx}^{(2)} \hat{\mathcal{P}}_{-1,A}^{(2)} \right).\end{aligned}\quad (9.26)$$

Let us perform a sanity check and compare the expectation value of the z observable of qubit S (σ_z^S) after the controlled Hadamard at $t = 3$. In the Schrödinger picture, the state after the controlled Hadamard is given by the last line of Eq. (9.10), which we repeat below:

$$|\psi_3\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} [|11\rangle_{RA} |11\rangle_{SB} + |-1-1\rangle_{RA} (|11\rangle + |-1-1\rangle)_{SB}].\quad (9.27)$$

Then, the expectation value is $\langle \psi_3 | \sigma_z^S | \psi_3 \rangle = 1/3$. In the Heisenberg picture this is

$$\langle \hat{q}_{S,z}^{(3)} \rangle = \langle \hat{q}_{Sz}^{(2)} \hat{P}_{1,A}^{(2)} + \hat{q}_{Sx}^{(2)} \hat{P}_{-1,A}^{(2)} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} [\langle \sigma_z^S \rangle + \langle \sigma_z^A \sigma_z^R \rangle c] = \frac{1}{3}, \quad (9.28)$$

which agrees with the Schrödinger picture.

At $t \in (3, 4)$, Bob interacts with his qubit S via a controlled-not, with Bob as the target. Before the interaction, Bob's initial descriptor is $\hat{q}_B^{(3)} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)_B$. Then, after the cnot:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{q}_R^{(4)} &= \left[(\sigma_x^R c + \sigma_z^R s) \underline{\sigma}_x^A, \sigma_y^R \underline{\sigma}_x^A, \sigma_z^R c - \sigma_x^R s \right]; \\ \hat{q}_A^{(4)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{Ax}^{(2)} \hat{U}_{H,S}^{(2)}, \hat{q}_{Ay}^{(2)} \hat{U}_{H,S}^{(2)}, \hat{q}_{Az}^{(2)} \right); \\ \hat{q}_S^{(4)} &= \left(\hat{q}_{Sx}^{(3)} \underline{\sigma}_x^B, \hat{q}_{Sy}^{(3)} \underline{\sigma}_x^B, \hat{q}_{Sz}^{(3)} \right); \\ \hat{q}_B^{(4)} &= \left(\sigma_x^B, \sigma_y^B, \hat{q}_{Sz}^{(3)}, \sigma_z^B \hat{q}_{Sz}^{(3)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (9.29)$$

In Sec. 9.3.2, we showed how Ursula and Wigner may perform a Bell basis measurement through their z components. The preparation involves first a cnot on (RA) and another cnot on (SB) . This yields

$$\begin{aligned} q_R^{(5)} &= \left(q_{Rx}^{(4)} q_{Ax}^{(4)}, q_{Ry}^{(4)} q_{Ax}^{(4)}, q_{Rz}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_A^{(5)} &= \left(q_{Ax}^{(4)}, q_{Ay}^{(4)} q_{Rz}^{(4)}, q_{Az}^{(4)} q_{Rz}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_S^{(5)} &= \left(q_{Sx}^{(4)} q_{Bx}^{(4)}, q_{Sy}^{(4)} q_{Bx}^{(4)}, q_{Sz}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_B^{(5)} &= \left(q_{Bx}^{(4)}, q_{By}^{(4)} q_{Sz}^{(4)}, q_{Bz}^{(4)} q_{Sz}^{(4)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (9.30)$$

Then, a Hadamard on R and S gives

$$\begin{aligned} q_R^{(6)} &= \left(q_{Rz}^{(4)}, -q_{Ry}^{(4)} q_{Ax}^{(4)}, q_{Rx}^{(4)} q_{Ax}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_A^{(6)} &= \left(q_{Ax}^{(4)}, q_{Ay}^{(4)} q_{Rz}^{(4)}, q_{Az}^{(4)} q_{Rz}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_S^{(6)} &= \left(q_{Sz}^{(4)}, -q_{Sy}^{(4)} q_{Bx}^{(4)}, q_{Sx}^{(4)} q_{Bx}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_B^{(6)} &= \left(q_{Bx}^{(4)}, q_{By}^{(4)} q_{Sz}^{(4)}, q_{Bz}^{(4)} q_{Sz}^{(4)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (9.31)$$

Ursula and Wigner now measure their respective labs. Because each one of them measures two qubits, their sensor organ also must be composed of two qubits. Therefore, Ursula and Wigner initialize with the descriptors

$$\begin{aligned} q_{U_R}^{(6)} &= (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)_{U_R}; \\ q_{U_A}^{(6)} &= (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)_{U_A}; \\ q_{W_S}^{(6)} &= (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)_{W_S}; \\ q_{W_B}^{(6)} &= (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)_{W_B}. \end{aligned} \quad (9.32)$$

After their interactions with the labs, all the systems evolve to

$$\begin{aligned} q_R^{(7)} &= \left(q_{Rz}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{U_R}, -q_{Ry}^{(4)} q_{Ax}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{U_R}, q_{Rx}^{(4)} q_{Ax}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_A^{(7)} &= \left(q_{Ax}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{U_A}, q_{Ay}^{(4)} q_{Rz}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{U_A}, q_{Az}^{(4)} q_{Rz}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_S^{(7)} &= \left(q_{Sz}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{W_S}, -q_{Sy}^{(4)} q_{Bx}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{W_S}, q_{Sx}^{(4)} q_{Bx}^{(4)} \right); \\ q_B^{(7)} &= \left(q_{Bx}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{W_B}, q_{By}^{(4)} q_{Sz}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{W_B}, q_{Bz}^{(4)} q_{Sz}^{(4)} \right); \end{aligned} \quad (9.33)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
q_{U_R}^{(7)} &= \left(\sigma_x^{U_R}, \sigma_y^{U_R} q_{R_x}^{(4)} q_{A_x}^{(4)}, \sigma_z^{U_R} q_{R_x}^{(4)} q_{A_x}^{(4)} \right); \\
q_{U_A}^{(7)} &= \left(\sigma_x^{U_A}, \sigma_y^{U_A} q_{A_z}^{(4)} q_{R_z}^{(4)}, \sigma_z^{U_A} q_{A_z}^{(4)} q_{R_z}^{(4)} \right); \\
q_{W_S}^{(7)} &= \left(\sigma_x^{W_S}, \sigma_y^{W_S} q_{S_x}^{(4)} q_{B_x}^{(4)}, \sigma_z^{W_S} q_{S_x}^{(4)} q_{B_x}^{(4)} \right); \\
q_{W_B}^{(7)} &= \left(\sigma_x^{W_B}, \sigma_y^{W_B} q_{B_z}^{(4)} q_{S_z}^{(4)}, \sigma_z^{W_B} q_{B_z}^{(4)} q_{S_z}^{(4)} \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{9.34}$$

Some notable facts. $q_{U_{R,z}}^{(7)}$ has no memory of A . $q_{U_{A,z}}^{(7)}$ knows nothing about S , and lost memory of R . The first part of Ursula's organ has information about the qubits R and S , whereas the second part of the organ knows about Alice. The only system Ursula's joint organ knows nothing about is Bob. $q_{W_{S,z}}^{(7)}$ lost its memory of Bob. $q_{W_{B,z}}^{(7)}$ only knows about Bob. Although Ursula's organ is ignorant about Bob, Wigner's joint organ knows about R , A and B , so Wigner knows more than Ursula.

9.4.1 Yggdrasill

We are now in position to draw the branching tree for the FR protocol. Between $t = 1$ and $t = 2$, Alice and R foliate into relative states as illustrated in Fig. 9.3. Next, let us ask whether Alice and S foliate further between $t = 2$ and $t = 3$. For this, we check if the conditions for foliating outlined in Prob. 8.3 are satisfied. We first check if the expectation value of the projections is non-zero. We have

$$\left\langle \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1} \left[q_{A_z}^{(3)} \right] \right\rangle = \frac{1}{3} \text{ or } \frac{2}{3}, \quad \left\langle \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1} \left[q_{S_z}^{(3)} \right] \right\rangle = \frac{2}{3} \text{ or } \frac{1}{3}. \tag{9.35}$$

Therefore, up to now, there is now restriction to calculate the conditional expectation values. However, to clearly define the foliations, we must also check if the product $q_{A_z}^{(3)} q_{S_z}^{(3)}$ is sharp. We may verify that

$$\left\langle q_{A_z}^{(3)} q_{S_z}^{(3)} \right\rangle = \frac{1}{3}, \tag{9.36}$$

which means that no sharp foliation relative to Alice and S occurs. In Fig. 9.3, we illustrate this by the blurry region between $t = 2$ and $t = 3$.

Although the Ω_A, Ω_S portion of the branching tree is blurry, let us investigate if this is followed by sharp branches for Ω_S, Ω_B between times $t = 3$ and $t = 4$. The product

$$q_{S_z}^{(4)} q_{B_z}^{(4)} = q_{S_z}^{(3)} \sigma_z^B q_{S_z}^{(3)} = \sigma_z^B \tag{9.37}$$

is indeed sharp. Moreover, the expectation values for the projections are

$$\left\langle \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1} \left[q_{B_z}^{(4)} \right] \right\rangle = \frac{2}{3} \text{ or } \frac{1}{3}, \quad \left\langle \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1} \left[q_{S_z}^{(4)} \right] \right\rangle = \frac{2}{3} \text{ or } \frac{1}{3}. \tag{9.38}$$

Therefore, the interaction between S and Bob allows for sharp foliations with the relative descriptors given by

$$q_{B_z, \pm 1}^{(4)} = q_{B_z}^{(4)} \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1} \left[q_{S_z}^{(4)} \right] = \sigma_z^B q_{S_z}^{(3)} \frac{1}{2} \left(I \pm q_{S_z}^{(3)} \right) = \pm \sigma_z^B \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1} \left[q_{S_z}^{(3)} \right]. \tag{9.39}$$

\mathfrak{B} , interacting with the blurry region, foliates into $\Omega_{B,1}/\Omega_{S,1}$ and $\Omega_{B,-1}/\Omega_{S,-1}$. However, note that the region connecting Alice's and Bob's labs is blurry.

Between $t = 4$ and $t = 5$, the cnot applied Alice and her qubit diffuses their foliations that before $t = 4$ were sharp. The foliations remain blurry up to $t = 6$ after the Hadamard is applied to

Figure 9.3: Local branching tree for the Frauchiger-Renner thought experiment exists. The blurry regions connect systems through blunt foliations.

R . By examining the product $q_{S_z}^{(5)} q_{B_z}^{(5)}$, we may also check that Bob's lab also diffuses. This remains after the Hadamard on S , so $q_{S_z}^{(6)} q_{B_z}^{(6)}$ is also blurry.

Now we focus on Ursula's part that measures R . We may verify that the product $q_{R,z}^{(7)} q_{U_{R,z}}^{(7)}$ is sharp. The reader may also check the projections. The relative descriptor of Ursula's first sensor is thus

$$q_{U_{R,z},\pm 1}^{(7)} = q_{U_{R,z}}^{(7)} \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1} [q_{Rz}^{(7)}] = \pm \sigma_z^{UR} \mathcal{P}_{\pm 1} [q_{Rz}^{(7)}], \quad (9.40)$$

showing that Ursula's sensor foliates into $\mathfrak{Q}_{U_{R,\pm 1}}/\mathfrak{Q}_{R,\pm 1}$. Something more interesting happens for Ursula's second sensor that measures Alice, which we may already infer from Eq. (9.14). We may readily verify that $q_{A_z}^{(7)} q_{U_{A,z}}^{(7)}$ is sharp, which allows for a sharp evolution. However, $\langle q_{A_z}^{(7)} \rangle = 1$, such that

$$\langle \mathcal{P}_1 [q_{A_z}^{(7)}] \rangle = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \mathcal{P}_{-1} [q_{A_z}^{(7)}] \rangle = 0. \quad (9.41)$$

This means that the only foliation that evolves from the interaction is $\mathfrak{Q}_{U_{A,1}}/\mathfrak{Q}_{A,1}$.

At last, we look at Wigner's interaction with his lab. The product $q_{S_z}^{(7)} q_{W_{S,z}}^{(7)} = \sigma_z^{WS}$ is sharp. We first examine

$$\langle q_{S_z}^{(7)} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} (1 - c) = \frac{2}{3}. \quad (9.42)$$

This yields the projections

$$\langle \mathcal{P}_1 [q_{S_z}^{(7)}] \rangle = \frac{5}{6} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \mathcal{P}_{-1} [q_{S_z}^{(7)}] \rangle = \frac{1}{6}, \quad (9.43)$$

which is in agreement with Eq. (9.14). This defines the foliations $\mathfrak{Q}_{W_{S,\pm 1}}/\mathfrak{Q}_{S,\pm 1}$. Now we check Wigner's part that measures Bob. The product $q_{B_z}^{(7)} q_{W_{B,z}}^{(7)} = \sigma_z^{WB}$ is sharp. The expectation value $\langle q_{B_z}^{(7)} \rangle = 1$, which only allows for the projection $\langle \mathcal{P}_1 [q_{B_z}^{(7)}] \rangle = 1$. Therefore, the only sharp foliation is $\mathfrak{Q}_{W_{B,1}}/\mathfrak{Q}_{B,1}$.

Time	Interaction	Gate	Foliations	Projections
(0, 1)	-	Rotation on R	-	-
(1, 2)	R, A	Controlled-not	Sharp	1/3, 2/3
(2, 3)	A, S	Controlled- H	Non-sharp	1/3, 2/3
(3, 4)	S, B	Controlled-not	Sharp	1/3, 2/3
(4, 5)	R, A	Controlled-not	Non-sharp	1/3, 2/3
(4, 5)	S, B	Controlled-not	Non-sharp	1/3, 2/3
(5, 6)	R, A	Hadamard on R	Non-sharp	5/6, 1/6
(5, 6)	S, B	Hadamard on S	Non-sharp	5/6, 1/6
(6, 7)	R, U_R	Controlled-not	Sharp	5/6, 1/6
(6, 7)	A, U_A	Controlled-not	Sharp	1, 0
(6, 7)	S, W_S	Controlled-not	Sharp	5/6, 1/6
(6, 7)	B, W_B	Controlled-not	Sharp	1, 0

Table 9.1: Summary of the time intervals (t_1, t_2) , the parties involved (X, Y) , the operation on the parties, the sharpness of the resulting foliations, and the values of the expectation values of the projections $\langle P_1 [q_{Xz}^{(t_2)}] \rangle$ and $\langle P_{-1} [q_{Xz}^{(t_2)}] \rangle$.

9.4.2 Discussion

Based on Tab. 9.1, in Fig. 9.3 we draw the Everettian branching tree for the Frauchiger-Renner protocol. In contrast to the Schrödinger picture, here the branching tree has non-sharp parts and all foliations are spatially local. In the interval $t \in (0, 1)$ the Hadamard changes the expectation value of the R qubit, which is indicated by a colour change. The black trunk of the tree contains instances of all eight qubits, but we emphasise the specific subsystems that are being foliated. If R and A foliate, all other systems remain unaffected. The first sharp foliation occurs at $t \in (1, 2)$, when the controlled-not originates $R_{\pm 1}/A_{\pm 1}$. The projection weights of these foliations may be consulted in Tab. 9.1. These foliations remain unaffected until $t \in (4, 5)$, when another controlled-not at the same physical location diffuses $R_{\pm 1}/A_{\pm 1}$. Between $t \in (2, 3)$, the controlled-Hadamard among A and S leads to the first interference bubble, which we indicate by the blurry part with the colour reflecting the projection weights from the sharp foliations entering and emerging from the region. Whatever enters the blurry region, contributes to the outcomes of foliations that emerge from it at a later time. Note that until $t \in (3, 4)$, the same instance of S and B were carried through all branches of the tree until they finally foliated into $S_{\pm 1}/B_{\pm 1}$ due to a controlled-not at their physical location. At $t \in (4, 5)$ both the $R_{\pm 1}/A_{\pm 1}$ and $S_{\pm 1}/B_{\pm 1}$ foliations diffuse through controlled-not gates. Between $t \in (5, 6)$ the Hadamard on R and S changes the projections, which we again indicate with the colour transition. The final measurements by Ursula and Wigner lead to the final foliations $R_{\pm 1}/U_{R\pm 1}/A_1/U_{A1}$ and $S_{\pm 1}/W_{S\pm 1}/B_1/W_{B1}$.

The Frauchiger-Renner thought experiment stirred the communities' interest, because they showed that at least one of three seemingly conservative statements must be false. We recall the statements here: (Q) Any agent may describe any system around them using the formalism of quantum theory and, based on this description, infer predictions (or retrodictions) of measurement outcomes using the quantum-mechanical Born rule; (C) An agent can use conclusions obtained by admitting the view of another agent; (S) A measurement carried out by an agent has a definitive outcome from the viewpoint of the measuring agent. It is known that Everettian quantum theory rejects at least one of the rules [51]. In light of the tree in Fig. 9.3, we may comment on the statements in the present context. Here, (S) remains true. To evaluate (C), the original argument uses Alice's relative outcome R_{-1}/A_{-1} to infer that B_1/W_{B1} . Yet, quantum theory admits both $B_{\pm 1}/W_{B\pm 1}$.

The reason is that both foliations $R_{\pm 1}/A_{\pm 1}$ contribute to $B_{\pm 1}/W_{B_{\pm 1}}$ through a non-sharp region. The same happens for the pilot-wave in Bohmian mechanics [77]. The contradiction with quantum mechanics only arises if one insists having sharp foliations at all times, which is not possible in the Everettian theory. Wigner cannot adopt the viewpoint (C) of Alice/Bob, because they are using incompatible bases. Condition (Q) is emergent, but not fundamental in unitary quantum theory. The situation is nicely summarised by Ref's. [119] abstract: "Unperformed measurements have no results. Unobserved results can affect future measurements."

We worked out the relative descriptors for the Frauchiger-Renner thought experiment. In the context of Everettian quantum mechanics, the exercise shows that in experiments where agents have full quantum control over other agents, the branching tree will have both sharp and non-sharp parts. Sharp relative foliations may be defined from entangled composite systems, but not every entangled system foliates sharply. The conclusion one may draw from this is that quantum agents have a blurry memory.

9.4.3 Memory analysis

Let us analyse Alice's memory. For this, let us collect the preparatory information we have on Alice.

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(1)} &= \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(0)} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)_A; \\
\hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(2)} &= \left[\sigma_x^A, \sigma_y^A (\sigma_z^R C - \sigma_x^R S), \sigma_z^A (\sigma_z^R C - \sigma_x^R S) \right]; \quad q_{Az, \pm 1}^{(2)} = \pm \sigma_z^A P_{\pm 1} \left[q_{Rz}^{(2)} \right]; \\
\hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(4)} &= \hat{\mathbf{q}}_A^{(3)} = \left(\hat{q}_{Ax}^{(2)} \hat{U}_{H,S}^{(2)}, \hat{q}_{Ay}^{(2)} \hat{U}_{H,S}^{(2)}, \hat{q}_{Az}^{(2)} \right); \\
\mathbf{q}_A^{(6)} &= \mathbf{q}_A^{(5)} = \left(q_{Ax}^{(4)}, q_{Ay}^{(4)}, q_{Rz}^{(4)}, q_{Az}^{(4)}, q_{Rz}^{(4)} \right); \\
\mathbf{q}_A^{(7)} &= \left(q_{Ax}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{UA}, q_{Ay}^{(4)}, q_{Rz}^{(4)} \sigma_x^{UA}, q_{Az}^{(4)}, q_{Rz}^{(4)} \right); \tag{9.44}
\end{aligned}$$

Let us define a normalized Frobenius product as

$$\langle \dots, \dots \rangle = \frac{1}{3 \dim \mathcal{H}} \langle \dots, \dots \rangle_F. \tag{9.45}$$

Then, we obtain

$$\langle \mathbf{q}_A^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}_A^{(2)} \rangle = \sum_{i=x,y,z} \langle q_{Ai}^{(1)}, q_{Ai}^{(2)} \rangle = \frac{1}{3}, \tag{9.46}$$

which reflects the fact that Alice remembers its x component after suffering the cnot as a target. At $t = 2$, Alice also admits a relative descriptor, for which we can investigate its memory:

$$\langle q_{Az}^{(1)}, q_{Az, \pm 1}^{(2)} \rangle = \pm \frac{1}{6}. \tag{9.47}$$

For the step of the controlled-Hadamard, with Alice as the control, we have

$$\langle \mathbf{q}_A^{(2)}, \mathbf{q}_A^{(4)} \rangle = \frac{1}{3}, \tag{9.48}$$

because she remembers her z component. However,

$$\langle \mathbf{q}_A^{(1)}, \mathbf{q}_A^{(4)} \rangle = 0, \tag{9.49}$$

which means that Alice changed completely as compared to her initial version. The descriptor $\mathbf{q}_A^{(4)}$ is Frobenius orthogonal to $\mathbf{q}_A^{(1)}$. Alice, as a quantum agent, has transformed into something that has nothing to do with the Alice of the past. This teaches us that quantum agents are very volatile as compared to classical agents, whose state remains virtually unchanged. If we repeat the exercise for Wigner, we may verify that his relative descriptions remember Wigner from the past.

Chapter 10

Rudiments of decoherence

The decoherence program treats open quantum systems, and explains how quasi-classicality emerges from quantum theory [75, 106, 107, 109]. It also relates to the quantum Darwinism program that shows how one hopes to derive the Born rule [124, 126–129]. The concept of openness here is akin to the treatment in statistical mechanics, where we use open canonical and grand-canonical ensembles. In the latter, the system under control or interest is subjected to an environment, which has a temperature T and a chemical potential μ . If the subsystem in contact with the environment is in equilibrium with it, the system will acquire the temperature and chemical potential of the environment. Theoretically, one could always consider the combined sub-system plus environment as a global closed system in the microcanonical ensemble. But in practice, this is not possible. All sub-systems are *open* in this sense.

Classical open systems are not always sensitive to their environment. A table is minimally affected by the surrounding air acting as the bath. While changes in air pressure and temperature can eventually lead the table to equilibrate with the new conditions, the relaxation times are large, and the effects are seldom drastic. To illustrate further, imagine a feather exposed to the same environment; it would be significantly more influenced, exhibiting shorter relaxation times. Nevertheless, the key point is that there are classical systems that are scarcely affected by the environment. For instance, the trajectory of a bowling ball is hardly perturbed by photons scattering off its surface, allowing us to effectively ignore the environment. The luxury of ignoring the environment is rarely available for quantum systems.

For quantum systems, unless one is talking about the global quantum state of the universe, quantum sub-systems are fatally open. Even the cosmic microwave background acts as a strong environment for millimetre sized systems. Yet, introductory textbooks begin with isolated quantum systems, such as the particle in a box, as if there were no environment. The formalism of the decoherence program allows us to understand how environments affect the quantum system of interest within the context of unitary quantum mechanics. A simple example are photons scattering off a quantum system, where the photons serve as the bath. The scattering processes inevitably entangles the photons with the surface of the sub-system, which leads to an information flow from the system to the environment. This information flow is decoherence, which manifests as a loss of coherence of the quantum state of the sub-system, leading to quasi-classical behaviour. The relaxation times are so short that they frequently elude experimental resolution.

In this chapter we introduce the rudiments of the decoherence program, and apply it the double-slit experiment and a qubit subjected to a spin environment.

10.1 Pointer states

Consider a quantum system with associated Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_S and an environment described by \mathcal{H}_E . The environment is just as quantum as the system, such that the composite system has the

associated Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_S \otimes \mathcal{H}_E$. Suppose for the moment that the system has not interacted with the environment yet, such that the composite quantum state is of the separable form $|\psi\rangle|E_0\rangle$. Here we omit the product \otimes for brevity. Assume now that $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_1\rangle + |\psi_2\rangle)$, where $|\psi_1\rangle$ is physically sufficiently distinct from $|\psi_2\rangle$, and the system now interacts with the environment. Since both $|\psi_1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle$ have the same phase, one says that the state vector describing the system is coherent. The evolution of the global state is unitary, such that

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_1\rangle + |\psi_2\rangle)|E_0\rangle \longrightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_1\rangle|E_1\rangle + |\psi_2\rangle|E_2\rangle). \quad (10.1)$$

The composite state after evolution in Eq. (10.1) is generally an entangled state between the system and environment, that is, if $|E_1\rangle \neq |E_2\rangle$. If $|E_1\rangle = |E_2\rangle$, then Eq. (10.1) remains separable, which would mean that the environment did not entangle with the system. In the case where the environment entangles maximally with the system, that is $\langle E_1|E_2\rangle = 0$, then the environment records maximal information about the system through the mapping $|\psi_i\rangle|E_i\rangle$. We say that $|E_1\rangle$ encodes information about $|\psi_1\rangle$, and $|E_2\rangle$ encodes information about $|\psi_2\rangle$. For this reason, one says that the environment *monitors* the system. The limit $\langle E_1|E_2\rangle \rightarrow 0$ is also called the decoherent limit, which is the limit of maximal entanglement. The term *decoherence* refers to the fact that since the system is now entangled with the environment, one cannot talk about coherence of the system anymore. Coherence has spread or delocalized from the subsystem to the composite system. Therefore, the sub-system decohered, but the global system remains coherent.

Assume now that we are in the decoherent limit $\langle E_1|E_2\rangle = 0$. The system's quantum states that do not entangle with the environment are said to be robust against decoherence. The states that do entangle with the environment will decohere. For instance, if the state of the system before interaction is $|\psi_1\rangle$, then the evolution will be $|\psi_1\rangle|E_0\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_1\rangle|E_1\rangle$. In this case, one also says that $|E_1\rangle$ was able to monitor the state $|\psi_1\rangle$ perfectly. In the context of unitary quantum interpretation, perfect monitoring means that the environment did not undergo meiosis/differentiation during the interaction. Although $|E_1\rangle$ serves as a monitor, the end state $|\psi_1\rangle|E_1\rangle$ remains separable. Therefore, given the specific environment, we say that the state $|\psi_1\rangle$ is a robust state, since it was not deformed by the environment. The same is true for the evolution $|\psi_2\rangle|E_0\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_2\rangle|E_2\rangle$.

Now, we keep the same environment $|E_0\rangle$, but change the system (basis) states $|\psi_{\pm}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_1\rangle \pm |\psi_2\rangle)$. Will the environment $|E_0\rangle$ be able to perfectly monitor (measure) the new states $|\psi_{\pm}\rangle$, that is, evolve to $|\psi_{\pm}\rangle|E_{\pm}\rangle$? The unitary evolution is now of the form

$$|\psi_{\pm}\rangle|E_0\rangle \longrightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_1\rangle|E_1\rangle \pm |\psi_2\rangle|E_2\rangle), \quad \langle \psi_1|\psi_2\rangle = 0. \quad (10.2)$$

Therefore, the answer is no! The reason is that $|\psi_{\pm}\rangle$ suffers decoherence. The interaction with the environment lead to entanglement.

Let us now establish the relevant nomenclature. We say that $\{|\psi_1\rangle, |\psi_2\rangle\}$ are the preferred states or basis. This basis emerges dynamically from the system-environment interaction. Preferred states are robust against the environment. The associated research program is frequently called environment-induced superselection [124]. The states $\{|\psi_+\rangle, |\psi_-\rangle\}$ are disfavoured by the system-environment interaction, because they decohere/entangle. The preferred states, on the other hand, do not entangle with the environment. Sometimes, the set of preferred states form a basis for the Hilbert space of \mathcal{H}_S . Then, the set is referred to as *pointer basis*. To avoid a possible confusion, superpositions of pointer states are usually not pointer states.

10.2 How to find the pointer states?

Consider now the perhaps more realistic situation where we have three sub-systems composed by the sub-system S , a measurement apparatus A , and an environment E . The interaction of the

uncontrollable environment with the combined system-apparatus states selects preferred combined states such that

$$|s_i\rangle|a_i\rangle|E_0\rangle \longrightarrow |s_i\rangle|a_i\rangle|E_i\rangle. \quad (10.3)$$

Then, $|s_i\rangle|a_i\rangle$ are the combined pointer states of the SA system. A common assumption is that the environment interacts strongly with the apparatus, but negligibly with the system S , such that the apparatus serves as a shield from the environment. Note also that Eq. (10.3) implicitly assumes that the system-apparatus correlations $i \leftrightarrow i$ remain intact after the interaction with the environment. If it weren't so, then the apparatus would hardly qualify as a good measuring device for the system S . However, in real life there is always some interaction between the system S with the environment, which affects the faithfulness of the apparatus by introducing correlations of the $i \leftrightarrow j$ type. The best measurement apparatuses are then those that minimise the $i \leftrightarrow j$ correlations. This also explains why some apparatuses are good to measure a certain basis set, but not others.

We now restrict ourselves to the idealised situation where we might assume that the apparatus-system correlations are always perfect, so that we may ignore the presence of the apparatus for the following analysis. Then, the Hamiltonian for the global system may be written with three parts:

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_S + \mathcal{H}_E + \mathcal{H}_I, \quad (10.4)$$

where \mathcal{H}_S is the Hamiltonian of system S , \mathcal{H}_E describes the environment, and \mathcal{H}_I is the system-environment interaction. The natural question is then: given a Hamiltonian \mathcal{H} , how do we find the system's pointer basis?

10.2.1 The quantum measurement limit

Pointer states

In this limit, the system-environment interaction \mathcal{H}_I dominates the Hamiltonian, such that we write $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_I$ [94]. The task is the following: given \mathcal{H}_I , find the set of preferred states $\{|s_i\rangle\}$ that do not entangle with the environment. In other words, we require that

$$|s_i\rangle|E_0\rangle \longrightarrow |s_i\rangle|E_i(t)\rangle. \quad (10.5)$$

More explicitly, establishing the equality through the unitary evolution $e^{-i\mathcal{H}_I t}$, we have

$$e^{-i\mathcal{H}_I t}|s_i\rangle|E_0\rangle = \lambda_i|s_i\rangle e^{-i\mathcal{H}_I t}|E_0\rangle = |s_i\rangle \underbrace{\lambda_i e^{-i\mathcal{H}_I t}|E_0\rangle}_{|E_i(t)\rangle}, \quad (10.6)$$

where λ_i is the eigenvalue of $|s_i\rangle$ after the action of \mathcal{H}_I . The evolved environment $|E_i(t)\rangle = \lambda_i e^{-i\mathcal{H}_I t}|E_0\rangle$ now explicitly carries information of the system through the eigenvalue λ_i . With this, we recognized that the $\{|s_i\rangle\}$ are eigenstates of \mathcal{H}_I . We also implicitly assumed that \mathcal{H}_I does not explicitly depend on time. The simple analysis in Eq. (10.6) immediately reveals the preferred states. In the measurement limit, the pointer states are the eigenstates of the part of \mathcal{H}_I that belongs to \mathcal{H}_S .

Pointer observable

Also, associated to the pointer basis $\{|s_i\rangle\}$, we may find the *pointer observable* \hat{A}_p . These observables are constructed from the pointer basis, which are eigenvectors of the pointer observable $\hat{A}_p|s_i\rangle = a_i|s_i\rangle$. We may readily verify that these pointer (or preferred) observables have the form

$$\hat{A}_p = \sum_i a_i|s_i\rangle\langle s_i|. \quad (10.7)$$

Problem 10.1: *The commutativity criterion.* Show that the pointer observable \hat{A}_p commutes with the interaction Hamiltonian \mathcal{H}_I , that is

$$[\hat{A}_p, \mathcal{H}_I] = 0. \quad (10.8)$$

Eq. (10.8) shows that the preferred observables are those that commute with the interaction Hamiltonian.

Problem 10.2: *Monitoring of the position.* Interaction Hamiltonians frequently have the form $\mathcal{H}_I = \hat{\mathbf{x}} \otimes \hat{E}$, where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is the position operator acting on \mathcal{H}_S and \hat{E} is the part of the interaction acting on \mathcal{H}_E . Find $|E_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}}(t)\rangle$.

Problem 10.2 explains why some devices, such as our retina, monitor the position eigenvalues, but not for instance momentum eigenvalues. The nature of the system-environment interaction determines the pointer observable, which in this particular case, was the position observable. Such devices are usually ill designed to monitor momentum observables. This partly explains why we see the world in real space, and not reciprocal space. A related discussion can be found in Ref. [58].

10.2.2 The quantum limit of decoherence

In this limit, the self-Hamiltonian of the system \mathcal{H}_S dominates the Hamiltonian [94, 109]. This typically is the case when the wavelengths of the environment are much larger than the ones of the system. Since $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_S$, the environments monitors the eigenstates of \mathcal{H}_S , that is, the energy eigenstates. Most of textbook quantum mechanics is concerned with calculating these energy eigenstates. What the textbooks lack is the discussion on how the slow environment monitors these states. Therefore, the natural observable for these systems is the energy basis.

10.3 The monitored double-slit experiment

We now have all the necessary elements to discuss the famous double-slit experiment. Traditional textbook presentations often emphasize the abrupt changes in the interference pattern, a framing that can introduce unnecessary misconceptions. Our goal here is to address and clarify these misunderstandings. In this setup, the system of interest, described by as \mathcal{H}_S , will be an electron passing through the slits. The environment, which can interact with this system, is the monitor capable of extracting *which-path-information* about the electron's trajectory.

Let us denote the state emerging from slit 1 as $|\psi_1\rangle$, and the state coming from slit 2 as $|\psi_2\rangle$. The environment before interaction with the electron finds itself in a *ready* state $|r\rangle$. If the electron emerges from slit 1 and the environment interacts with it, the evolution is of the non-demolition type $|\psi_1\rangle|r\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_1\rangle|1\rangle$, which means that after the interaction, the environment (or apparatus) switch changed from $r \rightarrow 1$, which reveals information about the electron. Similarly, we have $|\psi_2\rangle|r\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_2\rangle|2\rangle$. From this, we then know that the states $\{|\psi_1\rangle, |\psi_2\rangle\}$ do not entangle with the apparatus, and $\{|\psi_1\rangle, |\psi_2\rangle\}$ is hence the pointer basis with $\langle\psi_1|\psi_2\rangle = 0$.

Problem 10.3: *The pointer observable for the double-slit experiment.* Formulate and interpret the pointer observable correspondent to the pointer basis $\{|\psi_1\rangle, |\psi_2\rangle\}$.

Suppose now that the state emerging from the slits is not $|\psi_1\rangle$, but rather the superposition $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_1\rangle + |\psi_2\rangle)$. The pre-measurement evolution is then

$$|\psi\rangle|r\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_1\rangle + |\psi_2\rangle)|r\rangle \longrightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_1\rangle|1\rangle + |\psi_2\rangle|2\rangle), \quad (10.9)$$

where $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$ are the pointers of the relative states $|\psi_1\rangle|1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle|2\rangle$, respectively. Now, as long as $|1\rangle \neq |2\rangle$, the environment entangles with the electron. The density matrix can then be evaluated:

$$\hat{\rho} = |\Psi\rangle\langle\Psi| = \frac{1}{2} [|\psi_1\rangle\langle\psi_1| \otimes |1\rangle\langle 1| + |\psi_2\rangle\langle\psi_2| \otimes |2\rangle\langle 2| + |\psi_1\rangle\langle\psi_2| \otimes |1\rangle\langle 2| + |\psi_2\rangle\langle\psi_1| \otimes |2\rangle\langle 1|]. \quad (10.10)$$

We would like to calculate expectation values for the electron. For this, we calculate the reduced density matrix for the electron as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\rho}_S = \text{tr}_E(\hat{\rho}) &= \frac{1}{2} [|\psi_1\rangle\langle\psi_1| + |\psi_2\rangle\langle\psi_2| + |\psi_1\rangle\langle\psi_2|\langle 2|1\rangle + |\psi_2\rangle\langle\psi_1|\langle 1|2\rangle] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \langle 2|1\rangle \\ \langle 1|2\rangle & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (10.11)$$

The off-diagonal interference terms exist as long as $\langle 1|2\rangle \neq 0$. If $|1\rangle = |2\rangle$, this would mean that the two pointers were unable to acquire which-path-information, which leads to maximum intensity in the interference pattern. In the other limit, where $\langle 1|2\rangle = 0$, the pointers are orthogonal with respect to each other, meaning that they were able to acquire the maximum amount of which-path-information via entanglement, and in this way obliterating the interference pattern. The intermediary case where $0 < \langle 1|2\rangle < 1$ corresponds to the situation where the pointers acquire partial which-path-information. The more information the pointers acquire, the more the interference pattern deforms.

In the monitored double-slit experiment, we observe a smooth transition from an interference pattern to the decohered limit, where $\langle 1|2\rangle = 0$. Importantly, this transition does not involve a collapse of the wave-function. Instead, what appears as an effective collapse results from a controlled flow of information from the electron to the environment via entanglement. This decoherent limit is sometimes referred to as the *classical limit*. However, it is crucial to recognize that the entire description remains fundamentally quantum. Interestingly, what we term "classical" here arises due to maximal entanglement, a distinctly quantum phenomenon. In essence, quantum behaviour drives classicality, demonstrating that quantum mechanics underpins classical mechanics, not the reverse.

Problem 10.4: *Probability of finding the electron at a position x . Show that*

$$\langle |x\rangle\langle x| \rangle = \langle x|\hat{\rho}_S|x\rangle = \frac{1}{2}|\psi_1(x)|^2 + \frac{1}{2}|\psi_2(x)|^2 + \text{Re}[\psi_1(x)\psi_2^*(x)\langle 2|1\rangle]. \quad (10.12)$$

10.4 Decoherence from spin environments

In the monitored double-slit experiment, we did not specify the Hamiltonian of the global system, which permitted a qualitative understanding of the process. In the next example, however, we will define the interaction Hamiltonian explicitly, allowing us to gain a more detailed understanding of the decoherence factor.

10.4.1 The model

We now discuss one of the simplest, yet most useful decoherence models, which was first developed in Ref. [27]. Here, the system described by \mathcal{H}_S is a qubit. We denote its basis as $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$. The environment is a collection of N spins (or qubits) described by the Hilbert sub-space $\mathcal{H}_E =$

$\mathcal{H}_{E_1} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{E_2} \otimes \dots \otimes \mathcal{H}_{E_N}$. We denote the basis for the environment by $\{|\uparrow\rangle_i, |\downarrow\rangle_i\}$, with $i \in [1, N]$. Then, the Hilbert space is given by

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_S \otimes \mathcal{H}_{E_1} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{E_2} \otimes \dots \otimes \mathcal{H}_{E_N}, \quad \dim(\mathcal{H}) = 2^{N+1}. \quad (10.13)$$

Next, we consider the quantum measurement limit with the interaction Hamiltonian modeled by

$$\mathcal{H}_I = \frac{1}{2} \hat{\sigma}_z \otimes \sum_{i=1}^N g_i \hat{\sigma}_z^{(i)} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \hat{\sigma}_z \otimes \hat{E}, \quad (10.14)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_z = |0\rangle\langle 0| - |1\rangle\langle 1|$ and $\hat{\sigma}_z^{(i)} = (|\uparrow\rangle\langle\uparrow| - |\downarrow\rangle\langle\downarrow|)_i$. The $\{g_i\}$ are coupling constants for which we may choose various distributions to play with. Since $[\hat{\sigma}_z, \mathcal{H}_I] = 0$, we know that the preferred monitored pointer observable of the system qubit is $\hat{\sigma}_z$. In other words, $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ is the qubit's pointer basis, which is robust against the interaction \mathcal{H}_I . Since $[\hat{\sigma}_z, \mathcal{H}_I] = 0$, both the populations and the energies of both the qubit and the environment are conserved.

This model provides an interesting example where the interaction Hamiltonian, \mathcal{H}_I , influences only the coherence of the system, with no particle or energy exchange taking place. Consequently, this is a prime example of an open quantum system with no classical counterpart, where information is the only quantity exchanged; a quantity that, of course, must have a physical instantiation. If we were to naively apply the second law of thermodynamics to this system, we might mistakenly conclude that it is closed, as there is neither heat transfer nor explicit work involved.

10.4.2 The state of the environment

Let us now analyse the eigenstates $|n\rangle$ of the environment \hat{E} . We have

$$\hat{E}|n\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N g_i \hat{\sigma}_z^{(i)} |n\rangle = (g_1 \hat{\sigma}_z^{(1)} + g_2 \hat{\sigma}_z^{(2)} + \dots + g_N \hat{\sigma}_z^{(N)}) |n\rangle. \quad (10.15)$$

Since \hat{E} is diagonal in the basis $\{|\uparrow\rangle_i, |\downarrow\rangle_i\}$, the environmental eigenstates have the product form

$$|n\rangle = |s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_N\rangle = |s_1\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |s_N\rangle = \bigotimes_{i=1}^N |s_i\rangle, \quad (10.16)$$

where $s_i = \{\uparrow, \downarrow\}$. Next, we define

$$n_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s_i = \downarrow \\ 0, & \text{if } s_i = \uparrow \end{cases}, \quad (10.17)$$

such that we may write all possible environmental eigenvalues E_n :

$$\hat{E}|n\rangle = [g_1 (-1)^{n_1} + g_2 (-1)^{n_2} + \dots + g_N (-1)^{n_N}] |n\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N (-1)^{n_i} g_i |n\rangle = E_n |n\rangle, \quad (10.18)$$

where $n = \{s_1, \dots, s_N\} \equiv \{n_1, \dots, n_N\}$.

10.4.3 The global state vector

A basis for the global state vector is therefore $\{|0\rangle \otimes |n\rangle, |1\rangle \otimes |n\rangle\}$. An arbitrary system-environment state can then be written as

$$|\Psi\rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{2^N-1} [c_n |0\rangle \otimes |n\rangle + d_n |1\rangle \otimes |n\rangle], \quad (10.19)$$

where c_n and d_n are complex coefficients. To understand how \mathcal{H}_I entangles the system with the environment, let us assume that the state vector is not entangled (separable) at $t = 0$, that is

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = (a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle) \otimes \sum_{n=0}^{2^N-1} c_n |n\rangle. \quad (10.20)$$

The state vector at arbitrary times t is then found by the unitary evolution

$$|\Psi(t)\rangle = e^{-i\mathcal{H}_I t} |\Psi(0)\rangle = e^{-\frac{i}{2} \hat{\sigma}_z \otimes \hat{E} t} (a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle) \sum_{n=0}^{2^N-1} c_n |n\rangle. \quad (10.21)$$

Using the fact that $\hat{\sigma}_z |0\rangle = -|0\rangle$ and $\hat{\sigma}_z |1\rangle = |1\rangle$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi(t)\rangle &= \left(a|0\rangle e^{\frac{i}{2} \hat{E} t} + b|1\rangle e^{-\frac{i}{2} \hat{E} t} \right) \sum_{n=0}^{2^N-1} c_n |n\rangle \\ &= a|0\rangle \underbrace{\sum_n c_n e^{\frac{i}{2} E_n t} |n\rangle}_{|\varepsilon_0(t)\rangle} + b|1\rangle \underbrace{\sum_n c_n e^{-\frac{i}{2} E_n t} |n\rangle}_{|\varepsilon_1(t)\rangle}. \end{aligned} \quad (10.22)$$

Therefore,

$$|\varepsilon_0(t)\rangle = |\varepsilon_1(-t)\rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{2^N-1} c_n e^{\frac{i}{2} E_n t} |n\rangle. \quad (10.23)$$

Problem 10.5: *Interpretation of the state vector.* In analogy with the monitored double-slit experiment, interpret the meaning of Eq. (10.22).

10.4.4 The decoherence factor

With the global state vector given by Eq. (10.22), we calculate the density matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\rho}(t) &= |a|^2 |0\rangle\langle 0| \otimes |\varepsilon_0\rangle\langle \varepsilon_0| + |b|^2 |1\rangle\langle 1| \otimes |\varepsilon_1\rangle\langle \varepsilon_1| \\ &\quad + ab^* |0\rangle\langle 1| \otimes |\varepsilon_0\rangle\langle \varepsilon_1| + a^* b |1\rangle\langle 0| \otimes |\varepsilon_1\rangle\langle \varepsilon_0|. \end{aligned} \quad (10.24)$$

To calculate the expectation values for the qubit system subjected to the spin environment, we obtain the reduced density matrix

$$\hat{\rho}_S(t) = \text{Tr}_E \hat{\rho}(t) = |a|^2 |0\rangle\langle 0| + |b|^2 |1\rangle\langle 1| + ab^* |0\rangle\langle 1| \langle \varepsilon_1 | \varepsilon_0 \rangle + a^* b |1\rangle\langle 0| \langle \varepsilon_0 | \varepsilon_1 \rangle, \quad (10.25)$$

which is analogous to the double-slit experiment, with the difference that since we specified the Hamiltonian, we now have an explicit expression for the overlap $\langle \varepsilon_1(t) | \varepsilon_0(t) \rangle$. One therefore defines the *decoherence factor* as

$$r(t) = \langle \varepsilon_1(t) | \varepsilon_0(t) \rangle. \quad (10.26)$$

For the present model, the result for the decoherence factor is

$$r(t) = \langle \varepsilon_1(t) | \varepsilon_0(t) \rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{2^N-1} |c_n|^2 e^{iE_n t}, \quad |c_n| \leq 1, \quad \sum_{n=0}^{2^N-1} |c_n|^2 = 1, \quad (10.27)$$

where we used $\langle n | n' \rangle = \delta_{n,n'}$. Also note that only the diagonal elements of the reduced density matrix in Eq. (10.25) are time-independent. This means that in general, coherence and decoherence of the system is a time-dependent phenomena. For this model, we may view the decoherence factor in Eq. (10.27) as a sum of 2^N vectors of length $|c_n|^2$ moving with a frequency E_n .

Case 1: the environment starts in one of its eigenstates

Suppose the environment starts out in one of its eigenstates $|n\rangle$, as for instance:

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = (a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle) \otimes c|n\rangle = (a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle) \otimes [c|\uparrow\rangle_1 \otimes \dots \otimes |\uparrow\rangle_N]. \quad (10.28)$$

You may choose any other environmental eigenstate. Then, from Eq. (10.18) with $n_i = 0$, the eigenvalue of the environment is

$$E_n = \sum_{i=1}^N (-1)^{n_i} g_i = \sum_{i=1}^N g_i = N\bar{g}, \quad (10.29)$$

such that the decoherence factor in Eq. (10.27) yields $r(t) = \exp(iN\bar{g}t)$, which despite having a recurrence time $2\pi/(N\bar{g})$, does not decay. This is of course an accidental situation that does not represent the typical state of a realistic environment. Yet, it helps us in understanding the properties of a typical decoherent environment.

Case 2: all environmental spins in a superposition state

Let us consider another fine-tuned, yet interesting initial condition: all the environmental spins start out in a superposition state with equal coupling strength $g_i = g$ with

$$|\Psi(0)\rangle = (a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle) \bigotimes_{i=1}^N c(|\uparrow\rangle_i + |\downarrow\rangle_i). \quad (10.30)$$

Recall that $n = \{s_1, \dots, s_N\} \equiv \{n_1, \dots, n_N\}$, where n_i is the configuration of a specific environmental spin i . Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} r(t) &= \sum_{n=0}^{2^N-1} |c_n|^2 e^{iE_n t} = \sum_{n=\{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N\}} |c_n|^2 e^{i \sum_{j=1}^N (-1)^{n_j} g t} \\ &= \sum_{n_1=1}^N |c_{n_1}|^2 e^{i(-1)^{n_1} g t} \dots \sum_{n_N=1}^N |c_{n_N}|^2 e^{i(-1)^{n_N} g t} = \left[\sum_{n_1=1}^N |c_{n_1}|^2 e^{i(-1)^{n_1} g t} \right]^N \end{aligned} \quad (10.31)$$

Moreover, n_1 in Eq. (10.30) includes the possibility of a superposition state, such that $n_1 = \{0, 1\}$, such that we write

$$\begin{aligned} r(t) &= \left[\sum_{n_1, \nu=1}^N \sum_{\nu=0,1} |c_{n_1, \nu}|^2 e^{i(-1)^{n_1, \nu} g t} \right]^N = [N(|c_{1,0}|^2 e^{igt} + |c_{1,1}|^2 e^{-igt})]^N \\ &= [N|c_{1,0}|^2 2 \cos(gt)]^N = \underbrace{(2N|c_{1,0}|^2)}_1 \cos^N(gt). \end{aligned} \quad (10.32)$$

Note that this model has a revival time of $\tau = 2\pi/g$.

Problem 10.6: *Estimating the decoherence and revival times.* Expand $r(t) = \cos^N(gt)$ around a time where $|r| = 1$ (full coherence) up to second order to show that coherence is lost after a time

$$t_d = \frac{1}{g} \sqrt{\frac{2}{N}}. \quad (10.33)$$

Figure 10.1: The decoherence factor $r(t)$ for $N = 1$ (dashed-blue) and $N = 100$ (solid-red), for the case where the environmental spins start out in a superposition state with equal coupling to the system.

Case 3: the random walk

A more realistic situation is when the $\{g_i\}$ follow a random distribution concentrated about a mean value. Then, Eq. (10.27) corresponds to a random walk in the complex plane. Ref. [27] worked out the decoherence factor for this case and showed that $r(t)$ follows a Gaussian decay

$$r(t) \approx e^{-(t/t_d)^2}, \quad (10.34)$$

where the characteristic decay time t_d depends on the specific distribution $\{g_i\}$ and the initial condition. Even here, there is always a recurrence time τ , but that in realistic situation scales with $\tau \sim N!$, which can easily surpass cosmological times [124].

10.5 Discussion

The brute force decoherence program has the following pragmatic steps:

1. Write the initial uncorrelated state;
2. Determine the entangled state at arbitrary times;
3. Write the entangled system-environment density matrix;
4. Trace out the environment and identify the decoherence factor;
5. Calculate the decoherence factor.

Environment	Blood cells, bacteria, droplets, hair, ... (10^{-6}m)	Sand, insects, seeds, dust, ... (10^{-4}m)
Cosmic background	10^{24}s	1s
Light (photons)	10^6s	10^{-18}s
Vacuum (laboratory)	10^{-2}s	10^{-14}s
Air (sound)	10^{-19}s	10^{-31}s

Table 10.1: Typical decoherence times for different environments. Reproduced from Ref. [109].

In this chapter we illustrated the program for the monitored double-slit experiment and the spin environment model. One can sophisticate the treatment and formulate a master-equation for the reduced density matrix. For this, refer the reader to Ref. [109].

Realistic decoherence times are astonishing. For discussion purposes, we mention some examples taken from Ref. [109]; see Tab. 10.1. For micrometer sized systems such as bacteria, droplets and blood cells, the cosmic background radiation or photons at room temperature are unable to decohere the system. Yet, as soon there are particles involved, even those of the best laboratory vacuum, micrometer sized system decohere fast. A bacteria subjected to air at room temperature decoheres at 0.1 attoseconds, which is at the limit of today's technology. In contrast, a dust particle of size 0.1 mm, which is visible to the naked eye decoheres in 10^{-31}s , which is way beyond experimental capability.

From the experimental point of view, decoherence times occur instantly, which partly explains why instantaneous collapse interpretations seemed reasonable at first. A related discussion can be found in Ref. [125].

10.5.1 Implications for orthodox interpretations of quantum mechanics

What are the implications of what we learned from the decoherence programme to the interpretation of quantum mechanics? In orthodox Copenhagen-type interpretations, the collapse is discontinuous, the outcome of the measurement is random, the probabilities are provided by the Born rule, the meaning of measurement is unclear, and because of this, the cause of a collapse is also obscure. Moreover, it is the user who chooses the observable to be measured, which determines a basis. In other words, the choice of the user determines the system's properties. However, decoherence teaches us that it is the system-apparatus interaction that determines the preferred observables that are able to maintain a record of the system.

Copenhagen also states that classicality is irreducible, that is, classical mechanics cannot be obtained from quantum mechanics. In fact, the *classical world* is more fundamental. Because of the Heisenberg cut, unitary von Neumann evolutions are not allowed. In contrast, the decoherence informs us that environment-induced superselection and suppression of coherence give rise to quasi-classical states.

Appendix A

Superdeterminism

A.1 The ψ -ensemble interpretation

Superdeterminism is not usually considered an interpretation of quantum mechanics. Instead, it is a more fundamental deterministic theory than quantum mechanics. A particular implementation of superdeterminism, the ψ -ensemble interpretation [63], is a ψ -epistemic theory in the sense that the wave-function emerges from more fundamental hidden variable constituents. The distinctive property of superdeterministic theories is that they violate statistical independence, that is, they have the property $\rho(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \lambda) \neq \rho(\lambda)$ [63, 71, 72, 122]. Therefore, the derivations leading to the Bell's inequality in Eq. (3.11) are inapplicable. A superdeterministic expectation value is exempt from violating Bell-type inequalities. Technology permitting, expectation values that satisfy Eq. (3.11) could experimentally favour superdeterminism.

Let us adopt the hidden variables collectively described by $\kappa(t)$ as presented in the ψ -ensemble interpretation [63]. We denote the hidden variables by $\kappa(t)$ (just as in Ref. [63]), because they are slightly less general than Bell's hidden variables $\lambda(t)$. The difference does not concern us here. The $\kappa(t)$ determine the outcomes at the time of measurement. For the pair of particles in the Bell test, the two possible outcomes are specified in the state $|\psi\rangle = (|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$. Let us denote the cluster of hidden variables leading to the outcome $|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle$ as $\{\kappa\}_{\uparrow\downarrow}$, and $\{\kappa\}_{\downarrow\uparrow}$ to $|\downarrow\uparrow\rangle$. The hidden variables deterministically map to a definite measurement outcome at the time of measurement. This is how superdeterminism solves the problem of outcomes [109]. Observing the state $|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle$ reveals information (through the mapping) about the value of the hidden variable at the time of measurement. These hidden variables are causally local because the information about the settings (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) was already available at the time the entangled state was prepared through local interactions.

Because the ψ -ensemble interpretation has more elements than quantum mechanics, predictions other than standard quantum mechanics are theoretically possible. In standard quantum mechanics, an ensemble of identically prepared states will generally admit different outcomes. In the ψ -ensemble interpretation, they are actually not identical, because they had different hidden variable values that originated different outcomes. One could then think of situations between consecutive measurements for which standard quantum mechanics predicts different results between measurements, but in which, in the ψ -ensemble interpretation, the hidden variables would not have time to change their cluster. Therefore, superdeterminism could be testable in situations where the hidden variables do not change between measurements. The details of such an experimental proposal can be found in Refs. [69, 70].

Some of the most common objections raised against superdeterminism include conspiracy arguments and more recently cosmic Bell tests [99]. Responses to these objections can be found in Ref. [72]. This is an ongoing discussion that we do not further address here.

A.2 Locality

Superdeterminism, Bohmian mechanics, and Everettian mechanics are not Bell-local, but they all allow for local information flow. Superdeterminism breaks statistical independence, and information is processed locally by the hidden variables, rendering it non-Bell-local. Bohmian mechanics features non-local hidden variables, but the pilot-wave facilitates the local transport of information. Everettian mechanics lacks Bell-locality due to the absence of a preferred foliation, leading to multiple measurement outcomes. However, both superdeterminism and Everettian mechanics qualify as local theories according to the broader sense of Einstein locality principles, such as the one mentioned in Sec. 8.1. Similarly, in relational mechanics and Qubism, the significance of measurement outcomes is contingent upon a specific observer's perspective.

A.3 Ingredients of theories

The most up-to-date no-go theorems do not exclude the possibility of quantum formulations admitting a local information flow. Yet despite alternative options (see Tab. 3.3), Bell's 1964 results continue to be advertised for quantum non-locality [19], which is a property of collapse/handshake interpretations. In Sec. 3.6, we showed how current no-go theorems provide us with four viable categories. We have given one example from each of the categories (A), (B) and (D), that allow for a local information flow.

In the ψ -ensemble interpretation, information flows locally via the hidden variables. In superdeterminism, the Schrödinger (or Heisenberg) equation is not all there is. The wavefunction is an emergent average description of an yet unresolved additional structure – the hidden variables. They are not required to comply with Bell's 1964 theorem, because they break the assumption of statistical independence. This comes with correlations that lack in theories admitting statistical independence. Superdeterminism makes peculiar predictions, which might be tested in the future [69, 70].

If one dismisses the additional correlations that come with superdeterminism but maintains hidden variables, then Bell's result enforces a theory with non-local effects, such as Bohmian mechanics. Unlike superdeterminism, where the hidden variables determine the quantum state, in Bohmian mechanics, the wave pilots the particles, which leads to non-local effects on the particles, but not on the waves.

Further, if one gets rid of the Bohmian particles, one is left with the Schrödinger equation only (or the Heisenberg equations of motion). One possible interpretation is Everettian mechanics, where the recording of measurement outcomes on decoherent foliations has no longer precedence over the recording on other foliations. In Fig. A.1 we depict how the stripping down of ingredients from the mathematical formalism takes us from correlated hidden variables to the bare foliations.

For the next section, we drop Bohmian mechanics from the discussion, because of its apparent incompatibility with the locality principles from relativity, and the difficulty of formulating guiding equations within the mathematical methods of quantum field theory. Then, for discussion purposes, this leaves us with superdeterministic and Everettian-type quantum theories.

A.4 Philosophical analysis

One of the reasons behind the proliferation of quantum interpretations is that there is no consensus on the philosophy of science. Contrasting superdeterminism and Everettian mechanics not only allows us to use a test to falsify one of them, but also contrast different philosophies of science. Although both superdeterminism and Everettian mechanics provide a causal, deterministic, and local description of quantum mechanics, both are frequently overlooked.

Figure A.1: Comparison of the ingredients of the formalisms in the (a) ψ -ensemble interpretation, (b) Bohmian mechanics and (c) Everettian mechanics. (a) The cluster of hidden variables $\{\kappa\}_{\uparrow\downarrow}$ is illustrated by the blue and green disks, which determine the state $|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle$. The $\{\kappa\}_{\uparrow\downarrow}$ correlate with the detector settings (**a**, **b**), which violates statistical independence. The dotted relative state represents a counterfactual possibility. (b) In Bohmian mechanics, one gains statistical independence. The hidden variables are the particle's positions $X_A(t)$ and $X_B(t)$. (c) In Everettian mechanics only the foliations remain.

To avoid subjectivity, let us state two philosophies of science: instrumentalist views usually adopted by advocates of superdeterminism [72], and explanatory approaches adopted by Everettians [40, 121]. Instrumentalism is motivated by what we observe, and the role of experiments is to increase credence in favour of a particular theory. In this view, better theories are the ones that give better predictions. In contrast, Deutsch's philosophy of science builds on Popper, and regards fundamental science as explanatory [37, 40]. The purpose of science is then not mapped to a particular prediction, but to conjecture explanations that specify an ontology and how it behaves. Theories that follow this philosophy do not rely on credence. Instead of finding a theory with high credence, scientific methodology finds flaws and deficiencies in a given explanation and seeks to replace it with a better one. There is no guarantee there is something as the *truth*, let alone a natural evolution towards it through this methodology. However, it does allow us to consistently compare different theories.

Before making the philosophical analysis using Deutsch's philosophy, we summarise how, within this approach, one of two rival theories might be refuted. Deutsch draws from Popper's scientific methodology in which a good theory is never confirmed; instead, bad theories are refuted and replaced by better theories. Paraphrasing Ref. [40], a bad theory is one that:

- (i) does not account for the objects of the explanation; or
- (ii) conflicts with other good theories (theories that observe the opposites of criteria (i) and (iii));
or,
- (iii) is easy to vary.

If a theory displays at least one of the properties above, then it can be made problematic, which then motivates a scientific problem. Therefore, a scientific theory can only be refuted if it has a better rival according to these criteria. If it has no rival, it can at most be made problematic by the same criteria. A crucial scientific test could be an experiment that allows the identification of a better theory.

We now use Deutsch's philosophy of Ref. [40] to contrast superdeterminism with Everettian mechanics, which according to the criteria above, allows for a crucial test to make one of them problematic. For the experimental proposal in Refs. [69, 70], one measures the z and x component of a spin observable σ alternately. In Everettian mechanics, the outcomes of the alternating measurements are uncorrelated. This is because the eigenstates of σ_z are not eigenstates of σ_x . In superdeterminism, a sufficiently short time between measurements prevents the hidden variables to change their cluster. Estimates of timescales can be found in Refs. [69, 70]. Therefore, assuming that such short timescales can be experimentally achieved, superdeterminism predicts the same result

between measurements, whereas Everettian mechanics generally predicts different results. If the experiment repeatedly observes the same result, this would be consistent with both superdeterminism and Everettian mechanics. However, superdeterminism would be a better explanation (according to criteria (i)), because it would clarify why only a single result was observed. The explanation is that the hidden variables remained in the same cluster. According to Deutsch's criteria (i), Everettian mechanics would be refuted, because it could not account for the object of the explanation; in this case, the hidden variables. If only superdeterminism is left as a good unrivalled theory, it cannot be refuted. Superdeterminism could, at most, be made problematic by criteria (i) - (iii). However, if the experiment observes different results, which is the state of the art, then superdeterminism is refuted by criteria (ii) and (iii). The argument can be repeated for other quantum descriptions, such as collapse variants [40].

A.5 Conclusion

Quantum no-go theorems are perhaps the most powerful tools so far to differentiate and test both modifications of quantum mechanics, and quantum mechanics itself. The most famous no-go theorem is Bell's 1964 inequality, which imposes restrictions on modifications of quantum mechanics. This is understood in the niche community studying the foundations of quantum mechanics but seems to be misunderstood in the larger physics community. We reviewed recent interpretive claims based on Bell's original inequality. The dominant view seems to conclude from Bell's theorems that quantum mechanics itself must be non-local. This motivated us to survey recent advances in local quantum theories and present at least two counter-examples with active research programs. Under currently used philosophies of physics, there are at least two quantum descriptions that are local, casual and deterministic. Superdeterminism escapes Bell's inequality by violating statistical independence. This allows for a hidden variable program that saves the principle of locality, which possibly helps the compatibility with general relativity. However, even unitary quantum mechanics itself admits a mode of description, namely the Heisenberg representation, which is local. A local realist interpretation of the Heisenberg picture is Everettian mechanics.

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